

School of Health and Life Sciences

Leadership in Midwifery: A Foucauldian perspective

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Abstract

Title: Leadership in Midwifery, a Foucauldian Perspective.

Background:

There is a growing body of opinion that leadership has a role in high quality healthcare. There have been several cases where investigations in healthcare, including maternity care by Kirkup in 2015 and Ockenden in 2022, have highlighted failures and that poor leadership has been implicated in those failures. The first instance of the current trend in compassionate leadership is in *Developing People: improving care* published by the NHS Leadership Academy in 2016. Formal reviews by Francis in 2013 and Kirkup in 2015 noted that pressurising management approaches lacked the compassion that healthcare ironically aimed to deliver, and this was mirrored by Sir Ron Kerr's findings in 2018 when he noted a top-down culture of bullying extending to those working in national bodies influencing the NHS in England. The Messengers review of NHS leadership in England is arguably even more direct in supporting previous assertions. Whatever leadership actually is, it does not appear on the healthcare policy landscape until 2008 and is currently still being defined and recalibrated in its application to healthcare. There are few published studies which engage with Foucault's approach in midwifery research. A search of CINAHL for example in 2022, showed none in the UK.

Aim:

The aim of the thesis is to critically examine leadership in midwifery using the concepts of Michel Foucault.

Methods:

The thesis followed two phases of research. Phase 1 being a critical examination of the documentary policy landscape, in terms of for example, the work of the Nursing Midwifery Council (NMC), The Professional Standards Agency, NHS policy, NHS Leadership Academy, Government policy, academia, and the Royal College of Midwives (RCM), as well as the major

investigations into maternity care. Phase 2 consisted of 13 semi-structured interviews with midwifery leaders from these organisations. Both phases adopted Foucault's concepts and ideas as an analytic approach.

Findings:

Leadership is an ambiguous construct in the discourse of professional midwifery and is often obfuscated with managerial titles and responsibilities. The use of collaborative and compassionate leadership practice appears to be as a result of rationalities of governing which have the effect of de-professionalising midwifery practice by impinging on professional discretionary spaces.

Contribution to professional practice:

Foucault's method of applying critique is by problematisation. As he pointed out in his lectures on *Technologies of the self* in 1982, he used problematisation as "*a matter of pointing out what kinds of assumptions, what kinds of familiar, unchallenged, unconsidered modes of thought on which the practices we accept rest.*" These findings will be of interest to professional midwives as individual leaders, and to the profession, and it is hoped that it will make a positive contribution by stimulating critique of unchallenged assumptions and modes of thought.

Index of Abbreviations

AEI	Approved Education Institution
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CINAHL	Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature
CQC	Care Quality Commission
DCA	Directed Content Analysis
FT	Foundation Trust
GMC	General Medical Council
HIS	Healthcare Improvement Scotland
HSSIB	Health Service Safety Investigation Branch
LME	Lead Midwife for Education
MBRRACE-UK	Mothers and Babies: Reducing Risk through Audits and Confidential Enquiries UK
NES	NHS Education for Scotland
NHS	National Health Service
NICE	National Institute for Health & Care Excellence
NMC	Nursing Midwifery Council
NPM	New Public Management
NRS	National Records for Scotland
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation & Development
PASO	Parliamentary Health Service Ombudsman
PSA	Professional Standards Authority for Health & Social Care
RCM	Royal College of Midwives
SARS CoV-2	Severe Acute Respiratory Disorder, Coronavirus, Variant No 2
UK	United Kingdom
UKCC	United Kingdom Central Council
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment

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“Humans are born free, but everywhere they are in chains”

Jean-Jacques Rousseau

Chapter 1. Introduction

This chapter outlines the relevant professional context of the thesis as well as a rationale for choosing to use the works of Michel Foucault. It also highlights the aim of the thesis.

1.1 Professional context

Subject to the many iterations of definition, credibility, and competency, as well as political, organisational, and public expectations, midwifery is an occupation based on supporting women in pregnancy and childbirth. Its role in history has been recognised, as the oldest chronicled female occupation (Thomas, 2009; Bannon, Alerdice & McNeill, 2017). And although there are a very small number of midwives who operate independently, the majority practice professionally in some form of maternity-focused care in the United Kingdom (UK) in the National Health Service (NHS).

There is a growing body of opinion that leadership has a role in high quality healthcare (NHS England, 2015; Sonnino, 2016; Alilyyani, Wong & Cummings, 2018). There have been several cases where healthcare, including maternity care, has been deemed to have failed and where poor leadership has been implicated in that failure. The first of these was Lord Darzi's review in 2008 which recommended investment in clinical leadership in undergraduate nursing and medicine (Darzi, 2008). Subsequent to this however, leadership is somewhat barren in the healthcare policy landscape until an apparent cluster of reviews and recommendations from 2013-2015 (Francis, 2013; Kirkup, 2015; Keogh, 2013; Berwick, 2013; Smith, 2015). This culminated in Lord Rose's review in 2015 which suggested good leaders should be rewarded across the NHS (Rose, 2015). The first instance of the current trend in compassionate leadership is in *Developing People: improving care* (NHS Leadership Academy, 2016). Both Francis (2013) and Kirkup (2015) noted that pressurising management approaches lacked the compassion that healthcare ironically aimed to deliver, and this was mirrored by Sir Ron Kerr's findings in 2018 when he noted a top-down culture of bullying extending to those working in national bodies influencing the NHS in England (Kerr, 2018). A year later the Kark Review (2019) suggested senior leaders should be subject to assessment and training in leadership. And finally in the Messenger Review (2022), heralded as the largest full-scale review of NHS

leadership in England ever undertaken. Whatever leadership actually is, it does not appear on the healthcare policy landscape until 2008 and is currently still being defined and recalibrated in its application. And whilst links can be made to leadership in maternity care in improving outcomes (Hardacre 2011; Horton, 2013), some can also be made to harming subordinates, particularly in corporate cultures (Nyberg, Bernin & Theorell, 2005; Nauman, Fatima & Haq, 2018). In a recent review, poor leadership based on authoritarian models and financial pressure had seemingly improved little in maternity care (Shannon, Alderdice & McNiells, 2017). Likewise, institutionalised bullying in maternity services has been previously linked to dominance leadership and management tactics (Curtis, Ball & Kirkham, 2008; Martin & Martin, 2010). NHS England's national maternity review linked poor leadership to bad morale (NHS England, 2015). In March 2015 the former CEO of the Royal College of Midwives wrote, "*We need leaders who are courageous, who are not content with the status quo and who will work with others to create the necessary changes*" (Warwick, 2015). But there has been a shift in midwifery leadership, in particular around the evidence of the positive health outcomes of midwifery-led care (Brocklehurst, 2011; Tracy, Welsh & Hall, 2014) or that for midwifery-led continuity of care models (Sandal et al, 2015). Therefore leadership, in an institutional sense, is a prevalent idea or set of ideas in the National Health Service, and yet it is unclear exactly which role it should or does play in midwifery and in what way.

1.2 Michel Foucault as rationale

Most research approaches are immersed in epistemological principles and theoretical assumptions which at the same time both guide *and* constrain the knowledge gained from endeavour (Kuhn, 2012; Lincoln, Lynham & Guba, 2011). Scientific enquiry, be it paradigmatically positivist or otherwise, is encased in ideology. By that is meant the unconscious domination of the possible range of thoughts about a subject or discipline becoming entrenched in a specified scientific discourse (Potochnik, 2020). Foucault outlines his critical thoughts on the philosophical and epistemological limitations of traditional scientific enquiry in *The Order of Things* (Foucault, 1970). Consequently, Foucault's central theoretical construct is that of discourse, and he views its boundaries as beyond those of text statements, seeing text and language for example as but one component of discourse. He has used discourse in a number of ways to show assemblages of power relations and the ways in which these become normalised as social practices in organised spaces such as the military,

hospitals, schools, and factories. Foucault asks us to examine more than things said and to highlight these in the context and contingencies in which they were said (Kelly, 1994; Stahl, 2008). However, most discourse analyses begin with a researcher questioning some set of social practices and their wider relationships with social structures (Fairclough 2001; Wodack & Myer, 2015). Foucault's concepts, tools and philosophy would allow a researcher to position midwifery and its subsequent leadership attempts as a discourse within a social and political structure. In doing so, the other tools in his work allow the specific exploration of power and its relationship to knowledge within that discourse. As part of a professional doctorate then, Foucault's work allows a researcher to apply critique to professional groups and how individuals are subjectified in their professions, as well as how the profession can be governed in the wider discourse of a political society.

1.3 The aim of the thesis

Aim: To critically examine leadership in midwifery using the concepts of Michel Foucault.

Objectives:

- To critique the topic of leadership in midwifery using discourse and critically analyse power/knowledge relations within that discourse
- To problematise Foucault's concept of subjectivity within a midwifery leadership discourse using his concept of governmentality.

Summary

Chapter 1 has outlined the professional context, and rationale for selecting Michel Foucault's work as well as the thesis aim. Chapter 2 refines Foucault's broad philosophical ideas to a form of theoretical framework from which to launch to critique and analysis of midwifery leadership and presents the methods used in applying it. Chapter 3 critiques the discourse of leadership in the literature. Chapter 4 refines and applies Foucault's concepts of power in establishing midwifery leadership as discourse, followed by his application of governmentality to the concept of subjectivity in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 shows the findings from participant interview and finally Chapter 7 then offers a critical synthesis and discussions of the entire thesis.

Chapter 2. Methods

Introduction

This chapter refines and justifies Foucault's work toward a theoretical framework and method of analysis. It firstly provides a brief introduction to Foucault, followed by the theoretical framework. It then outlines the methods of participant recruitment, documentary selection for critique and the subsequent ways in which this was structured and analysed.

2.1 Foucault

On reflecting on his work two years before his death, Michel Foucault noted, "*I tried to locate three types of problems: the problem of truth, the problem of power and the problem of individual conduct*" (Foucault, 1982). Foucault was educated when academia was immersed in the workings of Hegelians like Marx and Husserl, Habermas and the Frankfurt School, and Nietzsche. Of Nietzsche he claimed that, rather than write about his work, he used his ideas as analytical tools to think with. Foucault was a historian, philosopher, writer, activist, and critic (Jardine, 2010; Olssen 2010). Some have claimed an unwillingness on Foucault's behalf to define his research methods (Tambuukou, 1999; Graham, 2013) with some going as far as referring to his approach as 'methodological anarchy' (Thomas, 1997). Foucault claimed in one interview to disliked prescription, "*I take care not to dictate how things should be*" and whilst being critical to the point of provocation his focus was on disrupting equilibrium "*so that all those who speak for others or to others no longer know what to do*" (Foucault, 1994, p.228). However, as Veyne (2010) points out, Foucault was neither bound in structuralist ideals, nor was he a relativist or historicist, but he was undoubtedly a sceptic. Even that was challenged by one of his biggest critics, Habermas (1978), who claimed that a permanent perspective of scepticism was impossible. But, as Olssen (2006) explains, Habermas, even as his staunchest critic, on Foucault's passing in 1984, wrote, "*...within the circle of philosophers of my generation who diagnose our times, Foucault has most lastingly influenced the Zeitgeist*" (Habermas, 1986, p.107; cited in Olssen, 2006). However, Foucault never claimed to be producer of, nor subservient to, a grand theory in search of understanding (Biesta, 2008) and he is well known in rejecting 'grand narratives' (Ball, 2013).

2.2 Theoretical framework

In order that Foucault's thoughts and ideas can be deployed in the examination of midwifery leadership, it is first necessary to distil some core concepts from that work to provide a focus and critical rationale for analysis.

"I would like my books to be a kind of toolbox which others can rummage through to find a tool which they can use however they wish in their own area... I write for users, not reader" (Foucault. 1974, pp. 523-524).

Michel Foucault's work provides a valuable toolbox for theorising the topic of midwifery leadership, in particular it is helpful in challenging those who would ascribe value to it, or equally those who would dismiss it. Foucault's work is able to reveal some of the problematic and questionable issue of attempting to influence such a complex professional domain in the context of public sector healthcare. It can do this by focussing on meaning production, power effects, truth claims and knowledge systems as being the centre of both thinking and techniques of investigation. And by using a Foucauldian perspective of discourse as framing such things, it can emphasise the production of meaning, strategies of power and the propagation of knowledge (Foucault, 1978). As Rainbow (1997) points out, in Foucault's professorial position as Chair of 'The History of Systems of Thought' at the College de France, Foucault was clearly interested in systems of thought or sets of knowledges that influence how the world is understood. Foucault's work is vast, and whilst it can be seen to evolve in thought and approach three fundamental elements of that are presented here as theoretical pillars from which to problematise leadership in midwifery: **discourse**, **power/knowledge**, and **subjectivity**.

Foucault demonstrates problematisation as an approach to critique in *The History of Madness* (Foucault, 1961). However, Foucault's approach of problematisation saw him question socio-political knowledge trends, not for continuity, but for perturbations in such things, for points of rupture, as he explains for *"displacements and transformations of concepts"* (Foucault, 1972, p.4). This legitimises the inspection of *'moments of discontinuity and change in political, economic, institutional, and societal practices'* (Motion & Leitch, 2007, p.263). For Foucault

problematization is the core application of critique. In an interview in 1984 with Francois Ewald he speaks of his entire body of work stating, *"The notion common to all the work that I have done since History of Madness is that of problematization"* (Lawler & Nale, 2014, p.399). Critique for Foucault was, *"a matter of pointing out what kinds of assumptions, what kinds of familiar, unchallenged, unconsidered modes of thought on which the practices we accept rest"* (Foucault, 1988, p. 154). Problematization as a form of critique and involves, *"posing questions, of reflecting on and accounting for how certain systems of thought and practices come to be conceived in a particular way"* (Motion & Leitch, 2007, p. 265). Or, as Foucault states, it highlights *"the conditions in which human beings 'problematize' what they are, what they do, and the world in which they live"* (Foucault, 1984, p. 10). Foucault (1996) explained that his interest was in how particular discourses and associated practices came to be accepted as true or legitimate. The importance of the concept of problematization in a theoretical sense is that rather than limit the scope of investigation by preordained methods it allows the fundamental questions to be considered, such as why the notion of leadership is deemed suitable to be applied to a profession at all. Instead, rather than apply limits the sorts of questions asked, Foucault's perspective guides us toward the places and phenomena that should be considered worthy to question; and those are discourse, power/knowledge and subjectivity. Each will be taken in turn to legitimise this theoretical framework.

2.2.1 Discourse

According to Foucault, discourse comprises of sets of statements that form the objects, concepts, subjects, and strategies of which they speak. But they are also, *"governed by analysable rules and transformations"* (Foucault, 1972, p. 211). However, he also points out that discourses can be identified by the rules of formation of these things, and that such rules are 'systems of thought'. Moreover, these statements have certain regularity, and as Olssen (2010, p. 10) explains, *"Discourses pertain both to the rules of language and speech and embody both the formal systems of signs and social practices that govern its use"*. And as Venye, (2010) explains, any material object cannot be separated from the framing of the ways in which we come to know of it, and it is this premise upon which Foucault's concept of discourse is based. Some elaborate that discourse is an institutionalised and regulated exercising of power, of ways of thinking, talking, and acting (Arribas-Ayllon & Walkerdine, 2017). Importantly discourses therefore limit what can be said, who can speak, and the

positions from which they can speak, and can contain the interests of institutional domains (Motion and Leitch, 2007). As Foucault points out, his approach was to search for “*instances of discursive production, the production of power and the propagation of knowledge*” (Foucault, 1984, p.12). In viewing midwifery leadership as a discourse, Fairclough (1992) highlights useful points for analysis in conceptualising the discourse as a ‘meaning creation process’ with ideational, relational and identity functions. For example, midwifery leadership in its ideational function would relate to better birthing outcomes for women. Its relational function would relate to sets of power relations in terms of stakeholders within the discourse, namely midwife with woman, and midwife with government. Finally, its identity function would be a professional identity alongside that of a public sector employee. However, in considering such things even at the stage of a theoretical framework, this leads to questions of how midwifery itself is viewed. By that is meant questioning if midwifery is an occupation which needs to be managed, or as nested in the art and science of professionalism. However, discourse transformations further refine the utility of seeing discourse as a point analysis. Accordingly, Motion and Leitch (2007, p.266) highlight the value in considering changes in discourses, noting Foucault's views of “*mapping the displacement of boundaries, the new positions and roles made available for speaking subjects in the discourse, new modes of language, and new forms for circulating the discourse*”. Discourse transformations include the establishment of new procedures of “*separating out from among all the statements which are possible those that will be acceptable*” (Foucault 1972: 197). Fairclough's (1992, p.8; 2013) explanation of Foucauldian analyses of discourse transformations creates the possibility of considering intentional efforts to engineer socio-cultural change as the “*technologization of discourse*” by ‘*professional technologists who research, redesign, and provide training in discourse practices*’. This is beneficial in directing critique toward midwifery leadership and its complex relations with government and wider public sector healthcare.

2.2.2 Power/Knowledge and Truth

The use of the word power is often associated with dominance, oppression, or superiority; however, for Foucault, power is specifically both productive and positive.

“What makes power hold good, what makes it accepted, is simply the fact that it doesn't only weigh on us as a force that says no, but that it traverses and produces

things, it induces pleasure, forms knowledge, produces discourse” (Foucault, 1980, p. 119).

For Foucault, power is exercised and not necessarily held and is seen by Foucault as an underlying part of human existence. Some authors have pointed out that Foucault's work on power has evolved and is used in fields of application differently in terms of the ways in which it is exercised in discourse (Gallagher, 2008). The point, however, of Foucault's power is that it challenged the notion of it as being both limited and as possessed by a selected few. Equally important is power's inseparability from knowledge and its visibility in institutional apparatus.

“The university hierarchy is only the most visible ... and least dangerous form of this phenomenon. One has to be really naïve to imagine that the effects of power linked to knowledge have their culmination in university hierarchies” (Foucault, 1980, p. 52).

Knowledge is therefore both the creator and a creation of power, whilst power is both a creator and creation of knowledge. His main works which illustrate this power/knowledge dynamic were focused on hospitals, the asylum and prisons (Foucault, 1972; 1974). However, the concept of power/knowledge was later clarified as relational by the inclusion of strategy. By that is meant Foucault claims both individuals and organisation as being able to deploy power/knowledge strategies through discourses, either to circumvent or comply with existing power/knowledge relations. As Clegg, Courpasson and Phillips (2006) point out, using the concept of discourse makes visible the strategies of transformation, creation, and resistance in power/knowledge relations. Clearly, as midwifery is a longstanding professional discipline, those professionals play a significant role in power/knowledge processes in the discourse of midwifery leadership, however as they practice within public healthcare, they are not the only 'discourse technologists' (Fairclough 1992; 2013). Likewise, when considering macro-level states of apparently dominating power/knowledge relations, it is easy to be drawn toward forms of hegemony (Gramsci, 1971). However, Foucault's works draws toward the micro-level, and the power/knowledge relations operating via the construction and acceptance of truths. Of his attempts to problematise truth Foucault (1988) notes;

“Truth is no doubt a form of power. And I think that, instead of trying to find out what truth, as opposed to error, is, it might be more interesting to take up the problem posed by Nietzsche: how is it that, in our societies, ‘the truth’ has been given this value, thus placing us in its thrall?” (p. 107).

The value of the truth arguments in this theoretical framework and in critique of midwifery leadership is identifying the value place upon truth and the subsequent influence in discourse. But it also allows visibility of cross-discursive power/knowledge relations, for example the discourse of law and discourse of government. For example, the discourse of law valorises the knowledge ruling of a judge in a way which, in social discourse, is held in greater value than that, say, of an individual midwife. In this way it is possible to see the value attached to truth as central to a power/knowledge relation. Therefore, through a discourse lens it becomes possible to explore the forces impacting on midwifery as a profession as it strives to form particular truths and alter power/knowledge relations.

2.2.3 Subjectivity

It is possible to argue that Foucault's earlier works saw the creation of subjects as a product of disciplinary power, and therefore as a target of power (Foucault, 1975). However, in his later work he claimed it was impossible to study subjects without also considering them alongside their power relations. In fact, he implies through his notion of subjectivation that subjects are the product of practices of power (Dreyfus 1999; Välikangas & Seeck, 2011). Foucault (1988) began to explore the technologies through which individuals constituted and transformed themselves as subjects. This interest in the constitution of the subject can be traced from his seminar series on *The History of Sexuality* to his work on *Technologies of the self*. A Foucauldian perspective, however, emphasise that individuals within a discourse always have the ability to choose beyond the subject positions offered within it. As he says, *“everybody both acts and thinks”*(Foucault, 1988, p.14). His work on creating the self can add to a theoretical framework to critique midwifery leadership by considering a *branding the self* and *technologies of the self*. (Hill & Vallis, 2018; Motion & Leitch, 2007). The notion of branding of the self contrasts to a Cartesian notion of an essential or unified self, as Foucault (1982, p.351) stated: *“From the idea that the self is not given to us, I think there is only one practical consequence: we have to create ourselves as a work of art”*. This is valuable in an

exploration of midwifery as a professional discipline which has evolved a historical identity and is commonly debated in the healthcare literature (Sommerland, 2007; Cruess et al, 2014). Midwives, however, have a formative role in the identity of women, but an advisory role in the wider discourse of healthcare and society. And these technologies of identity can then be viewed as commodities, but which are positioned as part of discourse. Likewise, this is valuable in raising the questions around essential self, e.g., what midwives are required to be, versus authentic self, e.g., what midwives require of themselves to become. The former arguably places midwives in an employment discourse, the latter one of professionalism.

Foucault shows there are four types of technologies of the self which enable individuals to both understand and transform themselves; technologies of production, of sign systems, of power and of the self (Foucault, 1988). Technologies of production “*permit us to produce, transform, or manipulate things*” (p. 18) and these contribute to the creation of identity. Those strategies which construct meanings are technologies of sign systems that “*permit us to use signs, meanings, symbols, or significations*” (p. 18). Technologies of power therefore “*determine the conduct of individuals and submit them to certain ends or domination*” (p.18). Thus, within a given discourse technologies of power will aim to shape by procedures and norms a form of regulated identities of subjects. In the form of a response for example, technologies of the self,

“...permit individuals to effect by their own means, or with the help of others, a certain number of operations on their own bodies and souls, thoughts, and way of being, so as to transform themselves in order to attain a certain state of happiness, purity, wisdom, perfection, or immobility.” (Foucault, 1988, p.18).

2.2.4 Governmentality

This element of the theoretical framework of subjectivity will be problematised using Foucault governmentality which is elaborated in greater depth in Chapter 5. Governmentality is seen predominantly in Foucault’s last works, in his later lecture series in two titles; *Security, Territory, and Population* in 1978 and *The Birth of Biopolitics* in 1979. In his research, which he undertook with others at the time, he used the terms “governmental rationalities” and “art of government” and which later became “governmentality” (Burchill, Gordon & Miller,

1991, p.9) In this view however, Government is not the singular consideration of structural political rule, rather it refers to the myriad of procedures and approaches to guide the conduct of living bodies. Foucault's focus was exposing the rationality and approaches of governing at different historical moments (Binkly, 2006). In his original text he refers to his previous lecture on 'apparatuses of security' which centred on problems specific to populations and the need therefore to account for "*the problematic of government*" (Foucault, 1978, p.167). He refers for example to pastoral power, sovereign power, state power and liberalism. Governmentality is therefore the rationalising and reasoning behind the conduct of conduct and the subsequent deployment of actions in realising those rationalities via political technologies. Ball (2013, p.60) summarises well when he notes, "*Governmentality is a conceptual architecture of the modern liberal state and all its strategies techniques and procedures through the many and varied capillaries of power.*" Of interest as part of theoretical framework, is Foucault's work on governing of the self and the ways in which individuals are subjectified in discourses. Subjectification focusses on the procedures by which the subject is led to observe themselves, to analyse themselves, interpret themselves, and recognise themselves as a discourse of knowledge possibilities. It is "*the way the subject experiences the self in a game of truth where he relates to himself*" (Foucault, 1998, p.461). Therefore, the third component in this theoretical framework of *subjectivity* will be examined using Foucault's *governmentality*.

2.3 Methods: Phase 1 documentary archive

Discourse analysis of any kind considers how an individual's or group of individuals' understanding is environmentally and historically constructed by examining influential texts in terms of what is said and written (Neale, 2009). And, whilst Foucault's view of discourse goes beyond the boundaries of text, his approach arguably focusses on the power relations, and 'the conduct of conduct'. An initial examination of such things in universal healthcare (such as midwifery) was likely to be found in government policy, guidance, and regulatory protocols (Crowe, 2005). However, challenges are presented to the researcher in accommodating the wave of postmodern thinkers like Deleuze, Derrida, Nietzsche and Foucault, namely in their rejection of single sources of truth (Ramazanoglu & Hollan, 2002). And according to Neale (2009), discourse analysis is not a traditional method in a unified way, rather it is a process and a way of critically thinking about "circumstances of possibility" (p.94).

And whilst conventional techniques are used for generating verdicts from texts, these must be “...analysed discursively from a particular understanding of discourse, driven by a theoretical frame” (Cheek, 2004, p.1145). Likewise, Crowe (2005) notes that this epistemological stance forms an integral part of context of reading the data. One criticism of discursive analyses is that they offer no solutions, as they do not profess to seek truth or untruth, instead aim to disrupt that which is taken for granted, normal or inevitable (Burman, 2004: Antaki et al, 2003). But this can be countered to some degree by the sorts of questions asked by the researchers adopting it. Fairclough (2001), for example, states that a clear research question is better replaced by a statement of enquiry, as a point of entry to apply critique to a discourse. This is the rationale behind the aim of this thesis, namely; To critically examine leadership in midwifery using the concepts of Michel Foucault.

Furthermore, Neale (2006) notes such enquiry is better achieved if the researcher has existing knowledge about a domain of practice being investigated (*Appendix 2*). However, according to Fairclough (1992) and Grime & Ong (2007), key texts first need to be identified and collated. Fairclough (1992) suggests documentation should be critically examined in relation, not only to the theoretical frame, but to relational connections between discourses within the text, what he calls ‘intertextuality’. The format of directed content analysis (DCA) was used to refine the texts. According to Bloor & Wood (2006), the purpose of DCA is “*to describe the characteristics of the content of documents by examining who says what, to whom and with what effect?*” (Bloor and Wood, 2006; cited in a Vaismoradi & Turenen, 2013, p. 398). According to Hsieh & Shannon (2005), unlike conventional or summative content analysis, DCA is applicable where an existing theoretical position exists which directs initial coding as derived from existing constructs or concepts. They suggest that using the coding from the theoretical position means text can be coded immediately and data which cannot be coded highlighted for subsequent analysis to determine if it represents a new category or a sub-category of an existing code. That process is shown below in figure 1.

Figure 1

Pragmatically, by starting with the most up-to-date policy and guidance material, such things normally in the UK public sector state their influencing antecedents, events or emerging evidence used to construct them to case them in context. It was simple therefore to identify key texts from e.g., The Nursing Midwifery Council, The Professional Standards Authority, Government Policy on maternity and midwifery, the Royal College of Midwives, and the Kings Fund. They were collated initially under positions of influence, i.e., Central Government, Regulatory, RCM, or Other (*Appendix 3*). However, in terms of 'intertextuality', it became evident that Fairclough's (1992) notion of dynamic between discourses, illustrated potentially distinct discourses of: professional midwifery, NHS maternity, the NHS, a political discourse and one of regulation, scrutiny, and law. Although the critique of the archive has its findings shown at points in the thesis under Foucault's conceptual points, the archive did not remain static. And whilst the theory and methodology of discourse analysis embraces this to a degree, as a novice researcher I had not planned for the scale of that change. The archival analysis

refined the questions then asked of participants, and also my understanding of Foucault's philosophy and methods. However, the subsequent interviews with participants then offered insights, not only in new lines of enquiry, but enquiry and reflexivity back to of that initial critique of the archive. I was strongly encouraged by my supervisors to embrace and be critically reflexive of this aspect of research practice. The thesis does not follow a linear approach of a discrete findings section for the analysis of the documentary archive, such as a narrative review for example. Rather the findings are integrated into, and form part of the critique of Chapters, 4 and 5 under the appropriate theoretical position of Foucault's concepts. These are then used alongside the analysis of the participant finding in Chapter 6 to generate subsequent critical synthesis in Chapter 7.

2.4 Methods: Phase 2 participants

2.4.1 Sampling method

Qualitative enquiry shares, with its counterpart in quantitative research, the need for study samples to be representative of a wider population of interest, to improve rigour in the information which is derived from subsequent methods of enquiry (Polgar & Thomas, 2013). Of course, the ways of doing so are quite different e.g., in terms of probability versus nonprobability approaches (Cornesse et al, 2020). This study used purposive sampling i.e., participants were selected according to predetermined criteria based on their professional role in leadership in midwifery (Neale, 2009). As Polgar & Thomas (2013) point out, it is important that the researcher is clear which aspects of a particular phenomenon are being investigated. Therefore, the population of interest was derived largely from the initial review of the midwifery policy archive and by Foucault's theoretical position, namely in terms of *power* and *governmentality*. Patton's (2002) categories of purposive sampling are well established in health care research and the method chosen was theory-based and operational construct sampling to explore a predetermined theoretical/operational construct to elaborate and examine it. This was led by a wish to confirm rigour in adopting Foucault as a theoretical position but also allied to the organisational construct of midwifery leadership within a professional environment. There was an element of snowball sampling (Patton, 2002; Suri, 2011) where a small number of information-rich cases were actively sought out based on their appearance within the archive data. And whilst Patton (2002) warns of 'expert bias', this was viewed as a trade-off in terms of capitalising on expert wisdom, as robust research

into midwifery leadership from a critical perspective is uncommon. To that end, the sample population consisted of midwives who held a senior position of agency/authority in midwifery clinical practice (clinical leadership), a similar level of agency within the discursive apparatus involved in scrutiny and leadership direction (policy & quality) and those in midwifery leadership knowledge (higher education). The latter of these was threshold at 'senior' academic to reflect the likely level of experience and understanding in the role of knowledge in leading midwifery and included a Lead Midwife for Education (LME) which is a role in UK universities mandated by the NMC. These were not stratified in terms of sampling or categorisation of participants, as many participants would likely have held positions in multiple environments. Equally, based on the nature of the profession, all would have been involved in clinical practice to a senior level to work in policy or education for example. They are named in three discreet groupings simply to ensure each element of Foucault's methodological lens captured knowledge-rich participants across a spectrum of those within this midwifery discourse.

2.4.2 Sample size

Ritchie et al (2003) notes samples within qualitative enquiry are generally smaller than those in quantitative work and propose a point of diminishing return e.g., more data does not necessarily lead to richness of information. However, data saturation is an elusive concept since few concrete guidelines exist (Morse, 1995). Likewise, despite issues of saturation there are practical consideration which need to be considered (Crouch & McKenzie, 2006). However, Charmaz (2006) claims the goal of the study should guide the sample size, for example in the claims made within it, e.g., exploring heroin addicts rather than all drug addicts. However, as Patton (2002, p. 242) states, *"There are no rules for sample size in qualitative inquiry. Sample size depends on what you want to know, the purpose of the inquiry, what's at stake, what will be useful, what will have credibility, and what can be done with available time and resources"*. Based on all of the factors noted the study aimed to recruit four participants in each of the leadership environments noted earlier, in the end thirteen took part with four or five in each group.

2.4.3 Sample recruitment

Because of the nature of their roles, clarity on how participants were to be approached was a particular ethical consideration. For example, almost all of the organisations are political in some sense, and each have their own internal processes of determining who within their employment can or should be contacted about any research. For example, many of the organisations noted in Table 1 have communications teams, enquiry points etc, and they were emailed and/or phoned via their preferred contact method to establish who would be appropriate to then contact with further requests of involvement. For example, one NHS area required initial consent from their Research & Development Manager who requested an outline protocol (Appendix 4) to then give consent to contact their Head of Midwifery, who then approved an inquiry to their Clinical Leads. Conversely for the two Government participants, my details were clearly passed on by their internal mechanisms as both then simply contacted me directly to be involved. Others replied that I could locate a person's details and contact them directly without further organisational consent. Participants were allocated pseudonyms in the findings in Chapter 6 and allocated a title role from Table 1. One participant however was happy to identify themselves as employed at the time by the NMC, and their contribution in Chapter 6 is noted as not being representative of any organisational opinion, however.

Table 1

Organisational Profile	Types/Titles of Roles
NHS Scotland	Lead Midwife for Education (LME)
NHS England	Professor of Midwifery
NHS Education for Scotland	Consultant Midwife
Scottish Government	Midwifery Clinical Lead
Healthcare Improvement Scotland	Senior Lecturer Midwifery
The Royal College of Midwives	Senior Government Advisor
The Nursing Midwifery Council	Policy & Quality Advisor
University in Scotland	Solicitor Regulatory Healthcare Law
University in England	
The Association of Radical Midwives	
Regulatory Law	

2.4.4 Participant data collection

Participant data was gathered using in-depth semi-structured interviews. According to Morse & Field (2003), most researchers differentiate structured and non-structured interviews (Crabtree & Miller, 1999). Denzin & Lincoln (2005) propose three forms of interviews: the non-standardised, which uses no prescribed sets of questions; the non-schedule standardised, where prescribed types of information are pursued but where the ordering and phrasing of questions is flexible; and schedule standardised, where wording and ordering of questions is the same for all participants. According to DiCicc-Bloom & Crabtree (2006), the latter of these forms a consistent script, implying the researcher is aiming for a level of consistency among participants which leans toward quantitative enquiry. According to Mueller & Segal (2014) the unstructured interview approach is regularly used in clinical psychology for example where few *a priori* restrictions exist, and its unstructured nature offers maximum scope to investigate the experience of individuals. Likewise, there are arguably rich valid data to be gathered which have not been 'overly guided' by the researcher (Morse, 2012). However, according to Raworth et al (2012), semi-structured interviews are a justifiable choice to explore people's choices and behaviours, beliefs, and attitudes and moreover the impacts on their lives made by certain policies and events. Furthermore, they allow exploration of consistent enquiry on specific situations guided by the aim of the research being undertaken (Rubin & Rubin, 2005; King, 1994). The interview format was in-depth, allowing thorough exploration for example of power dynamics and governmental elements in participant's professional environments. It allowed a certain freedom of conversation based on what Esterberg (2002, p.87) terms "participants answers and interview flow".

The interview process was based on Creswell's (2007) outlined areas of; *preparation*, *constructing effective questions*, and *implementation*. For each shown here a brief critical reflection is noted in *italics* below each of the three headings drawn from my research notes, supplementary to the overall critical reflection on the research in Appendix 2.

Preparation: According to McNamara (2009), familiarisation with the interview protocol maintains focus on the area of questioning without the rigidity of a didactic structure. Likewise, Chenail (2009) suggests the choice of setting, reiterating the purpose of the interview, addressing terms of confidentiality, outlining the expected format, noting that the

participant can halt the interview at any time and outlining how the researcher can be contacted after the interview are important.

The first of the interviews with clinical leaders involved travelling to a large NHS maternity centre. I was placed in a waiting area and collected by a 'maternity subordinate' and taken to a managerial office, told to knock a door, to then interview participants at their desk. The sense was clear that these people were busy and important. Preparation was vital in ensuring clarity and justification of the 60 minutes spent with me and not somewhere else in the unit. The first of these on reflection did not fulfil that requirement, and that is reflected in the depth of the interview transcript. (Research notes, 6th June 2019)

Effective questions: planning appropriate questions allows deeper access to the experiences and/or knowledge of participants in order to gain useful text for subsequent interpretation (Chenail, 2009). Likewise, McNamara (2009) suggests: open-ended wording to alleviate binary yes or no responses but also allowing respondents to choose their own wording when answering; that questions be evocatively-neutral and unsensational in that they may influence responses; that questions are asked one at a time; and finally that questions should be worded clearly within the context of the study field of knowledge, for example, ensuring terms used fit within the general culture of the participants world or area of practice.

My notes indicate that the way I raised the questions around the midwifery regulator needed to be adjusted. The original guide used a prompt, "In what ways if any do you think midwives adjust their behaviour with respect to the NMC". This of course assumed that they did, and this altered the dynamic of the interview, likely aligned to the clinical environment we were in. It changed then to "what thoughts do you have around the work of the NMC in influencing the work of midwives?". (Research notes 10th June, 2019)

Implementation: Creswell (2007) notes the need for the researcher to be flexible and prepared for follow up questions, or even that these be prepared prior to the interview based on previous interviews with other participants. Creswell notes that despite the best efforts of

the interviewer and their protocol the participant may not answer the question that they were asked. He believes this to be a strength of the semi-structured interview in the flexibility of approach matched by the ability to get the interview back on track using the guiding questions.

As a novice researcher I made notes at the time as a form of acknowledgement of points of interest. On reflection however the notes became a refinement mechanism for the next participant, e.g., where the thoughts of participants on standardisation were consistently emerging, I noted in subsequent transcripts that these ended up being discussed in more depth. I spoke with my lead supervisor to gain assurance that this was acceptable practice as part of in-depth discussions. (Research notes, August 13th, 2019)

The interview format was a mixture of in-person face-to-face, video conferencing (MS Teams, Webex) and one phone call due to distance and timelines. As scheduled, they were 45-60 minutes in length. They were all audio recorded using Apple IOS and Mac technology (video calls were also audio recorded as backup). The device was passcode protected (not fingerprint or face scan accessible) and all requirements for ethical approval re data protection, consents etc followed. Authors such as DiCicc-Bloom & Crabtree (2006) note that in-person interviews are arguably a form of gold-standard, e.g., compared to phone interviews, based on non-verbal prompts such as facial expressions and body postures. However, Krouwel, Jolly, & Greenfield (2019) found little discernible difference between in-person and videoconferencing. Likewise, Archibald, Ambagtsheer & Casey (2019) claim satisfaction in their practice nurse research when using videoconferencing. However, video facilities, as well as offering the benefits of in-person visual conversation were vital in accessing this thesis sample. Some participants for example may not have engaged in the research based on time, distance or wishing not to be seen being interviewed. As such videoconferencing was explicit as an option format for participants in the recruitment material.

2.4.5 Participant data analysis

After transcribing the interviews verbatim, the data was analysed using a Directed Content Analysis approach to maintain consistency with justifications made earlier of the archive. This

was coded by hand for two reasons. I had become comfortable and proficient with the reading and coding and had field notes (both written and voice memo) taken immediately after every interview. Most of the country was based at home during SARS CoV-2, meaning less travel and more focused periods of time to immerse within the data. Secondly, creating nodes and memos on NVIVO 12 eased the administrative burden and was consistent and orderly when applied to the archive. However, I found it 'cold' when analysing conversations which I had been part of. Equally, coding was now more refined toward Foucault's governmentality, i.e., the mentality and mechanics of governing. Questions asked of participants were around their understanding of governmentality from *within* the midwifery discourse. Once all the transcripts were initially coded using for example 'authority', 'power/knowledge', 'surveillance', 'scrutiny,' the first transcripts were *revisited* where text coded 'other' was compared to other coding in other transcripts. An example is shown in Appendix 5 using participant data which cannot identify them. The transcripts reflect how the coding is refined by comparing them to others over time. And whilst DCA does lean toward more deductive coding than that of truly inductive approach, the use of Foucault's theoretical position to create a *form* of coding-frame allowed focussed depth in exploring the meaning in the data (Linneberg & Korsgaard, 2019). **Chapter 6** shows the themes drawn from the coded analysis, critically reflected against Foucault's conceptual works.

Summary

This chapter has outlined construction and layout of this thesis. It also introduced the reader to Foucault's philosophy as well as his key concepts and methods with which the subject of leadership in midwifery can be critically analysed. It has shown the way in which an initial analysis of the archive of policy, legislation and guidance began the processes of refining Foucault's approach, and how that refined the subsequent phase of participant data collection and analysis. Some areas of researcher critical reflection were also presented on those processes. Subsequent chapters now justify and refine Foucault's approach as it is applied to the topic of leadership in midwifery.

Chapter 3. The discourse of leadership

This chapter will begin by presenting an overview of the discourse of management in order that the leadership discourse can be seen in relation to that. It will then present a discourse of leadership theories before asserting critical similarities and differences between management and leadership. It will conclude by presenting leadership and its dynamic with followership by focussing on ways on which this can be predisposed to leadership as dominance-based or based on prestige. It concludes with a definition of leadership constructed from the critical analysis in this chapter.

3.1 The Discourse of Management

Building on Simon's contributions, Starbuck (2003) notes the breadth of management and organisation theory as encompassing scientific management, industrial psychology, psychology of small groups, human resources management and strategy. Likewise, Yang, Lui and Wang (2013) note the development of theories over time from practice and the mutuality of practice as being influenced by those same theories. However, the exploration of how groups organise and function in a workplace has existed since 2900 BC if considering Egyptian endeavours in construction and agronomy (Kitana, 2016). In 400 BC, Socrates described management as a skill separate from technical knowledge (Higgins, 1991). Subsequently, Plato saw management as a distinct art and promoted the selection of young men to be trained to be leaders in *The Republic* (Griffith, 1990). Nevertheless, the frame of reference for the classical management movement in the discourse of management is seen as approximately 1885 to 1940. The movement branched into two discernible fields of enquiry, one of scientific management focussed on productivity and the other of administrative management viewing organisations as unique single entities (Pindur, Rogers & Suk Kim, 1995). During this period Adam Smith, drawing on Cantillon, presented his neoclassical economic levers of aligning labour incentives with organisational goals (Kwok, 2014). Likewise, Babbage in the late 1800s advocated for work specialisation and profit-sharing as a means of improving productivity (Vani, 2013). However, the increased formalisation of organisations at the time, linked to the technical and scientific advances of the industrial revolution, likely stimulated the theoretical interest in organisations as part of a general scheme of management (Starbuck, 2003). Thoughts at the time comprised Taylor's scientific management, that sought the single

most effective way to complete tasks. Alongside Weber's bureaucracy, that was arguably focussed on rationalities of hierarchy, rules, and procedures. Likewise, research in administrative management, later largely attributed to Jules Henri Fayol, emphasised methods of transmission of information throughout organisations (McLean, 2011). However, most of the literature of the time is premised on the mentality and rationality of organisations as machines (Vani, 2013). Viewed as discourse, the iterative construction of ideas of the time saw Smith's ideas of incentives and productivity be developed by Daniel McCullum and focussed on the vertical flow of structural information into the now common organisational chart (Shafritz, Ott, & Jang, 2005). Moreover, Pembri (2109) usefully compares Weber's six elements of a bureaucratic organisation with Fayol's fourteen principles of management. And from this some similarities can be drawn in terms of the mentality and understanding of management in organisations at this time. For example, in both, matching skills to tasks is important, as is willingness to obey instruction, thereby ensuring compliance with tasks. Likewise, a prominent organisational demand for uniformity and homogeneity in the actions of workers, implying standardisation is evident. A sense of singular lines of accountability and in a vertical manner, suggesting group dynamic and horizontal responsibility is not well recognised. And in both Weber's claims and Fayol's, the goals of the organisation should be of the utmost significance in the minds of managers, from which can be inferred a locus of loyalty in prioritising the organisation over the workers within it. Critique of the classical positions rightly highlight the closed, inward-facing emphasis on production in a technological manner, and a minimal perspective on human actors and forms of motivation beyond cash rewards (Onday, 2016; Ivanko, 2013).

However, according to Ferdous (2017), the mechanised model of the classical theories of management led to conflicts between workers and organisations. Accordingly, Yang et al (2013), claim that as a result of such conflict the impetus to derive new models of understanding can be seen in the literature. According to Kayshap (2015), noting the Hawthorne studies in Chicago in 1924, the organisational literature becomes inclusive of the socio-psychological elements of employee motivation and incentives, such as personal appreciation and belonging. Likewise, Onday (2016) points out the role of the 'informal organisation' and that the collective of the 'co-workforce' could be a more effective incentive than financial reward. Workers as social beings now replaces the classical views of workers as

components. According to Hellriegel, and Slocum (1992), the work of the behavioural management movement since Mayo and Roethlisberger's experiments in the Hawthorne studies can be traced to Maslow's subsequent work in 1943 in defining *internal* states of sociobiological being and reward. And this, according to Pindur, Rogers and Suk Kim (1995), led to the extending of Maslow's theory to Frederick Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory of incentives and job satisfaction. Likewise, explicit critique of management applied to organisations can be seen in Gulick's (1937) work, *Notes on the Theory of Organising*. Subsequent studies punctuate the organisational management perspective from Simon (1950) in *Modern Organization Theories*. Likewise, in *Comments on the Organization Theory* (ibid, 1952) and *A Comparison of Organization Theories* (ibid, 1953). Nevertheless, Simon (1976) notes that Herzberg's work was extended by inclusion in McGregor's work in Theory X and Y building the impetus of management as linked to future enquiry into how internal motivations of the individual could be positively adopted in organisations.

What can be considered a modern management movement evolves from the 1960s as discourse of perpetual interrogation of managing systems, processes, contingencies, and strategy. However, these are still seen as evolutions of the principles of organisational managements quantitative and behavioural antecedents. For example, Ludwig Von Bertalanffy (1972), credited with systems theory, borrows heavily from the discourse of biology. Alongside it we can consider Fiedler's work in contingency theory as a systematic attempt to predict environmental demands in order that the biological manager can be suitably adjusted (Fiedler, 1958). The latter of these the bridges a connection to the discourse of leadership. For example, Fiedler's contingency theory of leadership broadly contemplates three elements. *Task structure*: How well defined is the job being considered. *Leader-member relations*: How well does the leader (who is almost certainly a manager) work with team members. And *Leader position power*: How much authority does the leader have? Used as a management tool, the theory leads to an index which matches types of people, to types of tasks, in types of environments. Both Fiedler and Von Bertalanffy in this example are attempting to predict patterns of human behaviour based on environmental stimuli. Viewed as sets of statement, these same dynamic filaments or technical-biological dilemma are traceable in the thoughts of others in the management discourse. For example, Koontz (1961) noted his 'management jungle theory' which accepts this dilemma of managing and that

theoretical work simply represented useful tools that could be drawn together in his focus on *process* management. However, this is arguably the foundation of Fayol's work prior to Koontz (Pindur, Rogers and Suk Kim, 1995). Von Bertalanffy's (1972) work in systems, in a closed systems view correlates to Weber's bureaucracy and Taylor's scientific management. In contrast, unlike the self-contained systems perspective, an open system operates in less stable conditions and relies on the environment for inputs and outputs, draws on the human resource dimension. The technical-biological are unruffled in this view and simply fusing within a given system. Open or closed, in simple terms, an organisation takes resources from the larger system (environment), processes them, and returns them to the environment in an altered format. Nevertheless, the emphasis on the potency of the environment is seen in Laurence and Lorsch's (1969) foundational work in contingency theory. As the title of their book implies, *Developing Organisations: Diagnosis and Action*, their thoughts can be seen as a managerial diagnostic, e.g., where in an integrated manner the entire managerial environment is appraised and analysed on set criteria. The biological element is not ignored, but the environment is seen as being able to be predicted in some way. As noted earlier, Fielder (1958) alters this to a form of leaderly diagnostic. This scheme of thoughts does somewhat imply an organisation as having a corporeal centre, pathologized and prescribed a form of curative treatment to return it to better health. Consequently, strategic management theory arguably aims to guide and navigate managerial efforts for that corporate entity through environmental uncertainty (Raymond, 1964). As part of this thread of prominent thought on strategy, Drucker's (1954) work on practice management is acknowledged, as can the shift in the 1960s from American business strategy toward corporate primacy in the work of Chandler (1962). This is amplified by Ansoff (1965) but with the emphasis now on competitive advantage. Porter's (1980) competitive strategy work can be seen with Hofer and Shendel's (1978; 1979) as continuing the drive of strategy to navigate competitive environmental forces, before the strategic structuring of organisations is the direction taken by Mintzberg (1979). However, arguably what exists from the point of Peters and Waterman's (1992) thoughts on the pursuit of 'excellence', is an acknowledgment of another stream of thought from Deming's observations in Japanese management approaches, namely Total Quality Management (TQM). However, a parallel can be drawn of Deming's work not simply to systems and a process management perspective, but also to Taylor's view of scientific solutions. Mirroring Walter Sheward's ideas in 1939 on process variability, Deming's

fundamental philosophy on quality is that productivity improves as variability decreases (Kenyon & Sen, 2014). However, Juran's (1998) work on the pursuit of organisational excellence and quality is valuable in bringing closer the concept of leadership to the field of management. For example, Deming claimed that over 90% of poor organisational quality was down to bad management. However, according to Pindur, Rogers and Suk Kim (1995, p.74), Juran's three basic steps to *managing* quality can be seen as structured annual improvements, major training programmes, and upper management leadership.

3.2 Leadership as Discourse

"It is clear that once the question 'Who should rule?' is asked, it is hard to avoid some such reply as 'the best' or 'the wisest' or the 'born ruler'...But such a reply, convincing as it may sound – for who would advocate the rule of 'the worst, or the 'the greatest fool', or 'the born slave' – is quite useless".

(Karl Popper, *The Open Society and Its Enemies*, 1945)

It is possible that events such as natural disasters, fighting racism or battlefield victories, can render visible and therefore somehow profile leadership and leaders, because such happenings in some way threaten human moral coherence. Or, where examples of super-human accomplishments can be seen which have the effect of stretching the boundaries of possibility in human existence. But according to anthropologist Donald Brown (1991) leadership is simply a human universal. By way of context, every nation on the earth has a single leader in some form, either political, a monarchy, or dictatorship. There are business leaders like Bezos, technological leaders like Musk, civil rights leaders like Luther-King, science leaders like Hawking and those in the world of sport, art, and philosophy. All of these manage to demonstrate, intentionally or otherwise, influence upon others toward a common goal. In terms of influential success however, if numbers are the choice metric, none can be more effective than the theistic texts of religion, demonstrating leadership by speculative ideas predominantly packaged in promises for corporeal souls after life has ended. Sadly, not all leadership is benign, if considering the darker side of humanity and the ability to incite group violence (Klaas, 2022). Leadership bestows reward on individuals adept at its implementation.

Whilst context-dependent, it normally raises earnings and social status, leading to even greater opportunities to influence. And yet whilst leaders may have measurable success, it is by selective and accepted social measures. And despite a preponderance of texts about the subject seemingly refining leadership to an empirical point of understanding (Hartley & Hinksman, 2003; Eva et al, 2019), there are examples of leadership disappointment. For example, male politicians have a historical proclivity to engage in infidelity in their occupational role (Ludwig, 2002). Equally, when psychology claims that ‘who we are is how we lead’ and that this can be highly toxic to others in an organisation, questions can be asked about how such leaders are appointed in the first place (Hogan & Kaiser, 2005).

According to van Vugt and Ahuja (2010), leadership research has developed in the overlapping discourses of armies (military leadership), nations (political leadership) and business (corporate leadership). And this is likely for good reason, since these strive in their efforts to deliver stability, prosperity, and defence to groups of people. Therefore, it makes sense to emulate these successes in the pursuit of understanding. But success in these three noted fields would rely on one or two leaderly individuals predicting deterministically the outcomes of thousands of subsequent instructions, which is unlikely. Or alternately, that those whom they implanted in key strategic positions were equally adept at influencing, which is more feasible. However, both emphasise a similar premise, that of a personal quality of a human actor to lead and the subsequent receptibility of those in the groups they influence. Consequently, the three fields of army, nation and business have a focus on genetics, as they share points on the same continuum: from surviving to thriving, i.e., from death (of territory, ideals, or homeostasis) to prosperity, and ultimately the maintenance of a familial line. Ludwig (2002) claims that leaders are themselves created by an intrinsic human need to be led, which is contingent on temporal and environmental demand. He claims leadership driven by the need to follow is the natural order of things. If it is indeed human, it is therefore biological leading to the hypothesis that leadership can be formally isolated in some way at the biological level (Arvey et al, 2006). If, however, the leadership impetus in the *biological* is contingent on the *environmental* and leader-follower actions can subsequently influence the environment, leadership itself leans toward complexity not predictability (Uhl-Bien, Marion & McKelvey, 2007; Weberg, 2012), and also the possibility that it is evolutionary (van Vugt & Ahuja, 2010; Kennedy, 2012)

3.2.1 *The Great Man (or woman) Theory*

The main premise behind this view of leadership is that leaders cannot be created but are born with an intrinsic 'spark' which can relate to exceptional intellect, determination, or Aristotelian virtue (Organ, 1996). Some of these positions were written of in the second century by the Platonic philosopher Plutarch in his *Lives of the Noble Greeks and Romans*. And although accepted as legitimate in the leadership discourse until a century ago, this theory is marked in its history by Scots philosopher Thomas Carlyle and his texts *On Heroes, Hero Worship and the Heroic in History*. However, some claim it is Freud's account of the compulsions that drive us toward authority figures, more than Carlyle's evangelising hero worship, that better explain the status placed upon the exceptional individual (Spector, 2015). Viewed in this way, great leaders are born, but are only made great by the impact and magnitude of their followers, for example, one only has to consider Churchill, an arguable mainstay of the heroic military landscape, who's status was premised on the successful outcome of war (Gibson & Weber, 2015). Therefore, this view of leadership can tend to present leaders within a context of conflict, i.e., those who 'save the day' either in national, political, or business environments. But this also implies the concept of victory and winning. It is certainly leader-centric in its heroic perspective and invokes a certain romanticism around which facts can be obfuscated over time (Alvesson & Johnstone, 2018). According to Schweiger, Müller and Güttel (2020) this is one of the reasons that heroic characteristics are difficult to overcome in the leadership discourse. However, with the rise of leadership in corporate spheres and less emphasis placed on military victory, the trends in literature have shifted theoretic work on leadership toward its application in organisations. According to van Vught & Ahuja (2010), this has seen the modification of simple leaders and followers, to managers and subordinate employees.

3.2.2 *Trait Theory*

The perception that circumstances, normally involving conflict, could profile certain aspects of human greatness, led in the 1940's to a shift in research to pursue exactly which parts of people were so great. This essentially pushed the leadership discourse to focus research efforts on the personality-leadership association (Stogdill, 1948; Maan, 1959). Potentially driven by the desire to make more and better leaders in a post-war economy, the extraction of key characteristics seen at this stage in the discourse of leadership is yet the pursuit to

manufacture leaders, but to be able to select them. However, given the selection criteria are arguably based on heroic characters seen thus far, the evolutionary elements of leadership are still emphasised. Professor Edwin Boring (1950), in the historical psychology literature notes,

“Although the Great Man theory cannot be wrong, since it is clear that men die having differed from one another in social effectiveness and therefore in greatness, there has been, nevertheless, for more than a century now, a growing suspicion that the theory asserts very little, since it specifies neither the attributes nor the conditions of greatness” (Boring,p.339).

This represents a slight discursive shift from the material body, to a more cartesian locus of heritable possibilities of thoughts and minds. And research at this time expended great energy in extracting a range of attributes such as intelligence and extroversion, with Stodgill (1974) systematically reducing these to assertiveness, dominance, self-confidence, persistence, and ambition. At the time, Stodgill’s associated skills set championed oral fluency and persuasiveness, which were later challenged as traits versus competencies (Bass & Bass, 2008). Critically this however assumes that the same types of traits are effective in all environmental conditions. This also translates into a universality in the application of traits to human beings. For example, that military generals would have the same trait-profile as a midwifery leader. Moreover, Colbert et al (2012) highlight that much of the historical research has used self-reported data. Likewise, House and Aditya (1997, p.410) noted, *“There developed among the community of leadership scholars near consensus that the search for universal traits was futile”*. However, there is some consensus that traits do have an element of heritability, but again this is based on environmental or social measures of what successful leadership actually is (Illes, Gerhardt & Lee, 2004; Judge, Piccolo & Kosalka, 2009).

3.2.3 Psychoanalytic Theory

Shortly after a focus on traits, began a focus on leadership behaviours, more specifically how influence could be understood as practices of mind. By now however this is arguably rooted in the corporate spheres of authority and management (Zaleznik, 1966; Gabriel, 2011). Perhaps not surprisingly, Freud’s influence on the literature emphasises the moulding of sons

in ways which emulate the greatness of fathers and overall, in the role of family itself. The focus on love and fear in linking father to son can be linked to the emphasis on benevolence and authority in leadership in the organisational environment (Obholzer, 1996). There is also a worthwhile element of this part of the leadership discourse around the deep emotional investment and sacrifice made by parents, the leaders, toward children, the followers (van Vugt & Ronay, 2014). However, a psychological focus on personality, including any unconscious historical elements of that, places a dependence on a scientifically accurate assessment of a leader's past, which was not in the body of literature at the time of the theories emergence. It also places a theoretical necessity on matching followers to that particular leader's personal profile, which may not match the practical elements of employment (Obholzer, 1996).

3.2.4 Charismatic Leadership Theory

Charisma could be considered a trait or natural ability, but it is worthy of enlightenment in the discourse of leadership theory on the basis of its observed mechanisms of persuasiveness. Some authors note that charismatic theoretical research is the next natural continuation seen in the discourse of leadership (Sandberg & Moreman, 2015; Tokbaeva, 2022). This form of leadership is common in ideological anchoring e.g., in political settings whereby individual leaders *require* the followership of others but often where leaders have no tangible superior skill or knowledge, but rather an appeal which can potentially benefit the follower (Tucker, 2003). This biases a heuristic rather than critical mindset however, laden with personal bias of 'vested interests', but also can be interpreted as linking back to Stodgills (1974) claims around oral fluency, self-confidence, and ambition. Charismatic leaders then rise to prominence in this theoretical frame not from what they *are*, but from what people can be persuaded to *believe* they are. Such is the potency of the follower group's identity, it is claimed by some that these leaders are described as being magnetic and therefore essential to the groups continued cohesion and identity (Kennedy, 2012). Evidence seems to show elements of charismatic theory linked to heritable traits in an evolutionary sense between high verbal IQ (Rosete & Ciarrochi 2005) and what's referred to as the babble effect, or babble hypothesis (MacLaren, et al 2020). These enforce the notion that 'talkativeness' in groups confers an ability of individual leadership potential amongst the group, but also the chance

that intentions of the leader may be mischievous and self-centred and easily hidden from that group (van Vugt & Ahuja, 2010; Kennedy, 2012).

3.2.5 Behavioural Theory

Having moved, over sixty years, from considering leadership as imbedded in genetic heroics, to heritable attributes, to a form of persuasive social glue, the leadership discourse switches to advancing research into what leaders *did*, versus what they were. Although Blake and Mouton's (1964) seminal grid was focussed on establishing leadership styles and behaviours linked to certain situations, it arguably perceives leadership as making managing better. Indeed, it's two axes of 'concern for people' and 'concern for task' are often referred to as a managerial grid (Cho, Yi & Choi, 2018). At a similar time, McGregor's (1960) work tacked the behavioural dynamic of managing by referring to strengths of authority, as leadership styles/behaviours linked to the belief or assessment of the agency of the manager over the managed. People were seen as lazy in the eyes of the manager and required 'autocratic leadership' and coercion. People seen as having untapped potential received 'participatory leadership'. However, the ability to view leadership as something which could be practiced and not based on some natural ability, meant leadership could be learned and taught. Illustrative of the merger with leadership as management practice at this time, is Maslow's Theory of Eupsychian Management (1965) which accentuates a focus on the personal nurturing of subordinates as a way to mutually benefit production in a way closely aligned with compassionate leadership approaches not seen until the turn of the 21st Century. However, Blake and Mouton's work points out a fundamental clash of concepts in research at this time. Namely they observe a nexus at which two sets of fundamental beliefs were dominating research practice in the discourse. Situationalism was implying the best leadership approach is derived from its situation, meanwhile behavioural theorists were arguing the contrary. "*Effective style theorists argue there is one most effective style which is emerging in the behavioural sciences*". Blake and Mouton (1982, p. 275). They point out that both cannot be valid. They go on to note, "*Confusion and contradictions are sometimes antecedent to the emergence of new order*" (ibid, 275).

3.2.6 Situational Theory

Genetics, traits, and behaviours are not ruled out in situational theory, nor does it attempt to replace previous work, rather, a situational perspective favours the shifting dynamic between the capacities of human actors and their environment. So far, the knowledge around leadership has remained leader-centric in some way and this development views an interdependency on both leader and what is being led, and why. However, whilst the literature favours Hersey and Blanchard's situational leadership theory (1982) it was quickly challenged as having mixed empirical validation of effectiveness (Blank, Green & Weitzel, 1990; Graeff, 1997; Thomson & Vecchio, 2009). However, it is useful in shifting the direction of thinking and research from a leadership prototype or the notion of a supreme character, who could be equally effective in any contingency. The evolution of situational theory in the discourse of leadership correlates historically with the management discourse around the potency of the environment on human actions (Laurence and Lorsch's, 1969).

3.2.7 Contingency Theory

In an evolution from Blake and Mouton's frustrations, contingency leadership theory notes a broader range of variables upon which actions of individuals interact with environmental variables. However, it is an advancement of a broader field of contingency theory prior to gaining traction in the archive from Fiedler in the 1970s. Laurence and Lorsch's (1969) broader contingency theory for example, claims that the environment in which an organisation operates determines the most effective way to organise (Scott, 1992). This mirrors the wider managerial discourse in thinking at the time in establishing the distinction between 'mechanistic' and 'organic' forms of organisation and management. (Burns & Stalker, 1961). At this point in leadership research then the organisation has primacy, seen as a unit of research, a corpus of sorts. The thinking which emerged from this time is not dissimilar to Blake and Mouton's polarising argument of situational contingences being seen as answered in the fields of 'science' or as a field of 'technology'. And Holton (1986) claimed contingency theory could capture and capitalise on both. Fiedler's Contingency Theory of Leadership is a development of his broader work on contingency theory (Fiedler, 1958). However, the antecedents of his work can be seen in the Ohio State Leadership Studies in the 1940s. His leadership work is steeped in the same task-orientated manager versus people-orientated manager as in Blake and Mouton's work, only that his model allows a form of ideal alignment

with overall productivity. Some claim, e.g. (van Vugt & Ahuja, 2010) that Fiedler's model attempted to make binary decisions about matching actions and environments and that it was Hersey and Blanchard (1979) who evolved this into continuums of authority. Equally, in doing so Fiedler's work is nothing more than the autocratic-democratic dynamic conceived by McGregor's X and Y model. However, since Fiedler's claims are somewhat deterministic, many have tested it. For example, Strube and Garcia (1983) claimed marginally favourable results in their meta-analysis of studies testing the validity of Fiedler's model. However, these were subsequently dismantled by critique of their analysis and the positivity of their findings attributed to sampling bias (Peters, Hartke & Pohlmann, 1985).

3.2.8 Transactional versus Transformational Leadership

Transactional leadership, or the influential part of that at least, is grounded in the notion of and intrinsic economic personal drive for productivity. In a workplace environment, an individual is in that environment with a view to maximising their own fruitful gain. The dynamic between individual and an organisational environment is based on an instrumental rationality. Clarity of the expectations of the leader is therefore primal in the ability of the follower to maximise his or her own benefits. This has antecedents in Weber's (1947) legal-rational work and is developed in the literature by Burns (1978) and Bass (1985) to include the subsequent elements of transformation. Burns' (1978) work was based on political leadership typologies, and whilst compliance dominates in the transactional dynamic, the transformative leadership strives to connect with shifting beliefs, needs and values of followers (Kunert & Lewis, 1987). Burns (1978) makes a powerful point in the evolving leadership discourse when he notes of transformational goals, *"the result of transforming leadership is a relationship of mutual stimulation and elevation that converts followers into leaders and may convert leaders into moral agents"* (p. 4). Bass (1985) applies Burns' work in organisational management and makes the distinction between efforts which focus on acquiescence with prescribed ideas in sustaining performance, but it leaders seemingly targeting a similar inward motivation seen in earlier theoretical views. He notes for example, *"a leader with vision, self-confidence, and inner strength to argue successfully for what he sees is right or good, not for what is popular or is acceptable according to established wisdom of the time"* (Bass, 1985, p. 17). Accordingly, the leadership literature at this time appears to acknowledge the emotional, moral, desire to be better, specifically that followers see

transformational leaders as inspirational, heroic, and charismatic, but at a very personal level. As Bass and Alviolo (1994) point out, followers are more likely to see these sorts of leaders as the person they themselves would like to be, but in a tangible workplace environment. The duality of relationship therefore moves from leadership styles and organisation, to leadership person and follower aspiration.

3.2.9 Distributed (or dispersed/emergent) Leadership

As the name implies, this grouping of knowledge and understanding, addresses the locus of leadership impetus moving from a concentrated point, normally of authority or agency. And this proliferates amongst a great deal of the current healthcare leadership rhetoric claiming that everyone has a leadership role in healthcare organisations (Cardoba et al, 2022). Originating in the psychology literature in the 1950s (Gronn, 2002), it is thought by some (Leithwood & Mascall, 2008) to be an amalgamation of 'shared leadership' (Pearce & Conger, 2003), 'democratic leadership' and 'dispersed leadership' (Ray, Clegg & Ray, 2004). Interestingly, in previous prevailing thoughts on leadership, authority has been a consistent factor not only in the theories, but in the environments in which leadership occurred. That authority, and the affiliated construct of accountability, raise questions about distributed leadership as a driver to distribute accountability in an arguably bureaucratic manner (Holloway, Nielsen & Saltmarsh, 2018; Bass et al, 2022). Distributed leadership more importantly moves the locus of agency toward followers and the need for them to be 'transformed' into the right sort of productive follower (van Vugt, & Ahuja, 2010). There is supporting evidence that these types of distributed egalitarian approaches can create happier, more productive employees in healthcare environments (Chreim & MacNaughton, 2016; Chreim, et al, 2010; Fitzgerald et al, 2013). Most importantly, distributed leadership moves the leadership discourse firmly toward leadership as normalised practice. However, since almost all organisations exist in some form of hierarchical structure, this implies the need to understand leadership as individual practices, alongside other clear levers of influence, and therefore highlights the titled or positional roles of formal points in organisations (Harris, 2013).

3.2.10 Servant Leadership

The philosophy of servant leadership is attributed in the literature to Robert Greenleaf. In leadership terms, his understanding of the topic has distilled into sets of specific characteristics, as noted by Spears, (1998). It offers a reflective glance toward traits and leader-centric modelling. However, servant leadership also moves philosophically toward heroic and inspirational beings, *provided* they are valiant in moral fortitude. Whilst previous noticeable threads of knowledge on leadership have all essentially tried to influence some form of social and/or organisational production, servant leadership adopts the quest of valuing followers over all other factors. More accurately, this form of ethical stewardship serves the group even at a cost to the leader (Greenleaf, 2002). This has application in high-risk corporate environments where certain other aspects of leadership traits, less well aligned to an ethical proclivity, can be screened out in leadership recruitment (Furtner, Maran & Rauthmann). Links have been made here naturally to contingency theory, e.g., where organisational conditions can be determined as requiring such morally dependable leaders and where sound organisational strategy can ‘match’ to demand for servant leaders (Eva et al, 2019). In the leadership discourse however, it seems evident that there is marked interest over a decade from the early 1990s in linking ethics, virtue, and morality (Graham, 1991; Lanctot and Irving, 2010; Parolini et al, 2009; Russell, 2001; Whetstone, 2002). Despite understandable questions around organisations which are compiled from authoritative management structures, their systematic review of servant leadership in organisational practices saw improvements not only in follower wellbeing but in team effectiveness (Paris & Peachy, 2013).

3.3 Management and Leadership

In *Leadership: Theory and Practice*, Northouse (2007) makes the point that there are many ways to finish the sentence “*Leadership is . . .*” (p.2). He does however provide a valuable definition of leadership when he notes ‘*Leadership is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal*’ (p.3). However, the *process* of the accomplishment of a goal uncovers a key to understanding one subtle difference in leadership and management. Leadership relies *not* on an externality of peculiar social or organisation legitimacy and rationality. Much as such forces can encourage leaderly things, their blatancy, or even suspicion, in the dynamic between leaders and followers collapses leaderly things to

little more than superficial transaction. In the symbolic 'Schrodinger's cat' hypothesis in quantum mechanics, the physicist explains that particles actually exist as interactive waves (quanta) until they are measured by humans, at which point their quantum state ends and they become simple particles (termed collapse of the wave-function). Shifting the focus from the unique determinable characterisation of the leader, toward the process component in leadership, allows the bond between leaders and followers to be seen as fundamental. By that is meant, in the process dynamic, driven by a shared goal, leaders and followers are both affecting and affected by that process. Leader and followers are in a form of leaderly wave function, a dependency, but when some form of external burden threatens the warm authenticity of that, it collapses to a cold economic exchange more comfortable in a management realm. Foucault wrote extensively of his micro-physics of power, and in leadership terms, once that dynamic is unbalanced by coercive rather than persuasive power the shift moves from core ethic to authoritarian repercussions. As Spears (2018) points out, approaches such as servant leadership, place significant emphasis upon, or even prioritisation of, the reciprocal relationship between leaders and followers. There will be a range of managerial or administrative working environments whereby such dynamics would seem challenging to comprehend let alone implement. Adopting or promoting such a dynamic in a workplace as a prevailing method of organising goal achievement, which places a reliance on personalities, feelings, and temperament, not only of one individual but in groups, would border on anarchy in management terms. However, Bennis (2007) claims, "*Managers do things right, while leaders do the right things*" (p. 12). Of course, if leadership is purely about influence, then managers can be leaders the second they inspire subordinates to do things better, once they notice from their monitoring role that things are not right. It does however highlight the arguably normative nature of leadership and the positive nature of management, or the nature of influence versus authority. Alternatively, it can obfuscate both when we see such things applied to human entities, which then forces the allocation of a role or title to *leader* and *manager*. It is perhaps the titling of human subjects and allocating them to an established parameter of organisational agency which opens the field of questions on what leadership is, versus what leaders do in management practice.

From the post-war era Katz (1950) claimed that management was applying direction to a group or organisation through executive, administrative, and supervisory positions. Kotter

(1990) proposed a structural approach to determining the differences in leadership and management. Kotter (2001) later defines management as a titled role, including in its remit such things as planning, budgeting, and monitoring on behalf of an organisation. Northouse (2007), highlights the management process requires tangible planned objectives and the goal of resource efficiency. From this perhaps can be inferred that whilst management is focused on creating order and stability, leadership strives to create constructive change and movement.

Management implies a level of pre-knowledge about the nature of task requirements prior to managing its implementation. Management, and managers, work therefore from a position of predictable knowing around the expectations of the consequences of a number of organised tasks. The margins around which management operates are a form of philosophical determinism. It implies a machine-like technology aligned to Taylors work in scientific management but also a transactional mentality in the exchanges between workers and the organisation. Transactional leadership in the process of managing therefore would have the goal of maximising the emotional and psychological connectedness between worker and organisation in repeated messages, subliminal and explicit, to influence the environmental conditions to both maximise and then normalise, the productivity of workers. Whilst management can focus on the material nature of tools, worker skill-base, micro-process refinement, leadership has mechanisms rooted in the subconscious rationalities of human existence. Where management theories have and still do aim to align processes, systems, inputs and outputs, leadership as a target seeks an adjustment of the hearts and minds of the human subjects. Perhaps this is why managerial lexicon uses terms aimed at directing the actions of humans, a form of pushing, and leadership appears to guide in a push-pull dynamic of leader-follower. Moreover, in viewing the level of agency in the two interwoven discourses of management and leadership, it is possible to further illustrate their ontological nature. To see what managers can do, look at what they are permitted to instruct subjects to do within the two parameters of law, and organisational or professional norms. The task demand, delivered as an instruction from manager to the managed, can be intentionally altered in its style of delivery from manager to subordinate, but the task is largely unchanged. The outputs are impacted by employee competence, compliance, and the requisite tools and facilities provided by the organisation. An awareness of repercussion is ever present in various forms

and magnitudes in the managed subject. However, to see what leaders can do, simply look at what managers *cannot* do without a followers emotional willingness, approval, and consent. Managers cannot *gain* employee trust, respect, loyalty, and admiration. They cannot *generate* credibility, buy-in, enthusiasm and commitment. Nor can they *expect* candour, and for individuals to go above-and-beyond the task.

3.4 Leadership and Followership

There is a notable profusion of explorations into leadership in the organisational literature (Yukl, 2012). However, according to Uhl-Bien et al (2014) where the construct of followership is considered, many studies have still been either leader-centric, seeing followers as recipients of the leader's influence (Bass, 2008), or seen as 'constructors' of leaders and leadership as a follower-centric views (Meindl, 1990). However, a more promising position is considering the co-created process of leadership in social relations (Fairhurst & Uhl-Bien, 2012). Viewed this way, leadership can only occur if there is followership (Uhl-Bine et al 2014). This establishes 'following' behaviours as a crucial component of the leadership process. Following behaviours embody a willingness to defer to another. Accordingly, DeRue and Ashford (2010) describe this as permitting a leaderly identity to another and at the same time declaring a follower identity for oneself. Likewise, Uhl-Bien and Pillai (2007, p.196) refer to this as a form of deference to a leader, noting, "*if leadership involves actively influencing others, then followership involves allowing oneself to be influenced*". Moreover, Shamir (2007, p.18) maintains that following is so important to leading that it refutes the construct of shared leadership completely, stating, "*leadership exists only when an individual (sometimes a pair or a small group) exerts non-coercive influence on other*".

By the late 1990's, some social science literature had considered the biological perspectives of leading and following (Chemers, 2000) but according to King, Johnson & Van Vugt (2009) the questions asked in research were still laboured by enquiring about 'what makes a good leader'. In seeking clarity around leadership, and by accepting the potency of the leader-follower relationship as something beyond authority, then this emergent behaviour hinges around a need to coordinate activity for *purpose*. That purpose would seem logically to be a future state of being, movement toward which would confer benefit to those involved and come about as a result of some form of social or environmental pressure. Those interested in

leadership in evolutionary terms claim, at a fundamental level, that such a purposeful scenario maps to a primal mindset of sustaining life (food, water, procreation), and protection from loss of life from predation (Van Vugt, 2006; Garfield, Hubbard & Hagen, 2019). However, much of the literature in these instances observes the post facto 'emergence' of leadership-follower behaviour. Therefore, in terms of the leadership input to that relationship, its emergence seems centred on perceived conflict with the status quo, or a sort of incompatibility between a current state and a future state, between groups of competing actors or within groups whose activity needs 'better' coordination. Leaders require to both initiate group action for betterment but also achieve that future state. That can be through motivation and/or reprimand of some kind. Human leaders plan and organise, direct, and monitor group actions. However, they can do this in several ways linked to theory, but these theories broadly exist on a continuum from leading democratically to despotically, from the back or the front (or above and below) and can be in small or large groups. For example, King, Johnson and Van Vugt (2009) claim that human leadership has evolved over five transitions. They imply leadership in its simplest form emerged from group problem solving. Those who solved better became leaders as others followed (Conradt et al, 2009). Secondly, leadership selected collective actions in larger-group conflict situations where dominant socially important individuals emerged as leaders. Thirdly, a broad societal move toward egalitarianism tempered emerging dominance models and laid the foundations for prestige-based leadership to emerge (Boehm, 1999). Fourthly, the move from agrarian to industrial economies contributed to societal complexity resulting in a need for more formalised leaders to manage what are by now complex group actions and interactions between groups. Finally, the expansion of powerful socio-cognitive mechanics, such as theories in psychology and human behaviour, allowed followers to be created through manipulation. Theorists such as Dunbar (2010) note that the skilled use of language became evolutionarily essential on the basis of simple efficiencies and even elaborates on this toward a form of 'Machiavellian Intelligence.' By this point, emerge the formation of formalised, titled, agentic positions of leadership where actions can be to the betterment or exploitation of societies (Van Vugt, Hogan & Kaiser, 2008). However, in his publication, simply entitled '*Follow me*', Van Vugt (2008) also notes that, despite the proliferation of political and professional leaders in modern day life, leadership failure accounts for 60-75% of corporate enterprise.

There are many traces in the leadership discourse which support the primacy of followership in understanding leadership (Kellerman, 2008; Kellerman & Pinsky, 2020; Uhl-Bien et al, 2014; Crossman & Crossman, 2011). However, according to Garfield, Hubbard and Hagen (2019), there are three prominent theoretical models of leadership, which all support the concept of leaders as being chosen by followers. For example, Hooper, Kaplan and Boone's (2010) *Collective Action Model* of leadership can largely be interpreted from a micro-economics perspective. It correlates with larger group sizes where there are obvious returns for better coordination in complex activities, where no leadership would be counterproductive and where free-riders or underperformers are identified by the elected leader for retribution. Essentially this approach focusses on the costs of producing jointly beneficial outcomes for all members of the group and this means making sure everyone does their fair share of the effort. However, the punishment element of this has been claimed to defer in evolutionary terms to the physically dominant male sex (Kakkar & Sivanathan, 2017). This gendered position in leadership is visible in much of this perspective on leadership, perhaps due to its biological nature. However, a prevailing recognition in the literature views the topic of leadership as based on a bimodal view of *dominance* versus *prestige*. Therefore, what is presented subsequently is a brief insight to both of these components of leadership theory, but which then unites these as a form of duality in potential leadership practice.

The evolutionary context for the *dominance model* is linked to primordial biological constructs, argued for example by Tiger & Fox (1971), as a way to understand leadership by acknowledging our primate ancestry. Again, this is arguably taken from neurobiological antecedents linked to male aggression and access to fertile females. Authors such as Johnstone (2000) have linked this form of behaviour to 'reproductive skew'. In a dominance model, leaders are feared by followers and will normally hold an ability (or perceived ability) to harm followers. They have dominant personality, are mostly male and aim to attain coercive authority over followers. This is largely associated with populist, authoritarian political leaders such as former president Donald Trump, but is also associated with questionable moral fortitude, and aggressive narratives and behaviours (Kakkar & Sivanathan, 2017). Despite these transparent, often narcissistic, displays of thinking and behaving there have been times when these leaders have proven popular with followers (Cheng, Tracy & Henrich, 2010). And some authors contend that this dominance typology of leadership is seen

with increasing favour where humans perceive threats and/or instability in their environment (Kakkar & Sivanathan, 2017; Hogg & Adlemen, 2013; Vang Vugt & Smith, 2019). It is perhaps possible to consider this position as aligned to that of the instinctual evolutionary position offered earlier. For example, if when considering Hogg's (2007) Identity-Uncertainty Theory, human actors are highly motivated to reduce uncertainty as this is felt as a threat. However, where uncertainty is implicated in members of a group, those whose identity is strongly associated with that group are motivated to undertake more extreme attempts to overcome those environmental uncertainties. Moreover, according to Hogg, Meehan and Farquharson (2013), strong group identities as a form of support are often more agentic in overcoming other groups.

In contrast to a dominance modality, is the *prestige model*, although some argue that the former and the latter are both cognitively and behaviourally distinct (Cheng et al, 2013; Vang Vugt & Smith, 2019). However, it still represents a covert valorising of males in terms of reproductive status. For example, in evolutionary terms, prestige is a form of non-violent dominance. In historical human societies men sought to acquire the skills and abilities (prestige) to compete against other males to be attractive to women. And across many populations, men who are considered to have high social prestige have greater reproductive attainment (Van Vugt, 2006). Albeit skewed toward non-industrialised societies, von Rueden & Jaeggie's (2016) phylogenetic meta-analysis of 288 results from 33 nonindustrial populations showed a strong statistical association between measures of male status and 'reproductive success'. In small scale societies, prestige-modelled conflict resolution is also associated with reproductive success (see von Rueden, Gurvan & Kaplan, 2010; von Rueden et al 2014). Consequently, Helrich and Gil-White (2001) suggest that the prestige model centres around the psychological desire in followers to emulate the leader's success as the initial genesis of motivation. Likewise, proximity to the leader whose skills, aptitudes and abilities are seen as desirable makes evolutionary sense and the followers then valorise the prestige of the leader. It is not difficult to see such fundamental biological leadership modelling as evident in the 20th century leadership discourse, in heroic and charismatic observations, even in the management sciences (Bonau, 2017). Nonetheless, leaders in a prestige model are considered as amiable, have a level of expertise which can increase over time, can be male or female and normally create positive outcomes for followers as much as

for themselves (Kakkar & Sivanathan, 2017), linking well to theories of transformational and servant leaders. Both are now considered dualistically in order to examine the dynamics between the modalities but also in the relationships of leaders and followers. In order to build critique these are also linked to potential traces in the historical discourse.

3.4.1 Prestige-dominance duality

According to Van Vugt & Smith (2019), if consideration is offered to the classic philosophical construct of leadership, then two themes emerge which align with the bimodal prestige-dominance peculiarity. On the one hand Confucius, Plato, and monotheistic prophets are seen as both humble but inspirational, kind and competent (Adair, 2002). This approach aligns with the notion of leaders as role-models, who possess superior skills, abilities, and intellect but who also emulate desirable personal qualities. In this sense a leader's actions confer benefits to their followers, but about which leaders are often not specific. Moreover, according to Potters, Sefton & Vesterlund (2007), by leading by example, prestige leaders may not intend to recruit followers at all, as they instigate emotional connections in followers such as admiration and passion or even love. The emotional connection is significant however on both sides of the prestige-dominance model but for opposing reasons, perhaps. However, this admiration within followers for prestige-leaders offering positive vision, wisdom, but also generosity in that respect, can confer elevated social status on the leader: even where that was not the intention (Henrick, Chudek & Boyd, 2015). This form of leadership seems almost gravitational. However, in contrast, Vang Vugt and Smith (2019) note the philosophical position of Nicolo Machiavelli and Xenophon as nested in the dominance position. They view leaders as rulers. The key here is that, whilst the prestige position relies on benefits for follower, this position has a focus on cost should followers not conform with being led. The emotional triggering within followers is then visible but should not be seen as direct punishment such as in a manager subordinate transaction. The point of interest is in the hypothecated cost or benefit in the mind of the followers.

A view of this duality as a form of behavioural ecology, would fall short of its potential were it to simply elaborate a management approach espoused by Blake and Mouton (1982) and Fiedler, however. And it avoids this by showing a deeper understanding beyond

dominance/prestige as a behavioural continuum of motivation. For example, prestige is largely based on asymmetry of knowledge between the leader and the led, whereas in dominance the asymmetry is in strength and agency (Vang Vugt & Smith). Crudely modelled, this would view one as motivated by gravity and gain, and the other in repelling of pain. However, the observations are that a duality of these two positions is often employed as strategies by titled leaders. For example, it would be simple to determine a prevailing leadership *style* in large scale societies by considering Barack Obama and Donald Trump. In either of these leadership appointments, a series of expensive exercises were undertaken to convince followers of the prestige or dominance of either and the associated individual benefits and costs conferred to followers should either of their competitors be appointed. Consequently, human leaders tend to rely on a duality of prestige-dominance *tactics* to best influence group behaviours (Van Vugt, 2006). In terms of legitimacy, the prestige-dominance duality maps well to models of leadership autocracy versus democracy, or participative and directed styles, and correspond to this duality (Vroom & Yago, 1998), as do studies which consider positional versus personal power in organisation theory (Johnson & Duberley, 2006). Similarities can also be argued with the duality when considering the transactional versus transformational styles, where the latter aims to influence through inspiration and the former via controlled incentives. On the other hand, as Breevart et al (2014) points out, these incentives can be transactional when they are material and transformational to a degree if they are psychological. However, what a focus on the prestige-dominance model view achieves, is allowing better understanding of what leaders do, but also connecting to a deeper neurobiological follower apparatus. This opens up leadership as more than a set of actions, structures, or plans when considering organisations (Maner & Case, 2016). For example, it allows the demonstration of connections between the human biology of the subject, i.e., its material form, and socially constructed phenomena as useful in observing the peculiarity between leadership and management. However, where senior *leaders* are seen as setting strategic directions, who then set incentives and sanctions for *managers* to achieve that direction, we see that prestige-dominance leadership is ingrained or even hidden in organisational management (Drucker, 2012). In the context of titled leadership roles, there have been extensive studies in the field of social psychology which make a case for the correlation between leadership and status (Maner, 2017; Maner & Case, 2016; Cheng et al, 2013). And although prestige-dominance modelling remains grounded in leadership ability to

influence groups, the human actors will enact the approach in different ways. And although it is beyond the scope of this thesis to examine personality traits and the micro-economics of decision-making (Ferguson et al, 2019), prestige leaders do score higher in traits such as agreeableness and need for affiliation (Semenya & Honey, 2015) whereas dominance leaders score higher in the so called 'dark-triad' of narcissism, psychopathy and Machiavellianism (Jonasan & Webster, 2010; Klaas, 2022). Emotional rewards also have parallel differences in both parts of the duality: prestige leaders are associated with a sense of achievement or 'authentic pride', where dominant leaders associate with emotions of superiority and arrogance or 'hubristic pride' (Clarke, 2010). Whilst dominance-style leaders tend to be more assertive and use their influence for personal gain, prestige-style leaders tend to be generous, create attention from outside observers and are more liked (Maner & Case, 2017). However, both styles are focussed on groups, and according to Anderson and Kilduff (2009) both prioritise the interest of their groups as followers as much as each other.

In terms of how environmental conditions are perceived in the mind of followers, and its impact, according to Vang Vugt & Smith (2019) in experiments where people are asked to take part in mock presidential elections, there are distinctions in both prestige-dominance characteristics but also which are gender-biased based on environmental conditions. Specifically, where conflict is the environmental condition participants prefer dominant leaders, versus a shift toward more prestige leaders in stable peace conditions (Case & Maner, 2014; Mead & Maner, 2012). Curiously, participants prefer dominant leaders when a high risk of free-loaders exists in a group. Equally, according to Kakkar & Sivanthathan (2017) in an international comparison, dominant-style leaders are preferred where groups face large-scale economic uncertainty. Furthermore, Bastardo & Van Vugt (2019) note that followers make choices of economic trade-offs in choosing leaders from this bimodal model. Specifically, when there is a high probability that group coordination is more likely to fail (incurring cost to the follower), followers shift from the prestige to the dominant leadership profile as a preference (Luatsen & Peterson, 2017). Finally, correlations exist between levels of testosterone (positively in dominance and negatively in prestige) as well as neurological activity in either modality. For example, according to Watanabe & Yamamoto (2015) exposure to dominance-style leadership correlates with increased activity in threat-reward areas such as the amygdala, while prestige-style exposure stimulates cortical activity associated with social

learning. Whilst no causality is implied, it can be inferred that where groups of followers are engaged repeatedly in dominance leadership environments, they would likely be in biological position of threat response. It would be unlikely that this would be conducive to organisational harmony. Conversely, in prestige exposure, particularly where this were a normalised state of being, it is more likely that followers would be receptive to, and contributory to collaborative group working. However, another observation can be made, and it's point is twofold, namely, at an organisational level where there is perceived uncertainty or threat among a group, that potential followers will succumb to or welcome the potential dominance leadership approaches to restore stability. The second element is more challenging when asking, in whom are the uncertainties perceived. For example, the obvious thoughts on such things may conjure images of a choice CEO and their reputational characteristics and the subsequent approaches in an organisational context. However, if a government were to be the group who sensed the uncertainty and conflict, this becomes a noteworthy position for critique. Governments are created as temporary leaders, by electoral followers. Notwithstanding the wider political discourse in such matters, governments are by and large under constant threat of becoming unelected non-leaders, losing the followership. In particular, where that leadership were seen as questionable or incompetent by followers i.e., became government under threat, it is probable that a dominance style of public sector leadership, therefore management and administration, would result. Specifically, those groups who were at the behest of government leadership models with an appetite for certainty, would likely find their own professional leadership approaches, based perhaps on prestige modelling, as being fit for challenge. Figure 2 summarises the duality of prestige-dominance as one way in which to understand leader-follower dynamic, its complexity, but also its neurobiological antecedents.

Aspect of leadership	Prestige style	Dominance style
Philosophical tradition	Confucius	Machiavelli
Influence	Passive	Active
Mechanism of influence	Provision of benefits to followers (e.g., knowledge)	Inflicting costs on nonfollowers (e.g., sanctions)
Primary evolutionary function	Collective movement, foraging	Conflict resolution, warfare
Nature of decision-making hierarchy	Relatively flat, domain specific, based on expertise	Relatively steep, more generalized power
Source of deference	Information asymmetry	Power asymmetry
Followers	Active, respectful	Passive, fearful
Key emotional affiliations between leaders and followers	Primarily positive affect (liking, love, admiration, identification)	Mix of negative affect (anger, fear) and positive affect (respect, relief)
Role in group	Role model	Alpha
Phylogenetic history	Hunter-gatherers, non-human foraging animals	Primate dominance hierarchy negotiation
Potential costs for followers	Risk of coordination failure, difficulty delegating and scaling up groups	Risk of exploitation, succession problems

Summary and leadership definition

Viewing leadership from the perspective simply of influence is unhelpful, since influence can take many forms, from a need to survive, through to a drive to compete in an economic environment by almost any means. Seen from the perspective purely of following is equally futile for similar reasons and is laden with confirmation bias and possible false affirmation of the intention and efforts of leaders. When seen from a theoretical position we can see evolutions in ideas over time which all possibly address parts of the leader-follower dynamic in their own important way. Adding in the environment as the context of organisational management in which leading and following occurs, is mired in complexity since there are many multiples of this dynamic and human responses to stimuli are variable. However, in an organisational capacity, we can view leadership as driven by existential purpose and intension, i.e. some form of need for people to lead and follow, toward a different state which is assumed to be better than the current state. And viewing the inputs and outputs in this sort of change-activity from the perspective of dominance and prestige is valuable, and possibly even traceable to the types of changes needed and the environment in which the changes take place. Therefore, what is presented as defining leadership is not a duality of leading and following, but a complementarity in the connectedness between the need to affect change

and the way leadership impacts this. In this way it avoids an overly fixated view of the environment, or of the types of stimuli. To that end, leadership is defined as the complementarity of direction *and* influence. Defining leadership in this way ties usefully to Foucault's discourse as adjoining sets of practices, and of power/knowledge in impacting these practices. Equally useful in considering this complementarity is the role of subjectivity and governmentality as the ways in which individuals are positioned and position themselves within discourse. Focussing on direction *and* influence also permits a view of leadership as potentially fragile in its ability to maintain certain leader-follower relations. Likewise, defining it in this way aligns to a Foucauldian perspective and allow the conceptualisation of the power of discursive forces to maintain or shatter this complementarity.

Chapter 4. Power and midwifery leadership

Introduction

In order to critically examine midwifery leadership using Foucault's concepts it is first necessary to establish it as discourse. In keeping with the theoretical position in Chapter 2 this is done by showing the creation of *objects*, the creation of *concepts* and the creation of *strategies*. The fourth element, the creation of *subjects*, is undertaken in Chapter 5 using governmentality. The Chapter begins by establishing richer understanding of Foucault's discourse before applying power/knowledge as critique to midwifery leadership.

Discourse

In *The Archaeology of Knowledge* in 1974, despite power at this stage not being an explicit theme of his work, Foucault writes;

"...discourse is based on an 'already said'; and that this 'already said' is not merely a phrase that has already been spoken, or a text that has already been written, but a 'never said', an incorporeal discourse, a voice as silent as breath, a writing that is merely the hollow of its own mark". (Foucault, 1974, p.25)

Foucault's thoughts on the concept of discourse are associated in the wider 'linguistic turn' in organisational research in the social sciences in the second half of the 20th century (Curtis, 2014). Part of Foucault's views on discourse are as delimited groups of verbal expressions that constitute reasonably ordered, coherent and meaningful speech acts (Burrell, 1988). However, he establishes his analytical approach around discourse as an identification of the formative rules which resulted in the classification of expressions as coherent groups. In his inaugural lecture *L'ordre du discours (The Order of Speech)* held at the Collège de France in 1970, Foucault claims he strives to show *"in every society the production of discourse is at once controlled, selected, organized, and redistributed according to a certain number of procedures"* (Foucault, 1971, p.10). Likewise, according to Leclercq-Vandelannoitte (2011), Foucault's earlier attention to discursive formations (i.e., groups of statements), independent of their social setting, is better understood in his later genealogical framing of discourses as neither

“simple mirrors of social reality” nor as being *“a rule-governed, autonomous self-referring system”*, Instead, they are analysed as *“the crucial way to exercise power”* (Leclercq-Vandelannoitte, 2011, p. 1250). Consequently, Knights and Morgan (1991, p.253) view discourse in organisational research as a social arbitrator of *“ideas and practices which condition our ways of relating to, and acting upon, particular phenomena”* and which *“have the effect of constituting managerial and labour subjectivities that enhance the productive power of organisations”* (Knights & Morgan, 1991, p. 270). Likewise sets of discursive statement can shape how subjects can act and be Alvesson & Kärreman, 2000; Kärreman, 2014).

Foucault and power

Foucault views power as something which is done, not which is held, and as such is relational and not fixed. As Ball (2013, p.30) highlights, *“...these relations are not static, but nonetheless, at some points in time may as a set of strategies form a ‘general design or institutional crystallisation’ that is embodied in state apparatus”*. Central to Foucault’s concept of power is its relation to knowledge being both a product of and a productive force in the creation of knowledge. It brings to light Nietzsche’s notion of ‘truth telling’ rather than a sense of any definable and universal objective reality (Venye, 2010). In an interview in 1982, Foucault claimed his work on truth and power explores three classical problems,

“What are the relations we have to truth through scientific knowledge, to those “truth games” which are so important in civilization and in which we are both subject and objects? What are the relationships we have to others through those strange strategies and power relationships? And what are the relationships between truth, power, and self?”
(Foucault 1982, cited in Martin, 1998, p.9)

Accepting this means acknowledging that the claims made by the discourse (or discourses) involved in leading midwifery are equally contingent in truths and power relationships. The Foucauldian dynamic of knowledge-power, which goes beyond simply a connection or spontaneous relationship between the two, is illustrated by Mills (2003, p.70), cited by Ball

2013), *“Foucault characterises power-knowledge as an abstract force that determines what will be known, rather than assuming that individual thinkers develop ideas and knowledge”*.

For Foucault, organisations, particularly those involving the state, provide an ideal opportunity for this dynamic to propagate. Accordingly, Ball (2013) notes this can appear to bring to life things which previously did not exist, where knowledge components are accurate but *“which are the target of social regulation at a given moment in time”* (Foucault, 1983, p.2). Therefore, it is vital to see the power-knowledge dynamic in midwifery as constituent in the wider discursive formation of what is accepted to be knowledge with respect to leadership in midwifery. If a discourse is composed of sets of practices that systematically form the objects of which they speak, then it must also constrain as well as enable other forms of thinking and knowing. This illustrates the power of the discourse in not only normalising the workings within it, but in abnormalising any thinking outwith it (Olssen, 2010; Graham, 2005).

4.1 The formation of objects

The first object involves considering midwifery as part of a state-owned maternity care within the UK National Health Service (NHS). The second object is midwives themselves as a professional group. A third object is the role of the universities in the discourse of leadership in midwifery as they are the sole means through which midwives can enter the profession and therefore the discourse.

The first of these objects comprehends the NHS as a corporation of health-relates services and that midwifery is nested within that in varying forms across the UK. As such it is directly impacted upon by the wider discourse of UK public sector leadership, management, and administration. For over 30 years the NHS, specifically the way in which its leaders and managers have been urged to practice, has been as a result of adopting the neoliberal economic concept of New Public Management (NPM) (George, 2017). With the aim to make public sector services more like private sector businesses, the concept of NPM is built on the hypothecated economic efficiencies of the free market. Historically for example, Roy Griffiths, Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of Sainsburys, was requested in 1980 by Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher, to review NHS care which had been led by clinicians until this point. His solution was to create General Managers who would be accountable for income and expenditure on the basis that Griffiths had found the NHS was suffering from institutional

stagnation (Griffiths, 1983). Writing six years after the revelations of Griffiths, Klein appears to suggest the NHS was politically led toward a management revolution when he wrote,

“...the general management revolution swept on. Everywhere at every level, new managers were appointed: some brought from industry and the armed services, but primarily they were old-style administrators reborn as managers, with only a sprinkling of doctors and nurses.” (Klein 1989, p.209).

Until Thatcher’s radicalisations, the NHS was a universal public service constructed from groups of professionals all of whom had some form of ‘caring’ built within their professional ideology. And they were largely managed in this way until the Griffiths Report, with each discipline deemed to be steadily improving levels of clinical ability in their professional fields (Harrison & Politt, 1994). However, their collective presence in a national service became something which became an object needing to be managed. But management did not directly contribute to clinical *outputs* within the service being managed. Rather, its target was to perpetually reconfigure resources toward financial efficiency (Ackroyd & Bolton, 1999). Consideration of this corporate object might assume that health professionals can and should naturally align to it. Possibly that alignment is what leadership is intended to influence toward. For example, leadership within the midwifery profession might reasonably focus on direction and influence around its primary *raison d’être*, the relationship between midwives and birthing women. A corporate object however might petition for the *raison d’État* (reason of state) which Foucault outlined in *Security, Territory, Population*, his posthumously published Lectures at the Collège de France, 1977-1978 (Foucault, 2009). However, a corporate object would naturally lead to standardisation and financial metrification, as even the worst performing business models have a grasp of profit and loss, and constant comparison to others in the marketplace. As a visible part of influence in the midwifery discourse, most universities in the UK can also be viewed as corporate bodies, with most adopting charitable status of some description, they are also part of a neoliberal apparatus (Lorenz, 2012; Giroux, 2002; Ramírez & Hyslop-Margison, 2015). The discourse of midwifery leadership therefore cannot be isolated from that of a discourse of public sector healthcare and therefore, as Venye, (2010) explains, the objects within a discourse cannot be separated from the framing

of the ways in which we come to know of it. The object of the midwifery profession receives further critique in formation of strategies in 4.3.3.

4.2 The formation of concepts

The topic of leadership spans multiple theories, frameworks, models, and applications. However, Foucault's theoretical stance allows us to focus on those contingencies which help frame or limit the leadership discourse in midwifery. However, since midwifery is not exclusive of the discourse in public sector healthcare, many contingencies will cross discursive fields. Therefore, the key discursive concepts for consideration in midwifery leadership are; the drive towards improved safety, deepening professional accountability and assurances from government around the role of regulated practices. Foucault's view of problematising discourse was around searches for '*instances of discursive production*', '*the production of power*' and '*the propagation of knowledge*' (Foucault, 1984, p.12). And therefore, the rationality of such things can be seen in the antecedents of the movement toward systems of clinical governance as,

"...a system through which NHS organisations are accountable for continuously improving the quality of their services and safeguarding high standards of care by creating an environment in which excellence in clinical care will flourish." (Sally and Donaldson 1998, p. 61)

At this time a shift toward prioritising safe clinical practice was also met with a demand to inspect and adjust performances of clinical professional groups. A major emphasis in patient safety appears in the UK healthcare archive in the report *An Organisation with a Memory* by the Department of Health (2000). However, patient safety has a very long prehistory, in organised attempts to understand patient harm in the NHS since 1948 (Sirrs, 2022). However, until 1989 this history is largely devoid of terms around managing risk, in every subsequent year after which there is documented evidence of White Papers, institutional publications, the emergence of related journals and the appointment of the first Patient Safety Commissioner in 2022 (Sirrs, 2022).

4.2.1 Discursive discontinuities

Critique for Foucault was, *“a matter of pointing out what kinds of assumptions, what kinds of familiar, unchallenged, unconsidered modes of thought on which the practices we accept rest”* (Foucault, 1988, p. 154). And his use of discourse encourages us to seek *“displacements and transformations of concepts”* (Foucault, 1972, p.4). This legitimises the inspection of *“moments of discontinuity and change in political, economic, institutional, and societal practices”* (Motion & Leitch, 2007, p.263). In terms of events arising in the discourse of midwifery which could be seen as discursive discontinuities, this arguably comes in the report by Sir Bill Kirkup (2015). However, despite Foucault’s contestations around causality and historical events, which he called *“eventalisation”* (Foucault, 1987, p.104) these events could have significant political impact on the trajectory of priorities in midwifery leadership. Therefore, unpicking these historically emergent struggles can illustrate the formation of concepts involved in midwifery leadership as part of a wider discourse of public sector health service. For example, arguably the first publicised punctuation event directing large scale change in the leadership and management of UK health care professionals was in 1995 at the Bristol Royal Infirmary, which was as a result of one of the first cases of whistleblowing (Smith, 1998). The NHS corporate response was to include in the NHS Plan 2000 the creation of The Commission for Health Improvement to ensure such poor practices did not happen again. This was the first time that the clinical performance of the NHS was assessed by an external independent organisation (Patterson & Lilburne, 2003). Furthermore, the Kennedy Report in 2001 noted that a national director for children's services should be appointed to lead the development of child-centred healthcare, and recommended appraisal, continuing professional development and revalidation for all healthcare professionals to ensure they keep their skills to sufficient standard. However, this signalled a move toward an arguably consumerist position when noting the NHS should allow patients to access information about the relative performance of hospitals, services, or doctors (Butler, 2002).

Because midwifery is largely nested within maternity and neonatal care, incidents of systemic NHS failure impact on midwifery as a profession and therefore its leadership. For example, the 1999 inquiry into the unethical removal of organs and tissue from children and babies in Alder Hey NHS Foundation Trust (UK Government, 2001) could not exist in isolation from the Bristol Inquiry four years earlier (Smith, 1998). Neither would the impact of the Shipman

Inquiry in 2001 which resulted in five reports from July 2002 to December 2004 (Smith, 2003; UK Government, 2007). The UK Government Report in 2007 to Parliament regarding the inquiries findings was titled, *Learning from tragedy, keeping patients safe*. It notes that the General Medical Council had already started work on a 'doctor's MOT' by way of an appraisal and revalidation system repeated every 5 years (GMC, 2000). The report also notes the Shipman Inquiry Reports have led the creation of a White Paper which represent a comprehensive reform of the regulation of health care professionals. The title of the White Paper makes clear its rationale, *Trust, Assurance and Safety- The Regulation of Health Professionals in the 21st Century* (UK Government, 2007). If healthcare is viewed in the broader discourse of society, it can be inferred that trust and the assurance of safety are to be seen publicly as being redressed by government. The public may need assurance therefore that professional groups would be held accountable to government and less so to their own models of internal professionalism. As the White Paper points out,

"...the Government will agree arrangements to ensure that all councils become more accountable to Parliament, presenting annual reports to the UK Parliament" and that, "...to dispel the perception that councils are overly sympathetic to the professionals they regulate, council members will be independently appointed". (p.5)

Historically it seems reasonable to consider such statements as indicative of a post-Shipman perturbation in dynamic between the trust of the public and the state, and the state and medical professionals, in whom a degree of trust has been so historically implicit. The conception of *clinical governance* is first seen in the Labour Government White Paper, *The New NHS-modern, dependable* (Department of Health, 1997). The paper highlights the need for standardised guidelines for clinical procedures, and the creation of the National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE) to drive the approach. This is significant in the concept of standardised procedures and the genesis of guidelines for practice from a centralised point. In considering what clinical governance means as both a way of thinking and a way of doing things for professionals in the NHS it becomes clearer how this fits well with the Foucauldian *formation of concepts* and links to *objects*. For example, clinical governance describes on the one hand an attitude, i.e., the acceptance that health care organisations have a corporate responsibility to provide safe and effective services and to strive for continuous improvement

in performance and safety. On the other hand, it describes a set of structures and procedures which help to put that attitude into effect and normalise them (Sccally & Donaldson, 1998; Van Zwanenberg & Harrison, 2000). In this sense the level of responsibility by an organisation is highlighted, as is the perpetual need to measure and exceed current levels of performance (continuous improvement) and that the NHS as an employer accountable directly to Parliament, make this a leadership priority driven by a political discourse. In other words, not only is standing still not an option, the inspection or assessment of activity around that must be embraced by those within the leadership and administration of the NHS.

Below, Table 2 shows a timeline of the high-profile events in health care in the UK. It is worth noting that whilst systemic errors are found in all, the case of nurse Beverly Allitt was criminal in nature but did not lead to the same high-level response as Shipman’s murderous behaviour. The list is not meant to be exhaustive, however the impact on what are termed in the media as ‘scandals’ in health care and the resultant policy responses have been correlated as significant in the literature (Hutchison, 20016; Ekström & Johansson. 2008). It should be noted that recommendations of enquiries which highlighted the need to consider leadership only began in Francis Report (2013). Prior to this, according to Hutcheson (2016), the recommendations focussed largely on monitoring activity of professionals (mainly doctors).

Table 2

Major Error Event	Archive Document	Service
Beverly Allitt 1991	The Clothier Report 1994	Nursing
Bristol Royal Infirmary 1995	The Kennedy Report 2001	Surgery
Alder Hey NHS Foundation Trust	The Redfern Report 2001	Surgery
Shipman Inquiry	The Smith Reports 2002-2004	General Practice
Northwick Park Hospital	Healthcare Commission 2005	Maternity
Mid Staffordshire NHS Foundation Trust	The Francis Report 2013	Nursing/system failure
Morcombe Bay NHS Foundation Trust 2004-2013	The Kirkup Report 2015	Maternity
Heart of England NHS Foundation Trust	The James Report 2020	Surgery
Shrewsbury & Telford NHS Trust	The Ockenden Report (2022	Maternity
East Kent NHS Foundation Trust 2018-2021	Kirkup (2022)	Maternity
Nottingham University NHS Trust 2021	Ongoing	Maternity

According to Thompson (2000) adverse events, which are often labelled 'scandals', when happening in public sector services can have a significant public and political response. He categorises four features of these scandals are significant. These characteristics involve actions in contravention of an expected professional role. Secondly an attempt to conceal these events or actions. Public knowledge of the questionable events, and where these factors create an outrage within the public domain. It is natural to draw conclusions that response to such things would be without a political dimension given the nature of the NHS.

4.3 Formation of strategies

Foucault views power as relational and existing in a dynamic of power/knowledge. Power is not therefore structural in nature but reinforced in a complex interaction of social relations. As Ball (2013, p.30) highlights, *"...these relations are not static, but nonetheless, at some points in time may as a set of strategies form a 'general design or institutional crystallisation' that is embodied in state apparatus"*. For its use in problematising midwifery leadership Foucault's concept of power brings to light Nietzsche's notion of 'truth telling' rather than a sense of any definable and universal objective reality (Venye, 2010). In an interview in 1982, Foucault claimed his work explores three classical problems,

"What are the relations we have to truth through scientific knowledge, to those "truth games" which are so important in civilization and in which we are both subject and objects? What are the relationships we have to others through those strange strategies and power relationships? And what are the relationships between truth, power, and self?" (Foucault 1982, cited in Martin, 1998, p.9-15)

Accepting this means acknowledging that the claims made by the discourse (or discourses) involved in leading midwifery are equally contingent in truths and power relationships. According to Mills (2003, p.70), *"Foucault characterises power-knowledge as an abstract force that determines what will be known, rather than assuming that individual thinkers develop ideas and knowledge"*. Therefore, it is vital to see the power-knowledge dynamic in midwifery as constituent in the wider discursive formation of what is accepted to be knowledge with respect to leadership in midwifery. If a discourse is composed of sets of practices that systematically form the objects of which they speak, then it must also constrain as well as

enable other forms of thinking and knowing. In *The Archaeology of Knowledge* in 1974, despite power at this stage not being an explicit theme of his work Foucault writes:

“...discourse is based on an ‘already said’; and that this ‘already said’ is not merely a phrase that has already been spoken, or a text that has already been written, but a ‘never said’, an incorporeal discourse, a voice as silent as breath, a writing that is merely the hollow of its own mark”. (p.25)

Therefore, the strategic deployment of truths via power/knowledge noted in the theoretical framework and be seen throughout the midwifery leadership discourse by using some of Foucault's concepts of disciplinary power, and this is carried out here.

4.3.1 Docile bodies

Fundamentally this power requires control to maximise some form of utility, in other words to make individuals useful *and* to make useful individuals. He outlines four procedures, or disciplines which, *“made possible the meticulous control of the operations of the body”* (Foucault, 1975, p. 137). Foucault deploys one element of this approach by what he called ‘the means of correct training’ (Foucault & Rainbow, 1984). And this is made possible through the mechanisms of *hierarchical observation, normalizing judgment, and the examination*. By docility Foucault does not imply submissive timidity, rather he means to elaborate on the body as something which is malleable and manipulable, *“A body is docile that can be subjected, used, transformed and improved”* (Foucault, 1977, p.136). Each are considered here in turn to build critical examination of the discourse of midwifery.

Hierarchical observations

This can be seen as the way in which the NHS Leadership Academy positions and normalises leadership as part of the ‘truth spoken’ by selectively pursuing students in their programme, *Students-learning to lead in healthcare’* The quote offered by newly qualified nurse Anna below shows this propagation of truths spoken,

“When we’re training, it’s crucial that we learn some sort of leadership from the start, in particular that leadership in essence is not just about management, but also about advocating, challenging and nurturing, no matter our role or banding”

(NHS Leadership Academy, 2022b)

But also, in the manner in which NHS hierarchy and personal development is correlated with leaderly abilities, even in the naming of heroic leaders for each of the programmes which claim to be able to develop them below in Table 3.

Table 3:

Edward Jenner Programme	Mary Seacole Programme	Rosalind Franklyn Programme	Elizabeth Garret Anderson Programme	Nye Bevan Programme	Stepping Up Programme	Ready Now Programme
Want to get ready for your first leadership or management role? The Edward Jenner programme will build your foundation-level leadership skills.	If you’re in your first leadership role, the Mary Seacole programme will develop your knowledge and skills in leadership and management	For mid-level leaders aspiring to lead large and complex programmes, departments, services, or systems.	For middle to senior leaders, this programme will help you challenge the status quo, drive lasting change, and prepare for senior roles.	If you’re a senior leader who wants to move into a board role, the Nye Bevan programme will help you develop the skills attitudes and behaviours you need to succeed.	For Black, Asian and minority ethnic (BAME) colleagues, Stepping Up will help you develop your leadership and management	Ready Now supports senior BAME leaders to move into board level positions and significantly more senior roles.

(Adapted from NHS Leadership Academy, 2022a)

It is likely not coincidental that the programme aimed at ‘Board level’ which is the ultimate point of agency in the NHS, is named after the ‘father and creator’ of the NHS, Nye Bevan. However, it seems curious that two separate programmes are targeted at black and minority ethnic leaders, for whom presumably the theorists underpinning the work of the others are not entirely suitable. It is however a useful example of targeting the living body with maximum utility, arguably even at a genetic level. However, the genesis of leadership thinking, can be seen to be implanted at the very bottom of the hierarchy if one considers student

midwives in such a formation. *The Standards for Proficiency for Midwives* devised and implemented by the midwifery regulator (NMC, 2019a) and informally referred to as ‘the future midwife standards’, outline the outcomes that midwives must achieve at the point of registration. The emphasis in **bold** from the documents summary illustrates the regularity of the leadership demand.

*“Critical thinking, problem solving, positive role modelling, and **leadership development** are fundamental components of safe and effective midwifery practice. Midwives play a **leading** role in enabling effective management and team working, promoting **continuous improvement**, and encouraging a **learning culture**. Midwives recognise their own strengths, as well as the strengths of others. They take responsibility for their own continuing professional development and know how they can contribute to others’ development and education, including students and colleagues. They have the ability to develop in their careers in directions that can include practice, education, research, management, **leadership**, and policy settings. They continue to develop and refine their knowledge, skills, resourcefulness, flexibility and strength, self-care, critical and strategic thinking, emotional intelligence, and **leadership skills** throughout their career.”* (NMC, 2019b, p. 5)

Both the NHS and universities effectively endorse the ranking of leaderly abilities, normally associated with ascension through hierarchy, and both often entwine this with management responsibilities. The NHS on the other hand has Agenda for Change bandings for midwives which rank directly to publicly available salary reward (see NHS Careers). Midwifery titles vary even in single geographical areas; however, the responsibilities and accountabilities are clearly hierarchical. For example, ‘Lead Midwife’, and ‘Consultant Midwife’, all of which are relative and accountable to the four territorial government appointments of Chief Midwifery Officer (CMO).

Normalising judgment

Foucault's views on normalisation are extensive, however, in *Security, Territory, Population*, a lecture given at the Collège de France in 1978, Foucault outlines,

“Normalization consists first of all in positing a model, an optimal model that is constructed in terms of a certain result, and the operation of disciplinary normalization consists in trying to get people, movements, and actions to conform to this model”.

(Foucault, 2007, p.58)

It can be viewed in the midwifery discourse as sets of corrective actions, via e.g., audit or inspection, by way of highlighting the non-conformity whilst at the same time legitimising the need to conform. This normalisation is one of the ways in which discursive formations reinforce and validate the required activity within them. Ball (2013) argues that normalisation is part of the process of classification and therefore a way of enhancing disciplinary power via distributed ability and acceptability. That acceptance however must also run parallel to a view of non-acceptability. These normalising judgements are made in professional midwifery by the same regulatory body that created the previously noted future midwife standards via their fitness to practice system, much like other healthcare regulators. On the one hand, the filaments of standardisation toward collective ‘usefulness’ are visible but at the same time bodies are directed as living individuals to exist within that. One specific element of this form of disciplinary approach which pertains to classifications and normalisation, is the ability of the discourse to separate the worthy from the unworthy, by what Foucault terms dividing practices. In his lecture series at College de France in 1978 *Security, Territory, Population*, Foucault claims of disciplinary power that it,

“...normalises and of course analyses and breaks down; it breaks down individuals, places, times, movements, actions and operations. It breaks them down into components such that they can be seen on the one hand, and modified on the other”

(Foucault, 2009, p.56)

The examination

None of the elements of Foucault’s approach appear in isolation, however, the examination is arguably a clear example of disciplinary power. Writing in Sheridan’s translation of *Discipline and Punish* (1977) Foucault notes of the examination:

“...the examination combines the techniques of an observing hierarchy and those of a normalising judgement. It is a normalising gaze, a surveillance that makes it possible to qualify, to classify and to punish. It establishes over individuals a visibility through which one can differentiate them and judges them.” (Foucault, 1977, p185)

Ball (2013) points out the examination is not simply a grading threshold when viewed in Foucauldian terms, it is key to measuring against principles as a form of classification, subjects within a discourse. Whilst the exam has the obvious association with the university's role in this discourse, Foucault's conceptualisation of it allows this to be seen throughout the midwifery leadership discourse. The Future Midwife standards (NMC, 2019a) have a number of subsequent filaments of examination of those in the midwifery discourse, such as *Standards for pre-registration midwifery programmes* (NMC, 2019c). These establish thresholds of access to the university programmes and controls the teaching and learning content of educations. The third element is set out in the regulators control of the space and time spent by student midwives in practice-based education, which is mainly the NHS. This is outlined in *Standards for student supervision and assessment* (NMC, 2019c). Fitness to practice is examined against *The Nursing Midwifery Code* (NMC, 2018d), referred to by most as 'the code'.

Likewise, midwifery educators must be registered with the NMC, no matter their epistemic credibility. Similarly, midwives supervising and assessing midwifery students must undertake specialist examination themselves driven by the *Standards for Supervision and Assessment* (NMC, 2019c) and become categorised as a Practice Supervisor or a Practice Assessor. Midwives also must revalidate triennially, as noted previously, and this too is a form of self-examination and declaration as being fit to be within the midwifery discourse. All of these points of examination exert influence in some way and becomes an individual locus of possibilities in influencing the direction of midwifery.

4.3.2 Panopticism

This aspect of Foucault's power is usefully illustrative of his later work on self-governance based on the panopticon prison of Jeremy Bentham. However, the English former lawyer did suggest his 'inspection houses' could be used in schools, hospitals, and factories (Cohen,

2010). According to Jardine (2005), the costs associated with *actually* watching the movements of the incarcerated were prohibitive. Because the prisoners are unable to see their single observer they are inclined to assume, and therefore behave, as though they were being observed. In effect, although never actually observed any of the time, they are observed all the time. A set of knowledge and behaviours are now entangled between watchers and the watched. Foucault's writings evolve from the simple physical structure of the panopticon toward the principle of *panopticism*. The formalised systems of work-based 'performance appraisal' is normalised in the NHS (Coates, 2000). However, this gaze has been noted as a phenomenon in higher education (Prowes & Prowes, 2009; Bryman, Haslam & Webb, 2006), and therefore can be used to demonstrate its reach in incubation of a modified midwifery workforce. For example, student midwives are under panoptic scrutiny from the first day of their degree. Within the University of the West of Scotland e.g., where personal details are captured on an electronic system where administrators and academics alike access student scores for assessments in the midwifery programme. Another online system displays the details and nature of the clinical area they are in, have been, and are going to be and their ranking scores. It also displays student personal reflections about those and other assessments. On the same system, allocated academics can view details where concerns have been raised about character or behaviour and any reparative activity associated with that. Equally their activity on the university Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) tracks and displays which files and pages have been read, by whom, and when. Students also carry an electronic 'swipe card' which must be waved over a scanner when attending classes which is automatically recorded and displayed by university staff with certain access privileges. Midwifery academics however have student-rated feedback on each component of modular learning, coordinated by the university administration and exhibited in electronic 'dashboard' displays. In this framing of direction and influencing in midwifery discourse, educational leaders are watching their students, but are themselves being watched by the university, which is also being watched by the NMC. The NMC are watched by the regulator of regulators: the Professional Standards Authority (PSA), beyond which is the discourse of political state.

4.3.3 The professional subjects and truth

Foucault's use of speaking freely to power or *parrhesia* is formidable in the current context of midwifery leadership as discourse in considering *truths* spoken from a relative position of

subordination. This conceptualises the possible actions of single actors within a power relationship, but importantly also the truths of entire professions with respect to their governors and commissioners. By way of illustrating such a power/knowledge dynamic, the example is offered of the work of Professor Mary Renfrew and colleagues, extensive global research in a four-part Lancet Series: *Midwifery and quality care: findings from a new evidence-informed framework for maternal and newborn care*. It was published in 2014. Below is their evidential truth of what a midwife provides.

“...skilled, knowledgeable, and compassionate care for childbearing women, new-born infants, and families across the continuum throughout pre-pregnancy, pregnancy, birth, postpartum, and the early weeks of life. Core characteristics include optimising normal biological, psychological, social, and cultural processes of reproduction and early life; timely prevention and management of complications; consultation with and referral to other services; respect for women’s individual circumstances and views; and working in partnership with women to strengthen women’s own capabilities to care for themselves and their family”. (Renfrew et al, 2014, p.1129)

The Lancet journal and the archive of Cochrane evidence reviews are a responsible source of evidence in healthcare science. In the previously noted future midwife standards, the NMC claimed they were developed via an extensive and rigorous process of evidence review citing the evidence of Renfrew et al (NMC, 2019c). Renfrew et al (2014) reviewed extensive international research, and not only examined the views and experiences of women, but also undertook an analysis of 461 Cochrane systematic reviews to construct the framework to present the critical elements of high-quality midwifery care. This uncovered 122 effective practices significant to the care of childbearing women and infants. From these, 72 effective practices were further refined and analysed for specific potential outcome improvements in maternity care. Within the scope of midwifery, practice their research identified 56 specific outcomes. In its publication in the Lancet in 2014 it does not mention leadership once and yet it appears repeatedly in the life of students and registered midwives by way of a foundational component of professional practice from the midwifery regulator.

The second example is, *Leadership & Leadership Development in Health Care: the evidence base* (West et al, 2015). On behalf of The Kings Fund it points out,

“The leadership task is to ensure direction, alignment and commitment within teams and organisations. Direction ensures agreement and pride among people in relation to what the organisation is trying to achieve, consistent with vision, values, and strategy.”

(West et al, 2015p.2)

It does not provide ‘evidence’ for leadership in the way that a cumulative meta-analysis provides it when determining the efficacy of treatments of patients (Lau, Schmid & Calmers, 1995). Yet it is clear in its setting of leadership in a context of usefulness in the pursuit of strategic organisational success. It does however highlight caution in the customary use of bureaucracy when it notes, *“Commentators have argued that regulatory systems, increasing competition and setting targets are inadequate levers for bringing about the fundamental changes required to respond to the [leadership] challenges”* (p.5). As well as being illustrative of power-knowledge dynamics, it usefully illustrates the challenge in generating evidence of what leadership is at all. For example,

“Despite thousands of publications on the topic of leadership in health care, consistent with others (eg Hartley, Martin, & Bennington, 2008; Kim & Newby-Bennett, 2012) our review reveals relatively little research conducted to a high academic standard”.

(West et al, 2015, p.22)

This review of evidence found that actual evidence of effective leadership in the NHS is not only variable and inconclusive but that *“little robust evidence has been accumulated, despite the vast sums spent”* (p.23). A sceptical position toward this could infer this evidence-base for leadership in healthcare has found little evidence to support its own existence or claims in its published title. Despite the apparent credibility of its authorship, its place in the archive of healthcare leadership archive and its lacklustre claims, the leadership topic is still highly prevalent as something which is to be embraced. The midwifery profession as an object within this discourse therefore has evidence as a truth formation in power/knowledge, and which prioritises women and a midwife’s relationship with woman. And despite an apparent lack of

evidence in the application of leadership in healthcare the inference drawn is the existence of a power/knowledge dynamic between discursive actors in terms of the governors and the governed. Likewise in terms of parrhesia the ways in which the professional object speaks truth about truth games will be affected by that dynamic.

Summary

The key concept within the midwifery leadership discourse is a continuation of the historical drive from government to stabilise and make accountable, the actions of healthcare professionals, and that this is done in a visible way. Potentially this driving concept is based on the prevalence of public investigations into maternity care in NHS England. As objects midwives, individually and as a professional group are integral with the concepts of government. A stark illustration of Foucault's power/knowledge can be seen in presenting the types of truth expected and accepted in professional midwifery and the arguable lack of evidence that leadership is effective in improving the poor maternity performance in some parts of the UK. Despite this we can see the emphasis placed on leadership as part of hierarchical ascendance in NHS England. Panopticism is evident at almost every level in the hierarchy of practice and knowledge, with the control of student activity, behaviours, knowledge, and importantly as part of normalising this as they enter the profession in the NHS. A departure begins to be seen here from professional practice as an internally normalised activity, to an external apparatus of demands from the regulator.

Chapter 5. Governmentality and midwifery leadership

Introduction

This chapter uses Foucault's concept of governmentality to critique the subjectivity element of the theoretical framework. It first offers a critical understanding of governmentality as an element of Foucault's work before using it to problematise the midwifery leadership discourse. It focusses on the governmental components of the *pastoral, reason of state, police, neoliberalism, and governmentality and the self*.

Governmentality

In the course summary to his 1977/78 Collège de France *Securite, Territoire, Population*, Foucault acknowledged he had been concerned with "*the genesis of a political knowledge [savoir] that was to place at the centre of its concerns the notion of population and the mechanisms capable of ensuring its regulation*" (Foucault, 2004, p. 373). In the fourth lecture of this series on 'governmentality' he states that this title of Security, Territory, Population should remove territory and replace it with "government" (Foucault, 2004), and in that lecture he notes that the entire series should have been named "the history of governmentality" (ibid, p.11). Some time after these lectures Foucault explains this evolution in his work as "*the rudiments of something I've been working at for the last two years. It's the historical analysis of what we would call, using an obsolete term, the 'art of government'*." (2000, p.324). However, the value of Foucault's work on governmentality can be seen in a 1977 interview where he discusses the pact of security between state and the people has shifted from one of frontiers, territory, and borders to simply, "*you will be guaranteed*" (1994, p. 385). According to Burchell, Gordon and Miller (1991), this guarantee warrants security from such things as uncertainty, damage, risk, illness, lack of work, etc. Consequently, such arts of government are still imbued in populations with the same forms of knowledge and power practices as in most of Foucault's writing, but they do so over a much wider landscape of objects. He often referred to government as 'the conduct of conduct' (Foucault, 1982). In his lecture on governmentality, he uses the work of Machiavelli and the prince to show the evolution in the art of governing, specifically the shift from governing territory to the governing of things. His critique of that 16th Century philosophy notes that,

“sovereignty is not exercised on things, but above all on a territory and consequently on the subjects who inhabit it” (Burchell, Gordon & Miller, 1991, p,93). And this is based on the belief that the prince inherits his territory through entitlement and not through any particular set of abilities which may appear to warrant that inheritance. He also notes the prince is external to his principality and not part of it. For Foucault however, this fragile synthetic link between the prince and his subjects is not only a governmental singularity but as such is *“continually under threat from outside from the prince’s enemies”*. (Burchill, Gordon and Miller, 1991, p.95) This singular fragile linkage then become the object about which the art of governing is most concerned. As this is a singular form of object to govern, the goal here is identifying threats to it and scaling these in terms of their level of impact, but also *“to develop the art of manipulating relations of force that will allow the prince to ensure the protection of his principality.”* (Burchell, Gordon & Miller, p. 90). This has some form of familiarity with contemporary political risk management (Giambona, Graham, & Harvey, 2017). However, toward the end of the lecture he notes the three historically evolving models of state as corresponding to one of justice, one of administration and lastly the governmental state. He says of the latter *“this could be seen as corresponding to a type of society controlled by dispositifs of security”*. (Burchell, Gordon & Miller, p, 104). It is important to note that his position is historical and not an observation of modern political dynamics, however it is useful in refining his governmentality as tool for analysis if considering some of the text used in the lecture. For example, in his shift toward government of a population he uses terms such as *“population mass, volume, density”* (p.104) which implies the requirement calculability about that population. And Foucault's biopolitics is the means by which the group of living beings is understood as a population is measured in order to be governed (Eldon, 2007).

Foucault's governmentalisation of the state comes from his critique of the histories of governing and the power of truths. From man's relationship with the sovereignty of deities, and with monarchies, toward the *raison d'état* (reason of state) and likewise the development of Foucault's biopolitics (Foucault, 1978). A key understanding here is the primacy of reason as accepted truth and the effects of that on populations being governed. Accordingly, Lazzarato (2002) on biopower notes in a governmental shift toward *raison d'état* it is the value of calculation (*calcul*) rather than an earlier notion of wisdom (*sagesse*) which is the model for these rationalities to allow *“calculation of forces, relations, wealth, and elements of force”*

(Foucault, 2004, p.135). The sub-headings used next from Foucault are not separate ways in which governmentality 'happens' whereby one approach is adopted at the exclusion of the others. Rather they are ways in which governmentality can pinpoint key elements of critique for a researcher.

5.1 The Pastoral

Foucault outlines this governmentality in the context of Christianity and the metaphors of monotheistic approaches to governing. There are some resonances here with the leadership theories discussed Chapter 3, for example in psychoanalytical theory (Obholzer, 1996) and with heroic modelling (Spector, 2015). For example, his concept of the pastoral in governmentality terms is still a form of power whereby the subject aims to align themselves with some prescribed collective good where the subject becomes a vessel for the ultimate totalising power, that of the deity (Bevir, 2011). It would be unwise to misplace the eternal punishments proselytised by clergy for straying too far from that influence. However, it does perhaps illustrate a view of leadership in midwifery as maternalistic or even matriarchal and this allows a concept of wisdom and embodied knowledge in the contextually experienced midwife, not unlike Aristotelian *phronesis* (Deery & Fischer, 2017). In midwifery leadership it would align better with prestige leadership types seen in Chapter 3 and 'governance for the good', strongly relating to midwifery identity. It would however conflict with the policy level rhetoric in leadership which argues away from 'heroic leadership' toward more distributed forms. The Kings Fund (2011) publication on the future of NHS leadership used the term 'no more hero's' in its title. However, pastoral governmentality would emphasise trust in the midwifery expertise of professionals and professionalism. Gillies (2013) aligns this pastoral view to the historical model of the school headmaster. However, he also illustrates a valuable point form were this to be modelled in a midwifery leadership discourse,

"...one of the features of the pastoral is the absence of hard, statistical data and indeed any major focus on evaluation of performance. It is a different form of management at work, in which the aims and goals are around human relations and human wellbeing"

(Gillies, 2013, p. 72)

This pastoral perspective aligns well to a professionalised direction and influence in midwifery toward woman-centric values, and choices, largely accepted historically as part of professional identity (Divall, 2014). Midwifery leaders would rely on internalised professional authority and evidence-based practice in a power/knowledge dynamic. Important perhaps is the midwifery follower in this pastoral position which arguably relies less on coercion and docility and instead shows deference to professional wisdom (Divall, 2014). As a perspective of governmental rationality there is a clear moral sense of right and wrong which would unlikely clash with what the 'pastor' would request of their parishioners. In the same way, the matriarch would unlikely adopt a governmental technology which was contradictory to that inner morality no matter the organisational demands around performance. Not surprisingly, in this perspective there is less need for statistical forecasting to be leaderly in midwifery. There need only exist the ability to demonstrate credible knowledge and abilities, which offer beyond doubt to followers, a sense of influence toward better things for childbearing women. When Foucault spoke of La Perrière's work as "*government is the right disposition of things, arranged so as to lead to a convenient end*" (Bruchell, Gordon & Miller, 1991, p.101), it is likely these would be the professionalised leadership things.

5.2 Raison d'état ('reason of state')

Here the term reason could be seen as reasoning of state or rationality of state. It's subtle difference from political sovereignty is however intertwined within it in public sector healthcare. It can be seen as placing primacy on the apparatus of the NHS or directing toward maternity and midwifery as an institution. In doing so, all of the measurements and data, and performance of the institution come to be seen as requiring leadership. The aim is therefore not simply to reinforce a ruler, such as in sovereignty, but to reinforce the position of the institution itself. This form of Foucault's governmentality requires knowledge about maternity and midwifery. In midwifery terms this would see a focus away from reinforcing the position of the wisdom, experience, and expertise of the midwife leader toward ways and means which could best serve the collective state, e.g., using tangible and measurable data points could allow predictability, order and therefore security of and for the state with respect to maternity services. Some of the discourse discontinuities or perturbation can be useful points with which to view and critique and in doing so problematise the relationship between maternity care, reason of state, and the role of government as political sovereign.

5.2.1 *Voices within the discourse*

What is shown here are examples of the power/knowledge role in discourse but also in the positions which key actors within it hold. As Arribas-Ayllon & Walkerdine (2017) illustrates the discourse can be seen as an institutionalised and regulated exercising of power, of ways of thinking, talking, and acting. It offers critical insights into how the responses gathered from the actors reflect their own governmental rationality and the discursive factors that create these possibilities.

Sir Bill Kirkup offered specific findings in his first investigation of poor maternity care at Morecambe Bay, interpreted as critical toward 'normal births' (Kirkup, 2015). Likewise, Ockenden had repeated those claims about normal births in her interim investigation report on Shrewsbury (Ockenden, 2020). In December 2020, Jeremy Hunt MP, former Secretary of State for Health and Social Care, in his capacity as chair of the Health and Social Care Committee summoned the then Minister of State for Patient Safety, Suicide Prevention and Mental Health, Nadine Dorris. Mr Hunt asked, "*Does the minister not agree that it is time to stamp out the normal birth ideology...*". (Lintern, 2020). That Ms Dorris was in a ministerial position titled around safety is indicative of the primacy of such an issue for government. However, it is also valuable in Foucault's ideas around problematising and questioning socio-political knowledge trends not just for continuity, but for perturbations in such things, when he explains his desire to show '*displacements and transformations of concepts*' (Foucault, 1972, p.4). The theme of normal birth is a core part, not only of midwifery professional identity, but arguably in that of women in not being seen as patients. The power/knowledge dynamic here is evident from Sir Bill Kirkup, appointed by government, who uses a phrase in his inspection which is transformed into a form of toxic symbolism in the space of governing maternity services. The legitimisation which the power/knowledge dynamic gains from its proximity to the political sovereign establishes *normal birth* as a target for recalibration and adjustment.

James Titcombe lost his newly born son in 2008 which was one of the cases in Sir Kirkup's first investigation (Kirkup, 2015). He became a prominent campaigner for maternity safety and was appointed to the Care Quality Commission (CQC) from October 2013 to March 2016, as the National Advisor on Patient Safety, Culture & Quality. He was awarded an OBE in 2015 for

his contribution to patient safety and now works for Baby Lifeline and is a member of the Expert Advisory Panel for the Parliamentary and Health Service Ombudsman. He is held in some stature by the UK Government. His leadership status in maternity safety however arose after Mr Titcombe's determination to challenge the role of the midwifery regulator, the NMC, surrounding the events of his son's death. In 2018, the UK regulator of regulators, the Professional Standards Authority (PSA), published their Lessons Learned Review (PSA, 2018). The report was critical of the NMC's handling of the Morecambe Bay NHS Foundation Trust, finding several failings and highlighting Mr Titcombe's case in particular. The NMC ordered an investigation into their own role in the handling of Mr Titcombe's case by an independent private firm (Seale & Killwick, 2019). With a governmental lens, Mr Titcombe publicly challenged the sovereign position of the midwifery regulator, but by doing so challenged the midwifery profession and not state maternity care. His challenge may arguably have been directed at government who are accountable for maternity care, however government embraced Mr Titcombe, employed him at the CQC, making him an employee of the same state with whom he may have had grievance. He was awarded an OBE by the sovereign state for his maternity safety contributions. He was also present at the previously noted Health Committee where Ms Ockenden's interim report was presented and noted *"It's crucial that we do not make the mistake of assuming that what happened at Shrewsbury and Telford is another 'one-off'"*. (Lintern, 2020). The inference here being a rationality pursuant of much deeper investigations into the discourse of maternity care. Gill Walton, CEO of the Royal College of Midwives gave her statement as the professional body representing the interests of midwives. *"We fully support the review's recommendation that any externally allocated training funds which have been earmarked for maternity services must be ring-fenced for their intended purpose"*. (Lintern, 2022). Without over-playing the role of interpretation in deriving deep meaning, it could be inferred that previously allocated resources for training have not been deployed correctly. Like Mr Titcombe, Professor Baker the Chief Inspector for Hospital at the CQC seemed keen to pursue scrutiny and performance improvements, *"The continued national focus on the safety of maternity services is welcome and we are seeing some positive change. However, the progress made does not yet meet the scale of the challenge"* (Lintern, 2022).

5.2.2 Leadership or accountability.

The methodology employed by Ockenden (2020; 2022) has no need to embrace credible rigour to enter the discourse archive. The epistemic arbiter of the state overrules the agency of a randomised control trial as a power-knowledge relationship. Some of the recommendations from a governmentality perspective, are interesting and their apparent rationality and technologies. Improving safety by working collaboratively across NHS Trusts as rationality this is difficult to challenge. As a technology however, it is to be achieved by gathering data around 'serious incidents' via a reporting dashboard at least every three months to allow scrutiny at Board level (Ockenden, 2020). However, the views of leadership in the 2022 final report are a useful illustrator of the expansive context of leader people, leader hierarchy and organisational management, with one respondent quoted, *"When things go well, it is down to good leadership and when they don't, who takes responsibility? Does it rest with the 'senior' midwife, the trust's chief executive, the board or the midwife delivering the care?"* (p.57). It positions leader titles as obstetric lead, clinical director, and director of midwifery as responsible *"for daily operational delivery and strategic management"* and this responsibility from delivery to strategy is *'accountable to the trust board for quality, performance, governance and professional leadership'*. The investigation notes that these things were not always met at the trust. From a sceptical position, and applying a problematising approach, since these responsibilities seem to cover every possible eventuality in a maternity service and yet are responsibilised to three people, Ms Ockenden's methods of enquiry seem less focussed on causality than 'accusality'. In the leadership section of the report, which spans 12 pages leadership is entangled in workforce-based terminology and focussed on what is arguably poor management practice aligned to a leadership vocabulary. It does note stark examples of this which from a governmental perspective show signs of discursive clash between contracted employment and direction and influence, but also that policy plays a governmental role.

"...managed with a big...stick from behind, there was no forward-thinking leadership. We had changes in policy imposed on us, we did not contribute to changes. We were bullied, everything was done under the guise of 'clinical need' or 'your contract says.'"

(Ockenden, 2022, p. 67)

In terms of Foucault's parrhesia, the voices within the wider discourse are perhaps limited in where their truths can be targeted (Dyrberg, 2015); one midwife noted, *"It's very hard to speak up because despite what anybody will tell you, there are consequences to speaking up and the consequences are your life gets made very difficult"* (p.67). However, leadership as a form of behaviour adjustment mechanism is implied, noting tools which can be used and with which leaders are encouraged to address negative culture in the workplace, such as the Workplace Behaviour Toolkit (RCOG, 2021) and Civility Toolkit (HEE, 2021). Again, problematising such things leads to perplexity when subjects within a discourse are feeling unsafe and threatened, and the recommendations from a 5-year investigation by government offering ways in which leaders can make subjects less negative about these feelings. However, from a governmental perspective, a valuable insight is offered of the role and practice, or direction and influence as conflated with the authoritative managerial task, when pointing out the pivotal role of a midwifery matron. This role is noted in leading by example, including *"promoting professionalism in the workplace"*, but also, *"It is widely acknowledged that midwifery matron roles also encompass workforce management, budgetary responsibilities and effective resourcing of equipment and maintenance of estates"* (Ockendon, 2022, p.62). It is possible to be sceptical about which aspect of this would hold primacy in the mind of the midwife in such a role, midwifery professionalism, workplace professionalism, or administrative management.

With a sceptical lens on *raison d'état* the state has launched another investigation into themselves around maternity care, but with a tactic of implied validity based on an independence from itself (whilst commissioned and paid for by itself). Donna Ockenden is not Queens Council; she is a private sector commercial entity under contract. Her review is not 'independent' in terms of The Enquiries Act, 2005 (UK Parliament). Less than two months after the Ockenden Interim Report (2020) was published, Patient Safety Minister, Nadine Dorries, announced a £500,000 fund for 'innovative NHS maternity leadership training' (UK Government, 2021). Perhaps the appointment of a Minister for Patient Safety is a governmental tactic in itself, representing the perceived seriousness of the state in protecting its citizens. However, this is also reminiscent of 'the need to be seen to be' in terms of response by government. And a useful way of adding weight to that is a £500,000 training

fund in response to the interim report. This could arguably be a form of performative activism or optical allyship with the intended goal of 'being on the right side of history' (Kalina, 2020).

In April 2020, an investigation by Sir Bill Kirkup, previously an investigator at Morecambe Bay (Kirkup,2015), found that East Kent Trust implemented only 2 of the 23 recommendations to maternity care made by a Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologist report (Kirkup, 2020, RCOG, 2016). However, a certain momentum from the media now exists with respect to maternity care. In 2021 Channel 4 News and The Independent Newspaper reported on alleged maternity failings in Nottingham University NHS Trust, perhaps inspired by the publication of a CQC report around the Trust's maternity service as 'requiring to improve' in 'safety and leadership' (CQC, 2021). And, after the announcement of another independent enquiry, midwives made public their own concerns about the conduct of conduct. Taking the opportunity to respond to the media investigators, midwives spoke of inadequate staffing and a culture of fear and anxiety. One midwife noting, *"I come home crying every day, saying 'What the hell have I done?' I have put myself through financial hardship for three years and I've gone into a career where, every day, I feel like I'm going into chaos"*. (Lintern, 2021). One midwife claimed, *"They keep saying 'We've learned our lessons, it's not like that now' – but it's even worse now. It's worse because we know about it and it's still bad. Women are still at risk of harm"* (Lintern, 2021). With vacancies in that Trust of 70 midwives, the investigation claims one newly qualified community midwife was given the entire geographical area of Nottingham to cover on her own. As part of this thesis research, I submitted a Freedom of Information Request to the Department of Health & Social Care in October 2021 to establish the sums of public money which Ms Ockenden's company was paid for her interim and final report into Shrewsbury and Telford NHS Trust in April 2022. The Department, while conforming they did hold this information, rejected my request under Section 35(1)(a) which provides protection for information that relates to the formulation or development of government policy. (Appendix 6). Whilst avoiding conspiratorial hyperbole it is a fair representation of the primacy of the reason of state versus the request from a citizen of that state which questions the governmental technologies of that state.

5.3 Police

In his governmentality lecture in 1978, Foucault again used examples from La Perrière's who analogises the bumble bee that he claims governs his hive without need for a sting, Foucault notes, "...he must have *patience rather than wrath*" and require "*wisdom and diligence*" (Burchell, Gordon & Miller, 1991, p.104). Only in this sense wisdom concerns "*...the knowledge of things, of the objects than can and should be attained and the disposition of things required to reach them; it is this knowledge that is to constitute the wisdom of the sovereign*" (p.104). In order then to understand how to govern better, this form of governmentality requires information, as much as possible, about all the 'things' which are to be governed. And Foucault states, "I do not think one can fail to relate this search for an art of government to mercantilism and the Cameralists' science of police" (ibid, p.104). Applying a governmentality of police from which to further problematise midwifery leadership requires clarity that Foucault means the 17th century interpretation of police, including policy (an etymological antecedent to 'police').

5.3.1 Regulatory reach

By police governmentality, Foucault implies an even more systematic and meticulous administration of citizens and the way in which the collective action of government of those citizens can in turn maximise the state. The ideal police state adopts a deterministic approach by knowing limitless details about the individuals within it and maximises this toward the benefit of the state mission. This view of governmentality, in midwifery leadership terms, would drive direction and influence toward being able to interpret and assess midwives as detailed parts of the maternity collective, their individual knowledge, abilities, and behaviours, known ideally even at a biological level. In extremis, but to illustrate the concept, with the target of maximum safety in maternity, the ideal police governmentality would identify at an intrinsic level those midwives likely to cause harm. Their fitness or otherwise could be determined and predicted based on government goals.

Figure 3

The diagram in figure 3 summarises from the documentary analysis, systemic reach of the governmental police agency (in Foucauldian terms) of the professional regulator the Nursing Midwifery Council. The governmental technologies of how midwives are trained and educated (incubation) and their need for ongoing licence have been noted previously, particularly with respect the need to comply with forms of standardised caveats in that licencing. By *Eradication* is meant the mechanisms of expulsion from the discourse of professional midwifery. Foucault's panopticism reaches even into midwives' use of social media e.g., the NMC Guidance on using social media responsibly applies to "all kinds of online communication, such as personal websites and blogs, discussion boards and general content shared online, including text, photographs, images, video and audio files". (NMC, 2020, p2.) However, this also applies to students, "Nurses, midwives and nursing associates may put their registration at risk, and students may jeopardise their ability to join our register, if they act in any way that is unprofessional or unlawful on social media". (Ibid, p3). The Professional Duty of Candour demands that a midwife be open when mistakes are made by them or seen

to be made by others. The approach to determination by the state (in this case via the NHS employer) of which midwives should and should not practice, is enhanced by the contents of *Managing Concerns* (NMC, 2021). By *casuistry* is meant the ethical approach adopted in formal Fitness to Practice (FTP) hearings as a form of ‘case-based reasoning’. For example, FTP cases are presented, and comparisons made with other similar cases to assist in exclusionary judgments. Casuistry is a standard form of reasoning in common law and a branch of bioethics (Paulo, 2015; Bleyer, 2020). Cases in the discourse are an archive of FTP historical record of disciplinary recalibrations (or eradications) against midwives now and in the future. As a police governmentality, direction and influence are focussed on creating compliant midwives, assuming the knowledge about the governed is accurate and deterministically predictable.

5.3.2 Policy and strategy

Policy direction and influence is shown here under police governmentality, as it is a formalised attempt to marshal the activity of midwifery and maternity by endorsing direction of travel and metricising measures of success and performance. It also hopes to further highlight the possible impact of perturbative events. Two main policy threads of determining the actions of future midwifery practice lie in the English and Scottish directives, *Better Births: Improving outcomes of maternity services in England* (NHS England, 2016) and *The Best Start: A Five-Year Forward Plan for Maternity and Neonatal Care in Scotland* (Scottish Government, 2017). Both contain a similar element of idealised midwifery practice of based on evidential knowledge in directing and influencing toward improvement in maternity care, echoing the work of Mary Renfrew’s Lancet Series and midwifery-led models of ‘continuity of care’ (CoC). However, *Better Births* is explicit about its alignment to tragic events in Morecambe Bay and the subsequent recommendations of the Kirkup Report (2015). In England, this direction and influence was to be driven by The National Maternity Transformation Programme to deliver the ambition to halve the rates of stillbirths, neonatal mortality, maternal mortality and brain injury by 2025 (NHS England & NHS Improvement, 2020). This quantitative aspiration to reduce ‘bad outcomes’ was legitimised by its inclusion in The NHS Long-term Plan (2019). In Scotland, the direction and influence of *Best Start* claims to originate from the Strategic Review of Maternity and Neonatal Services in Scotland in 2015 and is legitimised within the Scottish Government’s Transformational Change planning. The Scottish Government claims

Best Start was influenced by the judgement in *Montgomery v Lanarkshire* case of March 2015 (Chan et al, 2017). As well as highlighting casuistry, this works as example of the debate around patient autonomy versus medical paternalism (Farrel & Brazier, 2016). What is also apparent is a subtle shift from the normally accepted information-asymmetry which exists in most healthcare environments, i.e., when professionals on the supply-side of the economic exchange know more about the demand-side than the patients do themselves, a feature of healthcare economics detailed since the 1960's (Arrow, 2003). It illustrates potentially a shift in mentality from patients *in* health care toward consumers *of* health care.

5.3.3 Governmental shifts in regulation

The mentality of influencing the conduct of conduct toward eradicating mistakes and mistake-makers can be seen in the discontinuities in governmental regulatory approaches in the discourse of midwifery. In doing so, it will highlight a desire of government power/knowledge but also the underlying rationality of government in 'a need to be seen to be' as well as an adjustment in the scope of professional distinctiveness in midwifery bases on redressing trust between government and the political state. Instigated by the failures noted by Francis (2013) was the review *Regulation of Social Care Professionals in England* (2015). The review can be viewed as a response to public confidence response from government to Sir Roberts findings.

"[Government] seeks to drive up public safety, professional standards and public confidence by proposing that regulatory bodies and the Professional Standards Authority have public protection as their over-arching objective" (p. 7).

At the time of this 2015 review of regulation, Kirkup's 2015 Independent Maternity Report was not yet published. However, the then Secretary of State, Jeremy Hunt, determined that legislation regarding the way midwives were regulated would change, to bring midwifery closer to the regulator (NMC). This was apparently instigated by a request from the NMC themselves in the same month that the *Regulation of Social Care Professionals in England* (2015) was published. Statutory Supervision in midwifery, considered as a form of *self-regulation* was placed under review. However, the Parliamentary Ombudsman (PHSO) justified this using three cases outlined in Kirkup's investigations in their Report (PHSO, 2013), which oddly was published prior to Sir Bill Kirkup's in 2015. The Ombudsman determined

these unanswered questions in Kirkup's ongoing investigations at the time were sufficient *evidence* of a consistent theme for the three families affected in the Morecambe Bay NHS Foundation Trust and as such legislation needed to change because,

"...the failure to learn from poor midwifery care, which could have resulted in future service users being put at unnecessary risk". (PHSO, 2013, p.5).

The Ombudsman, accountable to Parliament, but who are emphatic about their independence from government, concluded *'that midwifery supervision and regulation should be separated'* and *'that the NMC should be in direct control of regulatory activity'*. (PHSO, 2013, p.2). The removal of midwifery supervision began when the Kings Fund were commissioned by the NMC to review midwifery regulation following the incidents at Morecambe Bay. And the governmental rationality was evident in line one, page one of the report which began, *"Midwifery regulation is based on a model established in 1902 and the principles have remained essentially unchanged since that time"*. (Kings Fund, 2015, p.1). The newly formed regulator of regulators, the Professional Standards Authority is also cited in the Kings Fund report of 2015 as offering a more specific context for the need for change,

"...the imposition of regulatory sanctions or prohibitions by one midwife on another without lay scrutiny is counter to principles of good regulation in the post-Shipman era". (Kings Fund, 2015, p3)

The governmental momentum can also be seen in the state legal apparatus required to change legislation (Law Commission, 2014). However, the alteration of legislation meant amending the obligations around the *Nursing & Midwifery Order 2001* and the additional powers granted the NMC specific to midwifery under *Midwives Rules and Standards 2012* (NMC, 2012). And as the Kings Fund (2015) point out, these standards can be amended by the NMC but *only* after consultation (p. 4). However, the proposals consulted upon in April 2016, to remove midwifery supervision, were rejected by 84% of midwifery respondents. Moreover, the proposal at the time to also remove the statutory *Midwifery Committee* at the NMC was also rejected at consultation by 91% of midwifery respondents. Neither objection impacted on the governmental position and both proposals were carried out in 2017 (Merrifield, 2017).

The dominant political discourse rejects the legitimacy of professional midwifery in an arguably acrimonious, paternalistic slight. This was also despite the explicit plea from the then CEO of the Royal College of Midwives Cathy Warwick (Merrifield, 2016). Having been a coherent part of professionalism in midwifery, for some time it was to be replaced by forms of 'clinical supervision' which would still support midwifery practice, but which would be the responsibility of a midwife's employer, the NHS, i.e., the state. The legislative changes which validated this move (and Amendment to the Midwifery Order of 2001) also removed what was known as *post-registration education and practice* (PrEP) requirements which ended on 31 March 2016. Midwives would now undergo triennial revalidation in the same way as nurses and healthcare assistants overseen by the NMC. It is clear that whilst claiming some form of fair due process that, that even from a perspective of timelines the UK government, to whom the NMC are accountable, determined on 3 cases of poor care that an entire profession would have its discretionary space for decision-making curtailed by legal-rational authority.

5.4 Neoliberalism

Neoliberalism was not part of Foucault's lecture series where the rationalities and arts of governing were shared. However, he does highlight that economy was a form of government in the 16th century but that since the 18th has come to "*designate a level of reality, a field of intervention*". (Burchell, Gordon & Miller, 1991, p.101). However, it is shown here as a form of political rationality of governing in terms of establishing a landscape upon which midwifery leadership has to operate. It will allow the governmental rationality of the benefits of free-market ideology to be seen as operationalised and normalised as discursive forces through policy.

According to Venugopal (2014, p,165), "*Neoliberalism is everywhere, but at the same time, nowhere*". However, pertinent to public sector midwifery, is Harvey's (2005) assertion that where markets are not obvious modalities in a given state apparatus, such as in education or health care, a neoliberal position would demand that the state should create these conditions. Likewise, Ball (2013) notes, "*The state constructs the conditions of possibility for the economy as a 'concrete and real space in which the formal structure of competition could function'*" (Ball, 2013; Foucault, 2004, p. 132). Furthermore, Cole (2008, p.88) outlines five defining characteristics of neoliberalism as:

“A belief in the centrality of the market, a desire for reduced government (spending), privatisation of state ownership, reduction on regulation and controls, and a focus on the individual, as opposed to community or society, particularly in relation to responsibility”

According to Lazzarato (2009) this form of neoliberal economy is one which consists of a machinery of ‘regulated activities’ which is frequently re-reordered, modified and reinstated by the state. What is shown now is a critique of policy from a neoliberal governmental perspective. In particular where such governmentalities value arguably monetised aspects of healthcare. The failures at Mid Staffordshire Foundation Trust found an institutional culture that placed the *business of the system ahead of patient*’. Furthermore, Francis identified a pervasive culture of fear in the NHS and certain elements of the Department for Health, noting a widespread culture more of fear and compliance, than of learning and improvement (Francis, 2013). Moreover, he determined that

“...there lurks within the system an institutional instinct which, under pressure, will prefer concealment, formulaic responses, and avoidance of public criticism’ and ‘an institutional culture which ascribed more weight to positive information about the service than to information capable of implying cause for concern” (Francis, 2013 p4).

And whilst Morecambe Bay and Kirkup’s report do focus entirely on midwifery both of these events have something else in common, as with the failings in Kirkup (2022) in Nottingham: that of *Foundation Trust Status*. They have an illuminating effect in considering neoliberal rationalities of government in the public sector and are therefore examined briefly. Established by Secretary of State Alan Milburn in 2002, Foundation Trusts (FT) were seen as a new type of semi-autonomous NHS Trust (the geographical legal body which ran each sub-unit of health care in England). These FTs would be financially autonomous and operate in such a way as to be able to generate surplus income. Key to their role in the argument of governmentality is that FT status removed them from the central supervision of their Strategic Health Authority (although this was revoked after the Francis Enquiry in 2013). They were designed to be, in the words of Butler and Parker, (2002)

“...a sort of half-way house between public and private sectors [that will be] more efficient, dynamic and more patient responsive. Foundation status - which will give trust managers more freedom over local decision making, will in theory unleash local innovation and entrepreneurial spirit while remaining within the NHS "family" and true to the public service ethos”.

Carter and Kline (2017, p.217) note the intense pressure felt by health care leaders to emphasise a focus on fiscal prudence and fear of blame, all against a backdrop of high senior leader turnover. They note the Mid Staffordshire Trust’s Board agreement in January 2005 to cull 180 clinical posts because the Trust had a statutory requirement to break even at the end of the financial year yet when they examined the Trust Committee’s minutes from 2005-2008 there were no records of how in terms of patient care this would be mitigated. The prevalence of publicised maternity errors involving NHS Foundation Trusts (Morecambe Bay, 2015; East Kent, 2020, Nottingham 2021) is difficult to ignore. Scotland’s political rationality dissolved Trusts in 2004, bringing regional Boards closer to central direction and accountability and removing barriers between local councils and health as authorities. This culminated in direction toward integration of health and care solidified in law under the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014 (Scottish Government, 2014). This no doubt has been in part enabled by continuous party government control since 2007. England has not seen that same political continuity, with the Health & Social Care Act 2012. Broadly speaking, Scottish governmentality has been government-centric, whilst England has adopted a more free-market commissioning approach more fitting of a neoliberal mentality. The Kings Fund, as policy advisors for health care in England, drew many of these same conclusions in their recent review of the current rationalities and technologies of healthcare in Scotland (Kings Fund, 2018). Health legislation in England has recently taken radical shift to free-market rationality. However, in their recent paper, Mason and Araujo (2021), in reviewing the previous Health & Social Care Act 2012, note that from a governmentality perspective the Act was designed to, *“relocate the responsibilities of the Secretary of State to society and the healthcare system”* (p. 479). However, writing in the British Medical Journal, Delamothe and Godlee (2011) claim that NHS leaders and managers of the time were hugely sceptical:

“The scale of ambition [of the Act] should ring alarm bells. Sir David Nicholson, the NHS chief executive, has described the proposals as the biggest change management programme in the world—the only one so large ‘that you can actually see it from space’”
(p.342)

According to Hammond et al (2019) this attempted marketisation of health care in England made relatively simple processes for care delivery to women much more complex, for example, they had an adverse effect on cervical screening rates. The recent English legislative reforms in the Health and Care Act 2022 has points worthy of critique in its ascension to parliament. Its antecedent, *Integration and Innovation: working together to improve health and social care for all*, was published as a White Paper in February 2021 (Kings Fund, 2021). Its political direction *claims* similarity with Scottish legislation in terms of integration. However, on the cusp of the scope of this thesis perhaps, the political technologies inferred from what exists so far mean the Secretary of State gaining powers to significantly intervene in health care. Therefore, whilst responsibility for delivery and accountability is pushed far from government toward clinical staff, government reserve to right to alter this at will. The Health and Care Act 2022 claims to reduce bureaucracy as a rationality and by means of associated technology of removing regulatory roles of the Competitions and Markets Authority and The Public and Contracts Regulations 2015 and setting these powers within NHS Improvement. This means that elements within the wider discourse of state healthcare intended to protect a public sector ideology are ‘deregulated’, whilst midwifery for example is being ‘re-regulated’ at the level of the individual. The Secretary of State also gains new powers to create their own NHS Trusts should they desire as well as removing the nationally agreed fee tariff systems. Localised training and education boards will be removed from statute and be centralised with NHS England (Kings Fund, 2021). For a rationality focussed on local integration of services there are a number of soft and hard governing roles which seem to be moving toward central government control. The Kings Fund note the Act will formally consolidate the roles of NHS England and NHS Improvement, aimed at strengthening ministerial control over national bodies and service reconfigurations. This new single body will now be formally considered to be responsible for providing unified, national leadership for the NHS. However, part of the Act also creates powers for the Secretary of State to transfer functions ‘*from specified arm’s length bodies and to abolish arm’s length bodies where they*

become redundant as a result of any such transfers' (Kings Fund, 2021). Whilst the limits to this are not clear, this allows government to control or dissolve bodies such as The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), who are the clinical and economic evidence generators for health care in England. Problematizing this in the widest sense shows evidential knowledge as being deprioritised and the prioritising of the knowledge/power primacy of government. Equally, the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) that regulates medications and medical devices could meet the same outcome (McKenna, 2021). Moreover, under the pillar of Additional Measures, the Secretary of State would reserve the right to make payments to *any* provider of health and social care, not just the current statutory position of not-for-profit organisations. A sceptical position would at least consider the notion of a legislative doorway for political privatisation and marketisation of health care which is an acceleration of the rationality of the 2012 Act. Such a governmental shift in rationality and technologies would alter the midwifery professional dynamic with women as one of consumers of healthcare. It would also place public healthcare in a competition environment. As such, governments could offer a menu of costed options for women as healthcare consumers versus one of best clinical evidence and the primacy of the space for professional discretion.

5.5 Governmentality and the self

Foucault in his later studies became interested in 'arts of the self' in Greco-Roman culture, and following Nietzsche, became for Foucault an 'aesthetics of existence'. (Peters, 2006). He saw this is sets of inventive and experimental techniques by which an individual's transform themselves into work of art. *"The idea of a morality as obedience to a code of rules is now disappearing...and to this absence of morality corresponds, must correspond, a search for the aesthetics of existence"* (Foucault & Rainbow, 1984, p 343). The way in which subjects shape themselves in particular forms with relation to the discourse of leadership in midwifery are captured in Foucault's concept of *technologies of the self*. Foucault spoke of technologies of the self in his lectures at the University of Vermont in 1982 (Foucault, 1988). He notes in is interview with Rainbow, *"the kind of relationship you ought to have with yourself, rapport a soi, which I call ethics"* (Foucault & Rainbow, 1984, p.352) And this relationship with the self, is outlined in relation to the discourse of midwifery leadership in order: *ethical substance, mode of subjection, self-forming activity, and telos*. Again, like the forms of governmentality

outlined in previous sections of this chapter, this does not imply these should be viewed separately. Rather they are elements of a single concept of self-governance which should be viewed as being of varying concentrations. This is valuable in problematising the ethical and moral coding in professional groups, versus the dynamic of power/knowledge shown so far.

5.5.1 *Ethical substance*

This first aspect of Foucault's ethics relates to the part of the individual which acts as the focus of moral conduct. Viewed in this way situates midwives as autonomous professionals as being *encouraged* to accept their leadership behaviours as a form of ethical activity. In a discourse littered with leader terminology and present in investigation reports implicating leadership in failures, practice expectations of better leadership is presented as an almost logical requirement. This becomes almost a regime of truths whereby the autonomous professional would be pressed to forget the need to adopt leaderly things. This can then be seen as penetrating the 'everyday' in the workplace, through to the tangible reach and impact of the practice Code (NMC, 2018). However, if say an employment leadership demand contradicted the intrinsic ethics of midwifery professionalism and its core values, this would be problematic. However, as Winch (2005) claims, this is self-formation and rooted in acts around a dynamical relationship between discursive reality and the moral self. The ideal for an employer which required fewer or no errors in maternity would see the ideology of the job requirements become the internalised ethical substance of the subject. And the governmentality of leadership therefore calls for individual professionals to position themselves as the subject of their own leadership actions.

5.5.2 *Mode of subjection*

In the past, subjects would apply ethical judgment against theistic tomes such as the Bible. Ethical perspectives would be clarified, and subjects' actions rectified, based on the moral vector of prophetic texts. In the same way as rebellion against these teachings would confer expulsion from the congregation, so then rebellion against the midwifery regulator is positioned here. The midwifery regulator then is placed as an arbiter of ethical practice by subjectifying the midwives within their reach. The role of the NMC touches across almost every aspect of midwifery existence (see Figure 4). After implanting techniques of adjustment to standards of expectations shown earlier, the ethical *mode of subjection* that binds all of

these is the Code (NMC, 2018). To exist within the discourse of professional midwifery, requires midwives and universities to uphold these elements. There are 108 individual components in the Code, pre-empted in text by, 'To achieve this you must' and there are 25 standards. In relation to leadership specifically for example number 25 states, *"Provide leadership to make sure people's wellbeing is protected and to improve their experiences of the health and care system"* which illustrates a compliance imperative to reduce harm and improve service seen already in this thesis. Compliance and internal recalibration are replicated hierarchically in those with authority to do so, *"25.2 support any staff you may be responsible for to follow the Code at all times"* (NMC, 2018, p.22). The code also ingrains and normalises the moral authority of the regulator and the ethical duty toward the exposure of deviance in terms of registrant candour even if one longer wished to identify as a midwife.

"This includes investigations or audits either against you or relating to others, whether individuals or organisations. It also includes cooperating with requests to act as a witness in any hearing that forms part of an investigation, even after you have left the register" (NMC, 2018, p.20).

This mode of Foucault's ethics acts from and upon a position of internalised panopticism. From a leadership perspective the Code represents a moral benchmark not only for midwifery leaders but for everyone within the discourse of midwifery. However, it is also a lever which leaders can adopt as a tactic of influence. There is little scope to ignore the subtle authoritarian flavour of this mode of subjection when it notes that the Code applies to midwives, *"...whether they are providing direct care to individuals, groups or communities or bringing their professional knowledge to bear on nursing and midwifery practice in other roles, such as leadership, education, or research. The values and principles set out in the Code can be applied in a range of different practice settings, but they are not negotiable or discretionary"* (NMC, 2018, p.3). An employer which required maternity services to be directed and influenced toward no errors, would see the Code as an ideal mode of ethical subjection. If that were then synergised with the regulatory elements of registration and professionalism, that would be a valuable form of 'conduct of conduct' in identifying deviance from agreed norms.

5.5.3 *Self-forming activity*

This part of Foucauldian ethics is concerned with the types and forms of activities practised upon the self to achieve a desired ethical position. This refers firstly to the way in which the midwifery leader views themselves with respect to a desired ethical standard, but clearly relates to an externalised impression of what is expected by the discursive reality. And many of the ways in which this would be achieved have been heightened in terms of qualifications and gateways in leadership development. But also included are 'softer' activities such as the way in which leaders present to the discourse in terms of clothing, language, and attendance at public events such as those noted earlier in national maternity safety. A closeness to activities where decisions are being made regarding future states for midwifery for example would require being informed about executive terminology and presenting oneself in these fora in a certain way. As Nietzsche and Haase (2010) point out, these forms of elaboration can involve a range of acts of mental and physical self-discipline in order to achieve an ethical position. In the same way as governments arguably 'need to be seen to be', so too do midwifery leaders 'need to be seen to be' adopting leaderly opportunities, i.e., to show they are active participants in discursively normalised need for leading.

5.5.4 *Telos*

In *The History of Sexuality, Volume 2*, Foucault defines this mode of ethics as, "...an action that is not only moral in itself, in its singularity; it is also moral in its circumstantial integration and by virtue of the place it occupies in a pattern of conduct" (Foucault, 1992, pp. 27–28, cited in Nietzsche and Haase, 2010). However, this can be simplified by noting that this refers to a subject identifying a personal imagery of the sort of being they aspire to become. Clearly however this ideal is drawn within a given discursive formation and therefore linked closely to the three other aspects of Foucauldian ethics noted already. This becomes enlightening in midwifery leadership when considering the governmental rationality of the pastoral alongside that of reason of state, particularly in a dynamic of political sovereignty. Where conflict may exist between a professional identity and the demands of an employer were felt as dominant i.e., a dissonance would develop between *professionalism* versus *employerism*. For example, a midwifery leader who aspired to be valued by other midwives would likely engage in self-forming acts which related to professional identity, historical context, and intrinsic midwifery

values, and in implementing formal evidence-based midwifery practice. The core beliefs of the profession would likely reflect internally and externally in this sense. This form of telos would be driven by respect and credibility from other midwives, a form of prestige leadership perhaps. However, a midwifery leader who wished to derive positional credibility from the apparatus of planning and administration in an employment environment, would more likely self-form toward points of valorisation external or parallel to that of midwifery. *Professionalism* in midwifery arguably looks inwards toward childbearing women, whereas *employerism* gazes outward toward the dominant performative discourse apparatus. The reality of course is that these two tramlines are rarely separate and midwifery leaders who selected one at the exclusion of the other would most likely succeed at neither. However, in accepting an arguable duality of forces between professionalism and employerism, the question could be asked of whether effective midwifery leadership has a genuineness rooted in ethical practice at all. In so much as leaders must, where these forces don't naturally align, face a challenge of adjusting their own moral and ethical positions to contractual obligation. This conflict presumably would not be 'healthy' for the leader or for their followers. In the sense that leaders only exist if they have followers, to adopt a capriciously amoral position to getting future better things done would be short-lived and self-defeating and therefore not leaderly at all. Despite the obvious almost clichéd conflation between leadership and management, if a key tenet of leadership activity is to '*Demonstrate strong ethics and provide a sense of safety*', as Giles (2016) claims, then the selection by employers of which type of midwives should fill leaderships roles would be challenging: selecting those who can get things done, versus those who do the right thing. Accordingly, Everard et al (2004, p.122) notes the superficiality of drawing on leadership approaches which can be deployed whenever they are situationally prudent.

"If we are to manage our relationships...the important skill is to be able to suit our behaviour to circumstances, and individual. This calls for 'situational sensitivity' and 'style flexibility'".

If midwifery leadership is to be viewed via a Foucauldian ethical lens, a third tramline can be asserted: professionalism, employerism and *leaderism*. To expect that a professional should be asked to adopt an act which ignores (or replaces) the ethical elements noted by Foucault

is morally vacuous. Any leadership quest, normalised by one part of the discourse, required to replace the professional morality in another part of that discourse, would be highly incongruous. This would reduce the leadership task to a list of tools and strategies, in which midwifery leaders need hold little or no professional values at all and need only defer to the catalogue of tactics branded justifiable as leadership, management and administration. In this way leaderism simply becomes an entrepreneurial evolution of ideological managerialism seen since the 90's. Accordingly, Orielly & Reid (2010) leaderism is a hybridisation of New Public Management and UK public sector governance approaches emerging from drives to reimagine and reform the public sector.

Summary

This chapter illustrates a dissonance in modes of governmentality whereby the pastoral can be seen to align with the concept of professionalism, and police as a more realistic analysis of conditions in maternity services. And when considered alongside the power/knowledge critique in chapter 4 this establishes a source of potential governmental friction. And this is evident at the level of the ethical subject which in a pastoral governmentality would see leadership amongst the realms of the servant theoretical position, and where the police would sit within the transactions theories. In showing the neoliberal context of wider political policy we can see a momentum for certain governmental technologies to direct and influence the concept of professionals as economic providers of service and women as consumers. Equally the previously noted reach of the professional regulator is an ideal political technology with which to operationalise a governmental rationality of reduced errors or a need to be seen to be addressing them as a form of adjustment bureau. However, in governmental terms the shift to police from pastoral would mean the complete quantification of midwifery practice, and the value placed upon that by women. All of these metrics would then ideally need to fit within a matrix of administration, all of which seems to lie some distance from the woman-centric ethical stance of the profession.

Chapter 6. Governmentality in practice

Introduction

This chapter presents the findings from the analysis of participant data using the methods outlined in Chapter 2. It conceptually locates the key emergent themes with the theoretical approach and uses verbatim quotes from participants and uses pseudonym and role titles. The use of these titles adds a useful dimension in critical understanding as it can locate participants in various parts of the midwifery leadership discourse with respect to power/knowledge and governmental perspective.

6.1 Leadership direction and momentum

In considering midwifery leadership from a governmental perspective, it was important to establish both the perception of the location, and trajectory of leadership in the thoughts of participants, and each was asked to offer their instinctual reaction to the prompt of 'who leads midwifery?'. Responses were centred on two broad themes of 'bottom up' i.e., located and driven by women and midwives, and 'top down' in those who identified known centres of authority;

"It's midwives, it's midwives at every level, it's not me! I'm one of the key leaders because of my positional credibility and authority, but leaders are at all grades in midwifery, from Band 5 right up to me. (Clair, Senior Government Advisor),

"Midwifery is led by women. It's led by the needs of women, that's what leads midwifery." (Laura, Senior Government Advisor),

"It's three things, the Royal College, the regulator the NMC, and partnerships with higher education. And the Scottish Government interferes around the edges. Should I have been altruistic, and women focussed, and said 'women'? the reality is that women are a bit passive in all of it" (Viki, Policy & Quality Advisor),

“So you have the Chief Midwife at the NHS Jaki Dunkley Bent and her crew...hmm, you have folk at the NMC...and...its a really interesting question as to...I don't think there is one, (long pause)...gosh I'm just thinking...” (Jane, Consultant Midwife).

Some however were a little more sceptical in terms of location and trajectory;

“It's midwives, but they don't know it, and because they don't understand that they destroy it! They're responsible for it but at the same time they have a narrative going along that's a form of learned helplessness. It's always somebody else's fault. And there's a reason for that, because it's been subsumed with obstetrics and subsumed in nursing, from policy from...from our own history.”

(Maureen, Policy & Quality Advisor),

“Do you want the ‘correct’ answer [draws quotation marks in the air] ...or do you want me to..., service users, women, they create the passion of midwives on the ground, and we evolve as a profession to meet that. But, the reality is the constraints of women leading...we have a lot of services that aren't conducive to that kind of working, we're so restricted from finance and budgetary constraints, even just in numbers of midwives...but as a midwife you like to think that women are still leading the profession”

(Heather, Policy & Quality Advisor).

And one clinical midwife leader was sceptical around the rationality of leadership as being distinct from managing;

“[sigh & long pause] ...as a national thing you mean or...I'm tempted to say I've no idea who leads midwifery, and I don't know that midwifery knows what a leader is or whether leadership gets muddled up with managing everything!”

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead).

6.2 Leadership in practice and in people

Every participant was aware of the existence of the two respective national strategies of midwifery leadership, namely Better Births and Best Start. But in terms of views on practical leadership, midwives who were in clinical practice tended to see the title of leadership as aligned to practices of managing well;

“I’m visible, I’m here em...and I like to do my wee intentional walk round and say ‘Good Morning’ to all the babies and if the families are there I do my introductions and say ‘Hello’ and then I like to nip up to the ward so that I’ve got a handle on, so the staff know I’m here.”

(Fiona, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“Sometimes... sometimes you want to involve the staff and the team to make a collective decision so that it’s not just my decision, it’s our decision but you know sometimes I think no I’m going to make a decision about that. So sometimes as a leader and a manager you just have to say ‘right we are just doing it this way because’...”

(Rebecca, Clinical Midwifery Lead).

Others who were also titled or positioned as leading, but not in managing clinical practice, tended to focus on traits, behaviours, and the creation of followers as a result of those things, which may be seen as more distinct in the leadership-management ideology;

“You need to be credible, you need to be liked [laughs], you need to be authentic, and you need to have some, I guess...feeling of some positional power but that’s the weakest for of leadership to me, so it’s all about influence, credibility and therefore anyone can lead from influence and credibility you don’t need positional power.”

(Clair, Senior Government Advisor),

“Leaders need to be able to share that vision and they need to be able to translate that into what that means in that relationship that every midwife has with women and why they want to change how midwifery care is provided. It’s not just cause that’s a great idea its cause it needs to happen.”

(Laura, Senior Government Advisor).

There were however some challenges in being a leader shared by some, which seemed to highlight linked personal character and behaviours, and some of which were reminiscent of servant leadership;

“I think leadership is an extremely lonely place... because you are the person who will put the grit in the system, the person who will stand up and defend, and advocate”

(Clair, Senior Government Advisor),

“Sometimes my Quality Improvement Adviser shakes in her shoes when I say things sometimes, cause sometimes I like to learn as we go.”

(Fiona, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“Human nature is you need to have leaders that think out the bubble out the box, it’s the future vision, and leadership is the people who have the confidence to stand up and say, the care we’re delivering is not good”.

(Angela, LME)

Some comments seemed related to strategic elements of games or warfare by being aware of wider dynamics of power relations as being potential points of resistance to leading;

“Ok so I think you can challenge them, but I think... but...so some of the key things about leadership and I said it at the [redacted] conference last year is that you have to choose your battles. You have to read the room, and you have to see what’s happening and you have to...for me there is no point in dialogue that only suits a midwifery audience, your dialogue and what you do has to land in a multi professional and multi sector audience otherwise it’s dead in the water, because they’ll just say ‘oh there’s the midwives trying to do x,y and z’.”

(Clair, Senior Government Advisor).

6.3 Obstacles in leadership and leading

Findings suggest that environmental or organisational demands placed on midwifery practice was influenced by perceptions of risks and also resource constraints and that this in turn blurred the distinction in the leadership and management task. Some participants appeared to feel that previous methods of midwifery leadership practice as part of formal supervision may have been more effective in addressing both constraints.

“Midwifery supervision was always seen as something that was the great envy of other professional groups. I’d always seen it as pastoral first but with the intended goal of safety and quality, because without the pastoral you’re policing not supervising”

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor).

However, some wider environmental conditions were identified as possible rationalities in governing maternity services, rather than midwifery as a professional group;

“We’re in a situation of litigation and blame, and society...everyone wants to know who did it, we want a name and we want that person brought out, we do”

(Angela, LME),

“Because the current culture is risk-averse and it’s interventionalist and everybody across the NHS whether in maternity or nursing or general or wherever through realistic medicine.”

(Claire, Senior Government Advisor),

“Well, I think it doesn’t help that we’re target driven, so again that’s very political targets, but in the profession, litigation is absolutely huge and we’re so risk averse. So, if you even look at our c section rates and you know...they’ve just shot through the roof because even medics will not take any risks”.

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Nonetheless there were perceived benefits offered in terms of managing risk as a profession through previous models of midwifery supervision whilst at the same time developing professional practice. In particular the notion that the system which now partially replaces supervision is not as effective when managed by the employing institution;

“Supervision to me was about supporting that role modelling, the face model of a midwife in terms of those kinds of behaviour and what was expected of that midwife, and it doesn’t matter if you disagree with what a woman wants, it’s being able to support her to identify why and how she wants it and to make the right choices for her.”

(Laura, Senior Government Advisor),

“I think it was coming anyway. Its...it's not supervision that we’ve lost. So, what we lost was a sense of autonomy, or centralised attention to supervision, cos now it's in the hands of Trusts”

(Maureen, Policy & Quality Advisor),

“In supervision we had spot checks, documentation audits, we had annual reviews we had the adverse event type review, but there were multiple opportunities to pick up that ‘oh there's something not quite right here’ feeling, but now relying on a reactive system only....its not the same. They're the pinnacle of events, events that happen, but they don't pick up the near misses!”

(Heather, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“What supervision did remember was it grew leaders from within, and maybe the new clinical supervision bits will still grow leaders, but I think it's more likely to grow managers which is different, it's more legislative than professional.”

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Some however were sceptical about the previous model of supervision as being problematic in having a dual role which was essentially one of regulation, viewed perhaps as punitive, alongside a nurturing role. The implication being the possibility of confusion in both elements of that model;

“There was always a problem with supervision with the idea that your supervisor was somehow a professional support but also the regulatory voice”

(Maureen, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“Ok so I’ll start by saying there isn’t a perfect model, so we’re not going to get that, and the price we pay for some issues being escalated is that many others are not swept under the carpet, because that’s what happened with midwifery supervision”

(Angela, LME).

However, the point made by Maureen that the new model of clinical supervision is at the discretion of NHS employers is a shift in professional development from the professional domain to that of contracted activity, and this is not standardised or influenced by the professional regulator. In discussing the appointed clinical supervisory posts, Sharon points out;

“And now the new systems, certainly in England, are tied up with the contract. I heard some interesting figures yesterday where one Trust in England has only one full time advocate, and their paid in that role, and then another Trust has I think they said 14, it seems to be hugely variable”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

6.4 Managing and leading

Participant conversations all contained elements of professional midwifery challenges in managing within the constraints of institutional maternity provision. In particular, when raised in the context of continuity of care, and/or midwifery led care as the interview prompt;

“So the cynical part of me thinks it will all end with money, so if the money isn’t there that type of care won’t go ahead. Or a more...compromised mode of care might go ahead, but then we’ve known for years, from research, that women prefer midwifery care, based in the local community, and we opened a verity of those in the 2000s, , but it proved to be a more expensive module of care and they’ve all been shut down and definitely that was a budgetary underpinning, that caused that shift in model of care cos the model worked well”.

(Angela, LME),

“There’s maybe wee pieces of work and changes that we have been trying to implement in our service but we are told we have got financial constraints and then all of a sudden you send in a big body like Health Improvement Scotland and they say you’ve got X amount of time to ensure these recommendations are actioned”

(Fiona, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“I’m right now trying to implement continuity of care, but in reality, midwives aren’t interested cos there’s so many things that their worried about, and they’re going to the unions. We were due to start it today actually Stuart, it was due to start today, but it was pulled on Wednesday because the Trust is in financial distress and there is huge staff shortages”

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“So I think clinicians only see what’s relevant to them. I don’t think they would all see the same. I think they would see things as led from a management hierarchy, you know at Board level.”

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor).

6.5 Perturbations in the midwifery discourse

Participants were prompted to identify any events which may be associated with the current climate in professional midwifery with respect to leadership. And an emergence of relations of power were able to be recognised, in particular the relationship between the report by Sir Bill Kirkup in 2015 around the events in Morecambe Bay maternity unit and the dynamic between midwifery and its regulatory body the NMC;

“I mean we’ve come from a place where post Morecambe Bay, loss of trust, loss of supervision, a bloody mess, midwifery trying to find it’s way, the rhetoric and reality that I’ve talked about, and the NMC really really under huge pressure to get their act together with regards to midwifery.” (Jane, Consultant Midwife).

Participants were also able to see wider historical context in power relations between professional groups and government;

“I think there was something about bringing the whole standard for nursing across the Board after Francis, because we [midwifery] were always very focussed on our elements of our remit, our responsibilities, and what that meant for us” (Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor).

“A big thing is the Shipman Enquiry, and there were multiple versions, I think it was the 5th by Dame Janet Smith that went into detail about the role of the regulator and certainly called for a more robust regulatory process.” (Helen, Healthcare Regulatory Law).

However, some participants wished to challenge the rationality in the reconstructed regulation process as being inappropriate and even linked this to individual leadership characteristics of the then CEO of the NMC, thereby illustrating the elements of character linked to agentic authority in influencing;

“I blame Jackie Smith, hugely, for a regulator to lobby so as to crush one of the professions that it regulates like that is extraordinary. I mean 94% of the responses to

the consultation wanted to retain supervision, so how did Jackie Smith, I mean how, why did they have to take down midwifery and why did they have to bring it into line with nursing.”

(Jennifer, Professor of Midwifery),

“Jackie Smith was crackers! So I... she worked at the GMC and Jackie Smith was just, she wasn't a lawyer she had no interest in legal process, it was just about service level agreements, you know, timetables, did we prosecute this case within 9 months, yes fine tick, rather than is this a case we should be prosecuting. Some very sinister stuff went on under her time at the NMC.”

(Helen, Healthcare Regulatory Law),

“There would be differences in opinion you know amongst midwives about this. But um and I think there is also some opinion amongst...it was sort of a...it was a sledgehammer to crack a nut, at the end of the day it was only one Trust affected”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

6.5 Governmental effects

Participants were able to perceive a recent governmental shift in midwifery which appear to imply a fearfulness around errors, as well as a level of encouragement in highlighting mistakes through the NHS Professional Duty of Candour. But they also noted apparent modifications in the way they themselves were expected to influence the practice of others;

“I was working in government trying to drive the healthcare agenda. So, I was trying to drive things and I was concerned when they moved me to a model of scrutiny and compliance and again in simple terms, I didn't want to become the police.”

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“We are now being almost procured to provide a service, we’re no longer autonomous in that we’re no longer aimed at what as a profession we trained to do, we are part of an integrated team on the basis of where maternal choice has taken us.”

(Heather, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“Because midwives are being forced into practicing in ways, via the industrialisation, the medicalisation, and the rules and regulations, are being made to work in ways that actually breaks down trust.”

(Jane, Consultant Midwife),

“It's more of that kind of cover your back and legal side of things and that....anxiety then, I think there's more of that nowadays. If I look at something as simple as my documentation from ten years ago it wouldn't look anything like a document now.”

(Rebecca, Clinical Midwifery Lead).

Some participants shared a sense of dominance from prescribed practice in their work and in those whom they influence as leaders. However, this appeared to clash in some sense with the professional values or forms of known professional practice;

“The professional role of a midwife is to be the advocate for women to be the best they can be, to the person giving birth. We are trying to do that within a system that is not set up to do that, it's a system that is well developed to NOT be built on relationships to make the system continue. To put that pressure on midwives and midwifery to be able to practice in that way within a current system that doesn't lend itself to that, it's not possible.”

(Laura, Senior Government Advisor),

“It's about clinician anxiety, we're not able now.. to go with our instinct whereas ten years ago me as a community midwife I could've went with my gut instinct.”

(Rebecca, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“People are so scared to rock the boat, they are so scared to speak up because...they've got a mortgage to pay, and they are frightened to speak up, and that's the sort of,

quite lamentable situation we find ourselves in. And those...midwives who do speak up often then find themselves victimised by the Trust, referred to the NMC under spurious circumstances or are bullied and then leave". (Jane, Consultant Midwife).

"So are we truly in a position of learning and leading from that, because we now have the DoC and saying 'you know we're maybe not getting this right' but at the same time we're frightened of doing that because we have to give people this assurance that we're operating this way and getting everything right."

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Some participants saw the prescribed maternity practice standards and pathways of care as a significantly dominant force however, and which appear to reduce the scope for critical professional thoughts and actions;

"In a very basic level its like two camps, there's the midwives that they just do what they're told, they follow protocols, guidelines, they don't think out of the box, they'd never dare not do what they're told. And then people like me, who get shouted at every day because I try to move the boundaries, and constantly get told that there's protocols and guidelines that do that, and then when I say that the protocols and guidelines aren't evidence-based, they just keep trying to put me back in the box."

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

"People turn out day to day to do a good job, to go back to what brought them into it. The kind of stick around that is rules and regulations, policy compliance...em...I've actually thought about this a lot, I think people succeed sometimes despite thinking too much, in fact sometimes it's a coping strategy to not think."

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Nevertheless, some participants were able to show that challenging and stretching the frontiers of prescribed practice was in itself a form of leadership, but also observed a distinction between leading the midwifery profession within a wider environmental set of demands;

“...so when it comes to codes, pathways whatever if you're asking me ‘should you be pushing the boundaries?’ yes you should. So you can push things and challenge things by professionally articulating and having multi-sector debate and discussion about them in order to affect change would be my view. Some you will win and some you will not.”

(Clair, Senior Government Advisor),

“You have a regulator who’s current with the standard expected of a midwife at the point of registration, interestingly they can’t answer the question when I asked, ‘When do you stop having these skills’ they’d say ‘we will measure against the point of registration to be a midwife, then it becomes under your terms of employment’, but your employment isn’t purely for midwifery. Professional autonomy and advocacy are absolutely essential but we’re working within an employer model so this is where you need leadership that actually supports the policy that will support people to still continue to support women.”

(Laura, Senior Midwifery Advisor),

“We lost supervision because we were apologising for something that actually when you look at it wasn’t about being a midwife! You think about what happened at Morecombe Bay, that wasn’t about being a midwife, that was about a whole host of issues, organisational culture issues, you have to ask why did those midwives, a very small group of midwives have that attitude, where did that come from?”

(Maureen, Quality & Policy Advisor).

6.6 Regulation and the regulator

Two broad themes emerged in discussion around professional regulation, one on the regulatory body as an entity of governing, and another on the rationality of governing as a form of influencing and thereby leading midwifery. Whilst it was established from the point of participant recruitment that Sharon’s views did not represent a corporate position of the NMC, her insights from within the discourse of regulation were nonetheless valuable in sensing the governmental rationality of the regulatory body. In establishing perceptions of the forms of influence of the NMC, the following position was noted in terms of the regulatory influence on the activities in universities, who train and educate midwives;

“The NMC, they are our ‘controlling’ body, so they do dictate what’s in the programme, they dictate who can be on the programme, what’s in the curriculum, they come and they do the approvals, they do the monitoring so they are not seen in my mind as ‘leading’ the profession, or leading women at any point.” (Angela, LME).

And whilst the ability to influence the knowledge and behaviours of midwives in this way is formidable others had different views on the influence of the regulator as extracting professionals who did not align to these things, going as far as suggesting they identify those who may push the barriers noted earlier;

“The NMC is overwhelmingly a fitness to practice organisation. They pursue individual nurses and midwives for errors and so forth, or...there's a wide range of charges that the NMC come up with and also they deal with the real mavericks of the profession as well. At one time I know that the calculation was 35% of independent midwives are either under investigation or had been investigated by the NMC...and that does tell you that part of the NMC role is about keeping everybody in compliance, I think.”

(Jenifer, Midwifery Professor),

“I think there's a fundamental difference between leadership versus enforcement, and the NMC is not a leader it's an enforcer and that's just completely different.”

(Helen, Healthcare Regulatory Law),

“The NMC are experts at fitness to practice, the expertise for midwifery comes from the Royal College of Midwives.”

(Fiona, Clinical Midwifery Lead).

In terms of the regulators positioning with respect to the UK central government and therefore the influence of government translated to an influence in midwifery, the following shows an episode of recent reprimand applied to the NMC by the government’s regulator of regulators, the Professional Standards Authority. But also, a level of intimacy in the NMC as an apparatus of government;

“Those events absolutely have shaped the way things are at the moment and a lot does stem from things like PSA report, because you know the PSA pretty much had the NMC in special measures and was doing special reports on them and you know.”

(Helen, Healthcare Regulatory Law),

“The world of midwifery changed on its axis post Morecambe Bay. The NMC had to go and reflect on their poor performance but also at the same time midwives were used, were scapegoated”

(Jane, Consultant Midwife),

“Well...that’s...that is a really um...moot point in that I do believe that, even though the NMC is supposed to be an independent charity it is very influenced by government diktats.”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

However, the redrafting of the most recent midwifery standards across a range of points in professional midwifery from education to practice is noted as fundamentally important in influencing the incubation of new midwives when aligned to the agency and authority of the regulator;

“If you want to initiate change, you need a bit of power, and the lead midwife role gave me legitimate power, by which I could, under the NMC standards direct curriculum development and get more involved in the direction that I saw the midwifery team going.”

(Angela, LME),

“We’ve still got to have them implemented within the programmes and the earliest our first qualified midwives will join our register will be around September 2023 so we’ve got this time lag now before they’re maybe going to make an impact”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

However, some views of the standards or perhaps the rationale behind their development was seen as being driven by other motivations;

“The whole miserable fallout from Morecambe Bay...we’re still suffering from the fallout from that and...the fact that new standards had to be written when actually there’s not that much wrong with the old standards, was so that they could bring in more curtailing measures on midwifery practice.”

(Jane, Consultant Midwife).

A sense of the reach of the regulator within the governing of midwifery as well as wider maternity care was also noted, and which appear to extend the role of regulation into that of organisational governance;

“I sit on boards which are not exactly part of my role, I’m there to gain that very important intelligence or perspective to feed into our wider work and the new CEO is very much saying well actually by being in that space we can also help the organisation that needs to know about this, and we can articulate it to them”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“They have control over the whole environment...or the whole bubble, and we’re all inside that bubble. The uni’s are in the bubble, the midwives are in the bubble, the women are in the bubble, we’re all in that bubble.”

(Angela, LME).

In terms of the governmental potency of the regulator as a mechanism of adjustment to professional midwifery, there appeared to be momentum in involving the regulatory process as form of prevention from harm by seeing patterns of errors in the fitness to practice process. But also, some hesitation as to whether the reach of regulation was arguably part of a larger bureaucratic machinery;

“We sit on huge amounts of data which probably up to this point has not really been used to best effect. Once that data is more readily available it means that we can share that with the people that can do something about it. So we can't go around and say there wasn't enough midwives on shift, that is absolutely not the role of the NMC, but something like the CQC are very interested in that sort of data particularly if it's a

pattern emerging, or similar Trusts or if it's similar themes that registrants have been referred for [to ftp] and this is early work but I think that's very very exciting because that means we could get into that space of prevention."

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

The perception, or even mentality of governing, from within the regulator as to what leadership is and how it is carried out is arguably a position of a sizeable bureaucratic machinery expressly built on authority and command structures and less so on the influential claims of leadership made so far in this thesis. And in considering the mentality of influence of the regulator across the strata of points in midwifery, from student incubation, to practice and to possible exclusion, the following illustrates this well;

"But I think going back to the leadership for me it's about at all levels, because it's about who you have actually in government isn't it, it's who you have in the various organisations whether it be the RCM, the NMC, Health Education England and their equivalent in other countries, but also it's about what you've said, what happens at Trust and Health Board level. Making sure there's a director of midwives at board level and until all of those pieces are in place that's where you get the leadership emerging and working together"

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

6.7 Counter conduct

Foucault's view on power as nested within relationships highlights resistance as a form of power or counter conduct. And despite a broad acknowledgment across participants of the existence of some forms of prescribed or limited scope of practice in midwifery, the point at which this could or should be over-ruled was linked to professional judgement. There was however an awareness of the potential conflict between the scope for professional midwifery practice and adherence to guidelines;

"For a midwife, if there's some sort of guideline that a midwife has to follow, this is what the guideline says, this is the protocol, but here's the actual evidence, so you need

to make an informed choice. Now a lot of the women that I look after work outside the guidelines, because they've been given informed choice."

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

"Yea yea, you're fitting within the guidelines, but the thing is you look at guidelines and you think 'they are only guidelines'. it's more of a narrative, isn't it? What's a guideline for? It's there to guide."

(Maureen, Quality & Policy Advisor),

"...but some of us refuse to be controlled by the algorithm and that frustrates a lot people...a lot of people midwives a lot of midwifery managers, and I refuse to be algorithmically controlled, you don't get anywhere"

(Jane, Consultant Midwife).

6.8 Professional identity and ethics

A number of participants spoke of their professional identity as part of understanding leadership and the governmental conditions which impact that, with some equating identity to relative volume, some to role development and others to collaborative NHS practices;

"In the NMC you've got 640,000 nurses and 40,000 midwives. And now they've got however many thousand nursing associates as well, and midwifery really? It just doesn't stack up our voice is tiny in the NMC. We've made it loud because we've kicked up such a fuss, but nevertheless, there is a resentment that we get lumped in with nursing"

(Jane, Consultant Midwife),

"Well I do think there's a lot of confusion between management and leadership in our profession and it's a really very blurred boundary, and there's a lot of the managers...what I'd say are not very good managers who claim to be inspirational leaders and they're not!"

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead).

“We've probably spent a decade or two working effectively as a team em...which is right and proper but I'm wondering if within that we've become a bit complacent as a profession. therefore, we've gone through that curve of the people who were really the advocates of the profession, that won the war that won the parity then we've become complacent because it was all about the team and in some ways maybe we've forgotten about our professionalism and accountability.”

(Claire, Senior Government Advisor).

Others were specific in the post-Kirkup adjustments made by the NMC in bringing midwifery closer to nursing, when it had previously had some more autonomous distinction from nursing;

“Supervision wasn't working in certain areas and instead of taking learning from areas where it was working really well they just decided to plank it, scrap it and make it you know make nurses and midwives all the same.”

(Rebecca, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“Don't...because joining nurses and midwives together will actually make my eye twitch. Because it's been a huge big issue...and this is going to be one of those words...but there's been a dumbing down!”

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“It's actually a bit of joke within my peers that a lot of midwives felt aggrieved when the term 'obstetric nurse' was used recently.”

(Heather, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“That's where midwifery sometimes falls down is that as a profession, we... and I bring it back to professional identity again... if you look at our history of being subsumed within nursing, subsumed within obstetrics, trying to climb out of that, or lead that, means that we have to fight a lot of the time and I think choosing which battles to fight that goes on”

(Maureen, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Others were more direct in the dissonance in professional identity as being subsumed into the organisational context and framing leadership as performance in a management domain particularly where corporate amenability is rewarded;

“So... my concern about leadership in midwifery is about knowing all the components of what actually is good leadership, and by that not just in managers, it's overall leadership and what that actually means for a profession and not just an employer. I don't know how that can be matched up”

(Viki, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“People who've got to the top of the rather poor midwifery career structure have tended to be promoted because they will ‘go along’...they're good corporate people...and in times of austerity they tend to get promoted”

(Jennifer, Midwifery Professor),

“People thrive and get promoted within the firefighting role.”

(Laura, Senior Government Advisor),

“We have these, these parallel universes, we have all this wonderful rhetoric, and we have some great research, that's tells us where we need to be in midwifery. But people leaders like Mary Renfrew and Jacki Dunkley Bent get drawn into the bureaucracy that ties midwifery down”

(Jane, Consultant Midwife).

One participant noted the dichotomy of a newly qualified midwife who worked part time in a midwifery led service and part time in a hospital maternity unit. In particular she spoke of the effects of prescribed midwifery practice, inferred here to be in some way de-professionalising her practice;

“She’s only 24, and she wants to go back to the routine of protocols and guidelines because she’s frightened, but she loves it when she comes and is what she describes as being a ‘real midwife.’”

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead).

6.8 The need to be seen to be

A number of participants spoke of the increased messaging being attributed to public protection, including in the role of regulator, and some felt this was unjust in its implications. Some felt this was perhaps a messaging to the public that the appropriate adjustments were able to be seen to be happening to restore lost trust;

“The NMC are the first people to say, ‘our role is public safety’. They’re not saying, ‘Our role is to listen to women and to lead them to a nice place’, it just says regardless of the consequences our role is public safety”

(Angela, LME).

“I don’t know what protecting the public means. Is it about protecting the public from midwives? We are the public. It’s like a term that’s been banded around for years, ‘protecting the public’ but what exactly does the NMC mean? Is it about safety, is it about protecting them against evil midwives that don’t practice properly?”

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“They have come out with the key message that this is about instilling value to the public and giving faith in what we are providing, but actually that’s because supervision was vilified by the media so it’s all still a bit of spin if you look at it. “They’re there to protect the public from those crazy rogue examples like Shipman...there’s always a loose cannon, a rogue in every profession, these people have fundamental core issues. But they’re not in the most part protecting the public from 50,000 Harold Shipmans.”

(Heather, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Views were shared around the process of revalidation as being a form of both messaging to the public around trust, but crucially in a way which did not enhance professional practice but was largely a form of showing compliance;

“Knowing the back story, but having written lots of policy type documents it's the sort of short strap line approach isn't it so I can see why they'd use that. I think it suggests a focus on fitness to practice and punishment parts, but where does that capture professional development and leadership parts?”

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“It's absolutely a tokenistic thing so that the public can trust, see there it's again ‘the public the public’, I just find it tedious. I've to keep copies of nice things people have said about me. I could get the gardener to say they've seen it, or just say sign this, or I'll read what my friend says about hers, ‘and Jaki can sign all the bollocks’. Honestly what's it to do with being a better midwife, keeping all that paperwork?”

(Jaki, Clinical Midwifery Lead),

“Revalidation and instilling the public's faith, absolutely, I get why they've gone for it, but for midwives it's of much less value than what there was”

(Heather, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“...because at the end of the day what the NMC would say to me, probably 10 or 20 times a day was ‘we're here to protect the public, that's our role, we're here to protect the public’ And it made me feel, am I not in my role as a midwife protecting the public? And again, it was this notion that as a midwife, a nurse or a doctor you're a danger to the public, and that's how we've been made to feel.”

(Jane, Consultant Midwife).

However, the regulator appears to have partially acknowledged this messaging, at least in its messaging to midwives, or in a 'need to be seen to be' of a slightly different manner;

"But what you won't find in any of the literature is that being cited verbatim, what we're much more about is promoting better safer care. Because registrants actually took a dislike to the fact that their patients had to be protected from them. It's almost what protection of the public sounds like. So that's where that narrative for the external affairs has changed. So, we don't talk about protecting the public although that is obviously still what it is."

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

6.9 Bureaucratising toward mediocrity

Most participants noted an alteration to midwifery professional practice over the preceding five-year period, with a perception of a proliferation of standardisation, correction, and adjustment of some kind. And this was perceived to be implemented as a result of historical errors in maternity care and a response from government. However, the alignment of professional midwifery roles and values with a form of organisational management, was seen by some as the point for maximum leadership contribution. And this was evident even in those participants employed by government;

"What if the Government comes out with a version that's a contradiction to what you believe midwifery wants to go. You still need to be there to advocate to what a midwife is and what midwifery can do"

(Laura, Senior Government Advisor),

"I mean to me, top-down leadership doesn't work. Positional power is the weakest form of leadership. Making people and telling people they've got to do things does not work. So, if you can be professional, if you can be credible, if they respect you and if they like you because actually you are professional and you're a decent person, that is FAR more powerful than having a position."

(Clair, Senior Government Advisor).

However, some seemed to see the prescriptive standardising of practice as limiting to scope of professional decision making and hampering that scope with an organisational cultural of fear of some sort. Also, that measurement or recording of professional activities was centred around blame and organisational protection;

“It's usually can we clearly identify who we blame so that we can protect the Trust, and this is the awful thing, things like record-keeping, the record keeping has become so specific now I mean we're being expected to...we're living in this really punitive, punitive scary atmosphere. I could go and work in a hospital tomorrow if I wanted to but I'm out! I'm done! Because I can't, I cannot, align myself with practises that midwives are expected to carry out, not anymore, it's just unethical.”

(Jane, Consultant Midwife),

Nevertheless, whilst participants could acknowledge parts of the governmental response to events in Morecambe Bay, some pointed out an inevitability in the lowering of standards in maternity care or stifling of improvement based on the bureaucratic focus on minimum care thresholds rather than opportunities for enhanced care. If that were to be the case then midwives could be focussed on performing only to minimum threshold measurements, which are claimed to exist to protect the public;

“Keep in mind that NMC enforce what is the minimum standards of what's acceptable, they are not...I mean they would probably say they promote best practice and stuff like that but that's just nonsense!”

(Helen, Healthcare Regulatory Law),

“That whole dynamic, of algorithms, pathways...and...that's true across the NHS, it doesn't enable health professionals to use their clinical judgement. It doesn't enable them to flourish, and grow, because you can only work to these certain protocols...or algorithms...or it's the lowest common denominator.”

(Jane, Consultant Midwife),

“The bubble needs to move; you can’t have a static bubble. Because new equipment comes along, new technology, new ideas and so we need leaders to have the vision for where we want the profession to be, and that’s not a managerial role!”

(Angela, LME),

“It's really interesting isn't it...I suppose the adversary for me is protocols and guidelines made by people that have no bloody idea.”

(Jaki, Midwifery Clinical Lead),

We had in incident, subject to a HIS review, and one of the issues was training of staff in baby heartrate traces, and when that came out they tried to focussed on it. But even with that focus they're still not compliant of 100% of staff doing training, so if people had accountability and responsibility at the forefront, you'd think that would be driving, because we find actually managers are chasing people up. Now if we were still in supervision that would be picked up at an individual level, that responsibility would be clear in your role as a midwife, but now it's become a management issue of staff rather than about professionalism.

(Viki, Quality & Policy Advisor),

“What's the driver, and the driver is reactive to complaints and targets. Reponses for assurance, performance measures...(laughs) ...so if we went back to the good old days it was about doing what you knew needed to be done because it was inherently right, that was your role as a midwife.”

(Heather, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Some responses appeared to suggest that the effects of the network of prescribed practice aligned to retribution from non-compliance could be seen in newer midwives in a way which implied an ownership or acceptance at a personal level in decision-making. Suggesting this way of practicing midwifery had been seen as a form of responsibility;

“Something happens to them...something happens to them to make them comply...it's like the culture of fear and somehow that fear has a profound effect on them so they think the only way they can practice is by working in that way.”

(Jaki, Midwifery Clinical Lead),

“But I think that’s a really hard thing for the midwives who are at the coal face if you like, in a busy unit, with not enough staff, they get pulled down don’t they into this very ‘we’re just getting the job done’ and sometimes it's really hard to sort of look up and say actually we’ve got a responsibility in all this ourselves”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

There was a proposal that internalising and displaying the attributes in the regulatory standards could increase the chances of advancement for midwives in highlighting the value brought from secondment opportunities for midwives to spend time at the regulatory body;

“I feel that’s absolutely critical for them not only working with their regulator, to find what on earth their doing for them, but also how that is a development for them as an individual which could maybe then lead to other posts or promotion.”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

However, despite the possible contradiction in leadership as being aspirational, driving positive change, innovation, and challenging norms for the right reasons, all of which have been noted previously in this Chapter, there still exists an idea that standardisation can generate professional leaders. Although the claims of the standards being a form of leadership are response to the prompt, it can be inferred that an important aspect of being this sort of midwifery leader is an ability to interface or navigate the expectations of a wider matrix of bureaucracy;

“Yes and I think this is something for the profession really, you know they will see people in various moulds and have expectations of what they should do, and you know, particularly as they interface with government bodies and other bodies. But actually, you know, you, this should empower midwives these new standards, to be leaders within themselves.”

(Sharon, Quality & Policy Advisor).

Summary

There is little consensus in what leadership in midwifery actually is, with some viewing it as part of an institutional role or title, and others viewing it as personal characteristics of authenticity, but also of strategy in choosing where to focus leader efforts. The discontinuity of Kirkup’s findings and the governmental approach of removing supervision appears as a form of de-professionalising midwifery identity, and as a punishment of midwifery. The effects of regulation are contestable as a complementarity of direction *and* influence, as the influence is a dominant one of control, from the minutiae of midwifery education through to professional practice. A notable direction of influence can be seen however of bureaucratising spaces in which professional midwives previously held discretionary judgement. Likewise, the efforts to demand protection for the public are disputed in their own level of authenticity, as are governmental demands to reduce errors by adopting risk-averse organisational and institutional practices. But what is also clear is that compliance is not only becoming the discursive norm, but that an anxiety exists around performing with respect to that compliance. There also an evident discontinuity between midwives as employees versus midwives as autonomous professionals.

Chapter 7. Midwifery leadership: a discussion

Introduction

Building on critique from the previous chapters, this chapter refines and concentrates the critique of the discourse of midwifery leadership based on the analyses thus far. It does this by firstly problematising the prevailing governmental target of maximising safety by proceduralism and standardised practice, as a dominant ambition of governing. I felt it ethically justifiable to pursue whether the value of leadership in healthcare practice could be identified and linked to a theoretical perspective, therefore a critical synthesis of this is then conducted. The participant findings from midwifery leaders in Chapter 6 seemed arguably ambiguous about what leadership was, for example, if it was organisational strategy, or personal practices, and therefore in this chapter I critically analyse this at a conceptual level. Throughout the analysis in the preceding chapters, and crystallised in chapter 6, there was a developing discursive discontinuity of professionalism within the context of institutional employment. Therefore, the critical foundations of this are examined before, finally, building on the findings in Chapter 5 and 6, a governmental momentum of bureaucratisation is critically explored, and arguments offered around political sovereignty and a *raison d'état* state based on performativity.

7.1 Targeting errors

The UK government appear to have demanded a leadership *target* for maternity care which is unlikely to ever be met, i.e., one of zero errors. The patterns of influencing and performances toward maximising safety can perhaps be morally justified but will always require improving until there are no errors. The UK Government must show positive progress of improvement toward that target, to display to the public some reassurance in the competency of government, following multiple cases of poor maternity care in England. A governmental shift has been shown toward creating assurance that the activities of midwifery professionals are adjusted toward minimising error by way of prescribed practice, standardisation, and regulation. The momentum for such changes can be viewed as an attempt to maximise 'health' as a metric toward which performance should be orientated. An

initial problem for such an intention was noted by Foucault's former mentor Georges Canguilhem:

"Biological normalities have no guarantee other than their fact, unless one gives them a metaphysical foundation...health is not at all an economic exigency to be asserted within a legislative framework...this founds for them the risk of failure, a risk from which the individual cannot be protected by any statute of socially normalized life"

(Canguilhem, 2012, p.61)

Likewise in Foucault's, *Dits et écrits*, in 1994 he notes that legislation has a role in securing access to healthcare or health insurance, but not to health. When, as in the NHS, providing that insurance and service directly from state, then government must demonstrate not only the technical efficiencies of good care, but the allocative efficiencies in its rationed distribution. As Foucault points out, *"Health, good health, cannot come from a right. Good and bad health, regardless of the unsophisticated or subtle criteria that we use, are facts: facts of health and of consciousness"* (Foucault, 1994, p.376).

Debono's (2012) study of hospital-based nurses identified 600 procedural policies under which they could be held accountable. From hand hygiene and patient identification to fire doors and sexual harassment. However, on average participants could only identify three of these. It concluded nurses were rightly focussed on patients not policies. Likewise, some surgical nurses spend 35% of their shifts completing procedural documentation (Hendrich et al, 2008). Moreover, Carayon & Cassel (2019) asked medical clinicians to identify which 'rules' they would break to improve patient care if they could. Of those suggested, 78% were not statutory or regulatory requirements but organisational behavioural requirements. Likewise, Stock & Sundt (2015, p. 841) noted surgeons claimed to be suffering 'checklist fatigue'. Finally, the American Society of Anaesthesiologists have 91 standardised guidelines for practice, some over 20 pages long. In total there are 4 million sources of what Johnstone (2017) calls 'operating room standards of practice' from various regulators in these clinical spaces. This questions whether safety in healthcare by such lists are simply a tool in aiding memory lapse (Raman et al, 2016). However, they frame the worker in a way which suits the planner/administrator in a world of linear, repetitive task-orientated activity (Stock & Sundt,

2015). When such things are normalised, they are viewed as a form of culture creation, applied to safety and harm reduction by means of proceduralisation. However, this is only useful if linked to worker audit and accountability. Likewise, Bourier and Bieder (2013) claim this is driven by a need to be seen to be 'creating safety' i.e., by creating more procedures and as a consequence demand more compliance. This effect of rule inflation in turn implies a singular monolithic 'the way' of doing safety and enveloping all discretionary professional practice as deviant. Arguably this is a form of safetyism and has been, according to Haugen, Softeland and Eide (2013) contributing to regulation of safety culture for the last 30 years. Likewise, the belief in the robust relationship between written procedure and worker behaviour, shifts professionals toward a knowledge-centric perception of the written word away from the intuition of the worker (Silbey, 2009). However, it also makes (potentially dangerous) assumptions that modified behaviour leads to safer outcomes. Consider for example Palmieri et al (2010), *"Safety cultures are established through modification in employee safety perspective and work behaviour...individual employee behaviours cumulatively provide the primary antecedent for organisational safety and quality outcomes"* (p. 97-98). Much like 'the need to be seen to be', there exists an element of comfort for the commissioners, planners, and administrators in showing compliance measures exist. Furthermore, Schulaman (2013, p 244) notes the tenuous links between this approach and outcomes, *"Procedures can lead to confidence in task performance for the risk-averse, promoting a narrow focus on processes and not on outcomes"*. However, if the drive to proceduralise maternity care were ever to become normalised in a circularity of safety culture, other pitfalls can be identified. For example, rule inflation, rather than lead to greater safety, can lead to greater risk (Hale & Borys, 2013; Dekker, 2001). Likewise, Raman et al (2016) examining 380 consecutive cardiac surgeries found 30 adverse incidents despite 100% compliance with preoperative checklists, citing reasons such as false anatomical heterogeneity and complexity in human surgery. Furthermore, in a study of UK hospitals enrolled in a national patient safety initiative, Meddings et al (2016) showed no positive association overall with rules compliance and infection rates, but in some cases showed an inverse correlation between compliance and infections. As Dekker (2022) notes, planning for the unexpected cannot be captured in linear rules-based safety measures and highlights the usefulness of wisdom and intuition in professionals when he states, *"If we accept that the relationship between compliance and safety is more complex or more context-dependant,*

then we also have to accept a fundamental double bind for those who encounter surprise and have to apply procedures into practice” (p.18). According to the literature in procedural-based safety, imposed standardisation diminishes the ability of expert front-line worker to deal with unknown events (Dekker, 2003; Woods & Shattuck, 2000). Furthermore, Amalberti (2013) suggests a pathway of middle ground or ‘sweet spot’ which allows professionals and procedures to coexist. It stands between *controlled safety*: that which is imposed by regulation and standardisation, and *managed safety*: reliance on professional expertise and intuition to adapt to nuanced occurrences.

According to large empirical health care studies from Australia, the UK, and the USA only 60% of care for adults and children is in line with evidence-based guidance (Mangione-Smith et al, 2007; Runciman et al, 2012; Braithwaite et al, 2018; Steel et al 2008). Furthermore, 30% is considered waste or duplication of effort (Berwick & Hackbarth, 2012; OECD, 2017). However approximately 10% of health care interventions globally cause iatrogenic harm to patients (Baker et al 2004; Carayon & Cassel, 2019). According to Braithwaite (2020), this ratio of 60, 30, 10 has existed in health care for the last 30 years (Braithwaite, Glasziou & Westbrook 2020; Braithwaite 2018). He and others claim this has remained stagnant based on the linear, mechanistic solutions applied to what is ostensibly a complex phenomenon (Greenhalgh & Papoutsis, 2018). The intention here is not to show the normalising of harm to patients as a 10% margin of expectation but rather to illustrate evidence that increased bureaucracy as a remedy, e.g., in organisational restructuring or procedural policy-density, is not effective (Manion, Davies & Marshal, 2005; Nugus et al, 2018; Amalberti et al, 2018). In 2019, infant and maternal mortality in the UK was 3.7 per 1000 live births, versus 5.8 in USA and 2.1 in Sweden (European range: 2- 4.8) (OECD: 2022). No harm to life is ever acceptable, however birth is unlikely to be without risk of some kind, and the skills of midwives and organisation of care in European economies is starkly better than for example India (28.3 in 1000 live births: 27.5 in South Africa). The table below shows no unusual incidence rates in injuries between the four nations of the UK. It is not a shift in direction of this thesis into data-driven conclusions however, rather to illustrate that risk and error are arguably a fundamental component (albeit unwelcome) of childbirth. Even in Iceland where this data appears globally most favourable in this context, one in every 1000 live births results in serious harm (OECD: 2022).

Table 4

Stillbirth, Neonatal and Perinatal mortality rates (95% CI) by UK country of residence, 2019

Rates per 1,000 births	UK	England	Scotland	Wales	Northern Ireland
Stillbirths	3.35	3.33	3.22	4.02	3.24
Neonatal Deaths	1.62	1.55	1.49	2.85	1.42
Perinatal Death	4.42	4.33	4.28	5.70	5.56

(MBRRACE-UK, 2021)

Moreover, based on the work of Renfrew et al (2014) cited earlier, of an estimated 139m births globally, 289,000 women will die during pregnancy, childbirth or soon after. Additional to that, 2.6m women will experience stillbirth and 2.9m infants will die in the first month of life. That equates to a prevalence of death or serious harm of 4.2% or in incidence terms 42 in every 1000 births per year. Whilst such data are vastly unequal globally, England does not appear to have a significant concern per se, other than perhaps the public visibility of poor maternity service performance in some areas.

7.2 Leadership in practice

There is a sense from some sources that leadership in healthcare is beneficial in terms of quality of healthcare performance (Firth-Cozens & Mowbray, 2001; Shipton et al, 2008; Shore, Cleveland & Sanchez, 2018; Kline, 2019). However, whilst these measures of leadership's success could not be considered evidence per se in terms of a causal link between leadership and outcomes, one measure in healthcare that seems consistent in its impact is 'inclusiveness'. By this is meant a feeling among members of a group (over which leadership is intended to influence) of being valued, having a sense of belonging, and being able to admit mistakes without unfair judgement by others (Kline, 2019). However, this is not a revolutionary finding as McGregor, in his Theory X Y, discovered a similar positive motivational faculty of belonging in organisational management terms in the 1950s (Carson, 2018). Inclusive organisations are thought to be 'psychologically safe' places (Shore, Cleveland & Sanchez, 2018). However, this thesis has shown examples where midwifery leaders claim not all practice environments host this dynamic. Nevertheless, the inspectors of the conduct of conduct in NHS England, the Care

Quality Commission (CQC), note that managing staff with respect and compassion correlates positively with hard data such as infection rates and mortality. Not only that, but positive correlates exist between staff turnover and absenteeism (Dixon-Woods et al, 2014). However, the dynamic here is that compassionate leadership is a way of influencing management of people in groups. Even more convincingly is the impact of 'disrespect' in negatively affecting patient safety based on its inhibition of collegiality and communication. Likewise, similar observations are seen in compliance with prescribed practice guidelines (Leape, 2012). However, in 2019, 24% of staff in NHS England claimed to have been subjected to bullying, abuse or harassment by managers at an estimated cost to 'productivity' of £2.28b annually (Kline & Lewis, 2019). Equally, the UK central Government, since Francis reported in 2013, has been aware of systemic conditions within the NHS in England where institutional culture placed the business of the system ahead of patients. Even in the governance unit working on behalf of the Minister, the Department of Health, had within it a pervasive culture of fear. Sir Robert Francis also reported of a widespread culture of all-cost compliance stating, "*...there lurks within the system an institutional instinct which, under pressure, will prefer concealment, formulaic responses and avoidance of public criticism.*" (Francis, 2013). The dynamic here which is most pertinent is the element of public criticism, and of avoidance for whom. Therefore, on one hand there exists the potential benefits from staff, the governed, having open conversations with their governors (or each other) about errors, or possible conflicts, and on the other a desire for an appearance of false harmony in judging governmental efforts. Kline (2019) calls this lack of psychological safety in having open conversations across and within hierarchies a type of 'protective hesitancy'. The notion of what's commonly called 'truth to power,' Foucault called parrhesia. For example, in one of Foucault's Howison Lectures at Berkley in 1980 he stated, "*Parrhesia was the opening of the heart, the candour which should pass not only between the disciplined and his master, but in the relationships of the members of the group*" (Foucault, 1980). Likewise, one of 290 recommendations made by Francis (2013) was a series of initiatives called Freedom to Speak Up which itself became a review and instruction to NHS Chief Executives (Francis, 2015). Therefore, without this form of trust, assurance, and safety, especially in challenging clinical situations, it is likely healthcare staff, including midwives, would remain silent rather than have difficult conversations at all. This becomes arguably dichotomous where the existence of overly prescribed midwifery practice is evident, which some participants are frightened about, but

which some participants claim is 'merely' guidance and where others noted that challenging such rigidity is actually a form of leadership in itself. Perhaps then the goal of healthcare systems is to institute rules and practices which encourage safe space acts of parrhesia to counter the effects of corrosive environmental conditions. However, such exercises, despite being system-wide in nature would and do still focus on individuals, and not the conditions which impact them. For example, according to Evesson, Oxenbridge & Taylor (2015) such system-wide attempts are fundamentally flawed in creating organisational culture change. They are methodologically founded in contract/employment law and may therefore see toxic leadership and management as exception rather than rule since the governors must be informed by the governed that such examples exist in the first place. If evidence suggests people are wary of acts of parrhesia, a false understanding of hidden toxicity may exist. Equally, Evesson et al (2019) claim such toxic leadership culture is pervasive and widespread. But again, when referring to 'leadership culture' they note the tendency is to see leadership as a form of titled role in an authoritative management structure, i.e., in those most capable of influence. Equally illustrative of the governmentality within public sector administration is the act of 'whistleblowing', much of which seems focussed on protecting an individual who wishes to practice an act of parrhesia rather than addressing the wider dispositif of governing, and which results in a binary decision of being upheld or rejected by that same dispositif as true or false, warranted or not so (Tarrant, 2017). It seems conflicted when subjects require to whistle blow at a local level to those same governors who themselves are responsible in large part for the prescribed organisational norms in the first instance. Equally when reports continue to show widespread concerns about continued systemic failures in maternity care in England, which include 'micro-whistleblowing' in terms of midwives speaking up in formal investigations, midwives would be fair in questioning the effectiveness of their acts of parrhesia in changing things for the better. Moreover, this thesis has given examples from midwifery leaders who claim there are parallels in clinical midwifery practice, for example, the appearance of compliance with guidelines versus truly woman-centred midwifery practice, or as one participant called it "algorithm midwives and *real* midwives". We also see suggestions that contractual practice often takes priority suggesting that the fear of retribution from governors is a conscious effort in decision-making. However, some evidence suggests that a restorative environment versus a retributive environment in one NHS Trust had a positive impact on both staff and the organisation (Kaur et al, 2019). However, unlike

clinical practice, which in most cases is developed by rigorous peer review, many organisational practices need not meet any such threshold. Therefore leadership, when framed as positive human resource practice and named as being *inclusive* or *compassionate* is little more than a hegemonic response of 'yet more training' according to Kline (2019). Likewise, one large scale study noted that using training aimed at improving diversity was least effective in altering negative managerial biases toward women for example (Kalev, Dobbin & Kelly, 2006). Moreover, according to Atewologun, Cornish & Tresh (2018), training in Unconscious Bias, widely used in the NHS and Universities showed limited efficacy. Equally, whilst claims are made of leadership approaches to alter working practices toward creating value and respect at work, there is more compelling fundamental arguments about the positive contribution of appropriate numbers of staffing as effective at providing inclusivity. For example, hospital infections rates, clinical outcomes and patient satisfaction are consistently higher in those with higher numbers of managers than those which have fewer (Veronesi, Kirkpatrick &, Altanlar, 2019). This becomes significant when considering the headline findings from the largest inquiry into maternity failures in UK history, one of which was the need for UK Government to finance an appropriate level of maternity and neonatal workforce to ensure safe and sustainable care, as well as the need for the governors (Trust Boards) to better listen to staff (Ockendon, 2022). It may be an oversimplification, but time and resource spent on altering the way subjects 'feel' about working together in healthcare environments, but which are fundamentally under-resourced, seems contradictory. Both Ockendon (2022) and Kirkup (2022) investigated much larger scale maternity concerns and both recommended an increase in midwifery resourcing. Likewise, Francis (2013) noted that prior to failures at Mid Staffordshire, over 150 nursing posts were recorded as being cut to reduce staffing costs with no evidence that the operational impacts were considered. Nevertheless, in 2020 the CQC prosecuted East Kent Hospitals University Foundation Trust, who were then fined £761,000. Maternity failures in this incident were allocated to systematic failures but also noted staffing resourcing issues in obstetrics (CQC, 2021). Considering a governmental gaze, it is perplexing in this example that government in this case investigated its own service provision, using its own investigators, and the resolution was to fine itself for those failures. Unless perhaps the appearance of governing the conduct of conduct, is the desired message to convince the electorate with respect to the effectiveness of the governors (Gillies, 2013).

Nonetheless, there is little doubt that workplace culture or the way things are commonly done is influenced by such things as professional and organisational values or constitutional statements and policies which in turn influence the actions of subjects. The behaviours of titled leaders, i.e., what they pay attention to, what and how they choose to influence, impacts those who in title are followers. Therefore, at the risk of obfuscating it with hierarchy or management, even when considering 'positional leadership' the indications are strong that enhancing compassionate leadership practice influences the compassionate practice of others (West, Eckert & Collins, 2017). And conversely, a lack of psychological safety, created by conflict between dominant financial and performance-related targets can be corrosive (Kline, 2019). Current leadership lexicon such as compassion, inclusivity, psychological safety, seems focussed on making material reparations to human subjects who feel void in some way of such things in their working environment. On the one hand exists a governmental rhetoric which demands continuous improvement, performance efficiencies and no errors, and on the other the potential that these very decisions are causing harm in doing so. Therefore, titled leaders who view staff as a cost, rather than an asset to potentially deliver such demands, cannot be the successful role models they are required to be. As Unwin (2018) points out, practices of 'relational' intelligence are more positively powerful than 'rational' activities of regulation, measurement, and efficiency. This does however imply that such forms of leadership, in healthcare environments which were not inclusive, could be an influential mechanism toward repeated management decisions which multiplied many times could become normalised and create positive cultural change.

Therefore, despite the lack of robust evidence in the literature around leadership effectiveness at a high academic standard (West et al, 2015) what can be determined is that in healthcare environments where people *feel* valued and *feel* safe these are shown to have fewer errors, fewer staff injuries, less bullying, reduced absenteeism, and reduced patient mortality (Carter, West & Dawson, 2018). Accordingly, Kline (2018) notes that healthcare environments where leadership as practice encourages such feelings, improvement can be seen in creativity, risk awareness, innovation, and information processing, which are likely to be key in delivering the requisite demands of governors. However, Dixon-Woods et al (2014) importantly note that in healthcare the behaviour of national bodies influences what titled or positional leaders do or do not do. Meaning titled leaders are led by the norms of the wider

hierarchy. However, in asserting this, Dixon-Woods et al (2014, p.108) then exemplify the confusing vocabulary, role responsibility, and the fudging of leadership, management, and administration. For example, in their six key elements in delivering compassionate leadership they call for *“inspiring visions operationalised at every level by leaders”* leading to the questions: who is having the inspirational vision, the assumption that there are leaders at every level, and an obfuscation of the agency of a management mechanism required to operationalise anything at all. Equally, *“leaders ensuring clear aligned objectives for all teams, departments and individual staff”* somewhat assumes a substitution of the preferred term ‘leader’ over manager, the latter of which perhaps has controlling or disciplinary connotations which are unfashionably oppressive. Such things do however resonate with Foucault’s governmentality as a set of tactics which are individualising and at the same time totalising. The confusing governmental rationality which can be inferred from Dixon-Woods et al (2014,p.108) is illustrated by their claim that inclusive leadership cultures are created by *“providing a limited number of challenging but manageable priorities”*. The assertion here being a culture of leadership is created by prescribing a smaller number of things to be managed, which despite the minutia of jargon could be simplified to motivating the energising and efforts of workers to provide demonstrable performance success. Therefore, the operationalising of everyone at every level in carrying out clearly determined set of activities which benefit the organisation, could be construed as a form of ‘enthusiastic bureaucracy’. Meanwhile, Heifetz, Linsky & Grashow, (2009) offer insights into ‘adaptive’ inclusive leadership which can further distort leadership as a tactic of effective management. For example, claiming leaders must respond to problems for which there may be well-developed solutions, such as managing shifts patterns, begging the question about this being administration, or that leader is a pseudonym for manager. Furthermore, where less predictable challenges appear the adaptive inclusive leader’s role is in creating spaces for collaborative discussion, rather than presenting a predetermined solution to the problem (Heifetz, Linsky & Grashow, 2009). Debatably such things could be called ‘leadership management’, or ‘inclusive management’, or ‘compassionate management’, or ‘collaborative management’, or simply ‘good management’. Furthermore, Kline (2019, p.130) notes that inclusive leaders recognise *“The most important person in the room is the one who knows what to do”* and that effective leaders recognise that *“all members of the organisation have a leadership role in their work”*. Since leadership no matter its version or method requires a

priori the existence of followers, this implies that subjects move into and out of a leader-follower dynamic but in an arguably unknown way, time, or reason other than perhaps being dependant on the nature of the problem-solving at hand. It also implies a sense of human and operational agility whereby hierarchical clinical knowledge structures, to which professionals are accountable, will perhaps relinquish their authoritarian dynamic in the hope of wider organisational leadership benefits being derived from acts of inclusivity. All of that of course on a canvas of, in maternity care at least, a governmental demand for zero errors and an under-resourced workforce. Questions here can be raised about who then benefits from this form of leadership of inclusivity and compassion. It seems that healthcare organisations who are fair and kind to the people working within them manage to create better outcomes for the patients (or women) about whom they are professionally intended to show compassion. This would of course see an organisation as a structural entity, a tangible creation, which administers instructions to those it employs. Foucault, however, leads us away from a focus on power as an instrument of coercion, no matter the benevolence of intention, or from discrete structures in which such actions take place, and instead see that power is diffuse but embodied in discourse in 'regimes of truth' and in micro-practices of power relations (Foucault, 1991). The implication here being that such constituent practices are part of the corpus of the organisation.

This legitimises the questioning of inclusive leadership in healthcare as a series of sanctioned micro-power states, ways of being, where everyone is emotionally invested in a singular bigger picture. That those within the healthcare discourse see these actions as truthful and therefore morally warranted. It also paints a picture of a possibility of a group dynamic as highly motivated in achieving a form of big picture, and where every subject is openly kind to everyone with whom they interact in doing so. Associating such things to leadership theory, this dynamic has an overtone with distributed leadership (Gronn, 2000; 2002) and transformational leadership (Sashkin, 2004). Critically however, two concurrent leadership subtleties can be seen when applied to practice: that of a devolved 'top down' influence and that of 'emergence', associated with bottom-up or horizontal influence. The former implies a deliberate approach within a hierarchy to alter a power relationship with subordinates for another form of gain. It is not difficult to infer a truth game or some form of motivational deception from that. Also, however the assumption that the upward and horizontal emergent

emotional investment in turn is nonetheless still capitalised upon from above. Furthermore, Bolden, Petrov & Gosling (2008) claim that distributed leadership holds some rhetorical value by its ability to shape perceptions of participation, identity and influence but can equally shroud the underlying dynamics of power. And of transformational leadership, Sashkin (2004, p.174) refers to '*leadership that matters*', perhaps reflective of the 'feelings' element that has been evident in how leadership differs from task-centred management. Leadership as practice therefore seems tasked, intentionally, or otherwise, to 'connect' with human subjects in ways which resonate in a highly personal capacity, a form of 'leaderful' practice (Raelin, 2011). Therefore, leadership implicated in culture shifts, i.e., where such practices were discursively normalised, would ideally welcome leadership as praxis (Furman, 2012).

7.3 Leadership as construct: person, result, position, or process, or all or none of these

So far, this thesis has shown leadership in Chapter 3 as an evolutionary discourse of theories, styles and attributes. It has indicated leadership influence in midwifery can emanate from favourable human behaviours, from the behaviours of ranked, titled or positional leaders and from aspirational documentation (Best Start; Better Births). It has illustrated leadership influence also in terms of prescribed and permitted actions via professional regulation and education. But it has also questioned it as being a form of organisational tactic. Since a lack of clarity in the nature of leadership is implicated in all these matters, it would be valuable to interrogate it further by problematising it at a conceptual level and in relation to these matters.

7.3.1 Ambiguity

The use of concepts and constructs is fundamental to the research process. For example, Merton (1994, p267) notes that scientific concepts are idea which, "*having been tagged, substantially generalized, and explicated can effectively guide inquiry into seemingly diverse phenomena*". Likewise, according to Weber, they are to be considered '*one of the great tools of all scientific knowledge*' (Weber, 1946: 141). Much as Foucault presents his concept of discourse as containing repeated speech acts, power/knowledge relationship and normalising practices within a discourse which act to sustains its existence, so too does Gramsci's *hegemony* offer ideas which can elaborate on leadership as part of the discourse of healthcare. Hegemony refers to cultural and or linguistic dominance at the expense of other, alternative

expression (Gramsci, 1971). Gramsci explains that hegemony is realised through forms of consent by subordinate interests to the dominating culture they feel will best serve their own interests. Like Foucault, Gramsci claims that such practices are 'taken for granted' and that people embrace a form of consensus that can obfuscate potential troubles or conflicts. It is here where Gramsci and Foucault arguably diverge, and for theoretical clarity a brief appraisal is offered. The notion of power is omnipresent in Foucault's analyses and theory. Like Gramsci, Foucault views power as a relation of force that only exists in actions. However, unlike Foucault, Gramsci views power relations in forms of binary oppositions (such as the leaders and the led, the rulers and the ruled etc.). Arguably, whilst acknowledging power generates resistance, and that resistance is a form of power, for Foucault power is more diffuse (Daldal, 2014). The intention here is not to propose a new view of power which conflicts with Foucault, but to argue that 'pockets' of hegemonic force are present in the discourse of knowledge. Therefore, as Putnam and Boys (2006, p557) explain, "*Hegemony refers to the ways in which subjects participate in their own subordination through socially constructing their identities, knowledge and institutions*". However, as Grint, Jones and Holt, (2016, p14) point out, "*Leadership is a salient example of a discursive hegemonic constellation*". Likewise, looking critically at institutional theory, Kraatz (2020, p255) points out a similar form of domination stating, "*modern institutionalism as a mythical beast that cannot be killed. When one stabs at it, it merely grows new appendages from its wounds*". However, leadership is burdened by ambiguity. Ambiguity in critical terms meaning a degree of uncertainty associated with multiple meanings attributed to a phenomenon (Sillince, Jarzabkowski & Shaw, 2012) and remains contestable in the absence of agreed boundaries or solutions (Alvesson and Sveningsson, 2003; Levine, 1985). In this sense, Livine's (1985, p8) notion of ambiguity in concepts here refers to "*ambiguities in language and thought*". Levine's work is expanded by Alvesson and Blom (2022) when they note the ways in which apparently scientific concepts are framed to suppress ambiguity, or to convey the appearance that a solid phenomenon is being studied. They note for example, "*authors claim that there is such a thing as authentic leadership or an HR strategy and this is clearly captured by the study in question, but this often conceals ambiguity*" (p.61). When it comes to such ambiguous notions, Hirsch and Levin (1999, p.200) provide the term *umbrella concepts*, which are "*used loosely to encompass and account for a set of diverse phenomena*". Accordingly, what may be a diverse set of phenomena are, in fact seen as a singular phenomenon. Allied to the potency of a hegemonic

momentum, critique of leadership as being too broad and all-encompassing, according to Learmonth & Morrell (2019), does little to prevent its juggernaut-like progress. Moreover, Haslam (2016) has written in the field of psychology of what he calls 'concept creep'. This is where an intended concept becomes expanded vertically, where it becomes *quantitatively* less stringent as it is applied to weaker and weaker phenomena than to which it was intended. But also, expanded horizontally where it extends to a *qualitatively* new phenomena in an emerging context. Consequently, Alvesson and Blom (2022) suggest that where concepts happen in hegemonic dynamics, such as those receiving large institutional sanction, alongside conceptual ambiguity of wide scope and diverse use, "*have a tendency to, over time, crowd out other concepts, even if they would be more precise or helpful for the purpose of representation*" (p.62).

Based upon the assumptions in Foucault's own concepts, those of discourse and those of the art of governing, it is evident thus far that leadership, whilst arguably ambiguous or at best contingent, is part of the discourse of midwifery. It is hegemonic in that subjects within the wider discourse of public sector healthcare are subordinate to its inclusion in working practices. For example, it is unlikely that any time soon, those who are governors will announce to the governed that leadership, in concept or practice, is over and is to be abandoned. Therefore, by problematising it at a conceptual level it is possible to clarify leadership ambiguity as it appears in the various component knowledge/power structures in this discourse.

7.3.2 Leadership as concept

According to Grint, Jones and Holt (2016), leadership as a concept has gained massive popularity in the last decades. The concept is visible in a broad set of scientific contexts but with very varied meanings (Day and Harrison, 2007). However, as a scientific concept, leadership has been presented in a research context of traditions such as human psychology. For example, Fairhurst (2007; 2008) conceptually portrays the *psychological* and the *discursive* approaches to distinguish between language and social interaction, noting Foucault's position on such things as being 'historically marked constellations of talk patterns'. However, in reviewing hundreds of publications around conceptual and theoretical leadership Dinh, et al (2014) found neither of these two scientific concepts were noted. Furthermore,

according to Alvesson and Blom (2022) few authors attempt a specific definition of leadership as a concept, preferring to generalise about its effects on individuals. Some authors, in an attempt to intentionally contrast it with management, see it as influencing emotional meaning rather than tangible behavioural output (Alvesson, Blom & Sveningsson, 2017). Meanwhile others contend leadership relates principally to novel or unusual situations of change, rather than situations of routine and stability (Palmer & Hardy, 2000; Grint, Jones and Holt, 2016). However, these conceptual principals seem disparate since it is possible to create stability by focussing on emotions and values, much of the healthcare literature shows that. It is also possible to stimulate and manage change by focussing on desired behavioural outputs. Moreover, in professions, where values are agreed, articulated, and codified, the former of these is all the more apt as a form of 'professional stability management'. At a fundamental level of conceptual rationality, Grint (2010, p.1) reduces leadership to first principals when he notes "*I have followers*". This helps in the distinction between titles and hierarchical positioning which aids in understanding conceptual leadership as something other than rank. However, in midwifery for example the term 'rank' and the title Chief Midwifery Officer does offer a number of signifiers of who is at least accountable in organisational terms for 'leading' and 'managing' midwifery within a territorial domain. However, a focus on followership does confirm to a degree the assertion that anyone can be a leader. Critically however, the term follower is vast in scope and only mildly less ambiguous than leadership. For example, followers range in rationale from loyalty, subordination devotion or fear, to those who are disinterested but nonetheless compliant (Kelly, 2008). A follower then, despite their intrinsic motivations, is any individual who coordinates their actions to align with those of another (Kellerman, 2008; Van Vugt & Ahuja, 2010). Likewise, Crevani (2018) and Hoskins (2008) note that leadership and followership can be distilled into sets of shared social processes of negotiation and agreement on generating order. It seems then that leadership is associated with a team or group, where collective decision-making adjusts the group dynamic by mutual consent. However, this is critically challenged by Uhl-Bien et al. (2014) who claim leadership is never truly shared at a conceptual level, inferring that disequilibrium of some kind is present, either in knowledge, ability, or insight. Shamir (2012, p.487) goes further in claiming "*if it [leadership] is truly shared then I suggest we don't call it leadership because the term loses any added value*". Therefore, despite a lack of consensus on much of leadership as a concept, one thing is evident and that is 'influence'

(Yukl, 1989; van Vugt & Ahuja, 2010). We now live in a time when even that term can be obfuscated by 'social influencers' who by select metrics would be remarkably effective leaders. However, historical distinction between leadership and management seems blurred (Zaleznic, 1977) if, like Bass & Avolio (1993), we consider arguments around transactional versus transformational leadership. According to Alvesson and Blom (2022, p.64), "*Leadership is often used so broadly that it covers everything and nothing*". Leadership as a term is used as a form of signifier, an empty floating term which allows people to fill it with a range of desired meanings (Grint, Jones and Holt, 2016).

In terms of leadership being something *people do*, those people can be 'top' managers, such as a CEO, or it can be what all managers do, or what people who are not managers do, or if accepting 'influence' as the essence of leadership, it is what anyone can potentially do. In terms of leadership as a *mechanism* it can be visioning, knowledge-based instruction, inspiration, role modelling behaviours, or even in religious terms: meta-physical fanaticism. In terms of its *initiation* leadership can be leader-driven, follower-driven, group-driven or a combination of all three. Leadership can *present* as a style, a human trait, a model, a training programme, a theory, a framework, or a set of beliefs. However, leadership can also be "*a fantasy, an identity support mechanism or a language game*" (Alvesson and Blom, 2022). Despite the multiple connotations in its heterogeneous nature, Learmonth and Morrell (2019) claim the hegemony around leadership is omnipresent in organisational literature which considers its applicability in an arguably homogenous way. Foucault, however, would likely see the difficulties noted in tying down leadership to a prescription from ambiguity as seeing leadership as a form of power. Foucault notes for example, in a 1982 essays *The Subject and Power*, that power is only power when addressed to individuals who are free to act (Burchell, Gordon & Miller, 1991) and that "*power acts upon and through an open set of practical and ethical possibilities*" (ibid, p.5). Foucault elaborates that "*power is defined as actions on others' actions*" (Foucault, 1982, p.792). It is possible to infer here that coercion in the form of a management hierarchy is not Foucault's target, and that his views of leadership power would be intrinsic to human decision making at a deeper level. And in terms of the conduct of conduct, and the implications of leadership rationality, he further elaborates "*the nature of the term "conduct" is one of the best aids for coming to terms with the specificity of power relations. For to "conduct" is at the same time to "lead" others.*" (Foucault, 1982, p.789).

7.3.4 Leadership and the concept of followership

To be useful, the concept of followership requires fundamental understanding into both the nature and impact of followers on leadership. Accordingly, Lord and Brown (2001) outline this process as a 'connectionist' view and which sees leadership as a dynamical relationship involving leading and following as interacting together within a given context (Shamir, 2012; Uhl-Bien & Ospina, 2012). By considering this as concept two broad positions on followership are useful in better understanding leadership in an organisational context, namely *position* and *process* (Uhl-Bien et al, 2014). Positional followership involves roles, which are formalised and ranked roles, such as management-subordinates in a hierarchy (Katz & Kahn, 1978). The process or constructionist approach (Fairhurst & Grant, 2010), views leadership as mutually generated complementarity of leader-follower acts (Fairhurst & Uhl-Bien, 2012; Shamir, 2012). The former therefore focusses on follower behaviours in response to leadership styles, whilst the latter focusses on followership as a social process. It is not difficult to see organisational leadership as nested in one of these followership perspectives and professional leadership in the other. According to Hopton, Christie and Barling (2012) the unhelpful or submissive connotations of 'follower' and 'following' come from the role-based view which optimises the leader in traditional leadership research. Accordingly, Uhl-Bein & Pillai (2007) note this has romanticised leadership and subordinated followership. However, this opens to critique some claims of leadership effectiveness which show followership as a marker of successful leadership, when the 'appearance' of following may in fact be based on coercive forces. In particular, where subjects operate within spaces of existential permissions, where they are regulated and scrutinised, it is also challenging to consider the margin between the coercive and the willing and between the led and the instructed. This helps visualise professional midwifery leadership, and the form of relational care between a woman and midwife, even in the semiotics and semantics of 'midwifery-led care', as being dissonant when placed in a practice environment which is not truly pursuant of that. For example, where an employer organisation is emphatic about the narrowing of the bandwidth for professional decision-making, then the relations of following between woman and midwife can be contested as being a set of unwelcome risks of non-controllable actions. The knock-on effects of which could view professional midwifery leadership as poor performance in employee-follower conduct. Midwifery practice then within a space of multiple controls has two contesting follower relationships, that between the professional self and a woman, and the

political self as an employee. Arguably, the post-structuralist approach of Collinson (2006) in leader-follower relations allows better understanding when considering the constructionist process, in particular when viewing midwives as subjectified in a wider NHS discourse. In this way individuals are best understood as social-selves and according to Giddens (1984) peoples actions can be seen in a set of complex conditions and consequences, such as in the power dynamics claimed by Foucault (1982). In particular, Collins (2006) argues this view illustrates how individuals collude in their own subordination. This is particularly relevant when seen alongside Foucault's technologies of the self and 'acts of existence' (Foucault, 1992). Fittingly, Collinson (2006) outlines three types of follower identity which can be seen in the workplace. One he calls 'conformist selves', highlighting followers who act in agreement with prescribed ideal-type behaviours. For example, *"Conforming individuals tend to be preoccupied with themselves as valued objects in the eyes of those in authority"*. (Collinson, 2006, p. 183). The second, aligns well to Foucault's position on resistance as a form of power and that of counter conduct (Daldal, 2014) and what Collinson names 'oppositional selves' that employ various types of dissent as strategies to address the dissonance felt by followers in heavily controlled managerial systems. Finally, he notes the 'dramaturgical selves', acknowledging where subjects *"under the gaze of authority...are aware of themselves as visible objects"* (Collinson, 2006, p. 185). In these conditions individual followers engage in what Goffman (1959) referred to 'impression management', and subsequently this leads to a form of heightened self-awareness and followers becoming skilled manipulators.

7.3.5 Leadership as strategy

An emphasis has been so far that leadership in midwifery is partly constituted by professional evidence-based practice but also by regulation of midwifery behaviour; via a code of conduct, standardised practice, and revalidation but also of midwifery thought and knowledge; via control of university curricula, and regulation of those who dispense education. Also, that there exists, via public disciplinary hearings, a measure of punishment for non-compliance with these measures serving as a warning to others for their transgressions. A professional duty of candour insists, whereby the governed are expected to report themselves and others to that regulator, ensuring maximum probity for those who govern to make reparative actions toward order. As part of a wider governmental dispositif, healthcare policy shapes the practice environment in which midwives' function. These are considered a form of leadership

as strategy i.e., the establishing of a future state toward which subjects in a professional organisation are to be influenced. To that end, leadership as strategy requires to undergo critique and by doing so, problematised at a conceptual level. Strategy has become widely dispersed and accepted across the corporate sphere from its origins in the military domain (Knights and Morgan, 1991). And in the civil service arena, this proliferation is thought in large part to be down to New Public Management (McLaughlin, Osborne & Ferlie, 2002). And, as Sahlin-Andersson and Sevón (2003) point out, when concepts move from one domain to another their scope, meaning and application can vary. In fact, Sillince, Jarzabkowski and Shaw (2012) suggest that some actors within organisations even use this ambiguity as a form of rhetorical advantage. In scientific terms however, business strategy and strategic management, seem to hold differing meanings (Hambrick and Chen, 2008). This can be viewed in the literature from Porter's seminal work on business policy in industry positioning and managerial planning (Porter, 1980) to a resource-based view of the firm (Barney, 1991). Conceptual shifts can also be seen from strategic planning (Ansof, 1965) to strategic processes (Mintzberg, 1994) to strategy as practice (Golsorkhi et al, 2015). Moreover, Whittington (2000) sees the concept of strategy in four perspectives: the classical, the processual, the evolutionary and the systemic. Therefore, much like the case for leadership, strategy and/or strategic management, although they compete to some degree in concept and definition they seem to coexist. By that is meant neither have solved the misgivings or shortcomings of the other as new understanding emerges. They are therefore to some degree ambiguous and yet exist in a form of hegemonic protection within organisational science. Consider for example McKeown (2012) who states strategy is about shaping the future. Moreover, moving chronologically backward through arguably influential authors in the field, '*Competitive strategy is about being different. It means deliberately choosing a different set of activities to deliver a unique mix of value*' (Porter, 1996, p.64). Likewise, Mintzberg (1978, p.934) claims strategy is '*a pattern' of a stream of decisions with a significant element of emerging (not just deliberate and planned) actions*'. Or Chandler (1962: 13): "*Strategy can be defined as the determination of the basic long-term goals and objectives of an enterprise, and the adoption of courses of action and the allocation of resources necessary for carrying out these goals*".

Much in the way we can consider leadership as practice, Jarzabkowski et al (2007) consider strategy as practice and define it as,

'...as a situated, socially accomplished activity, while 'strategizing' comprises those actions, interactions and negotiations of multiple actors and the situated practices that they draw upon in accomplishing that activity'.

Consider then the above for stark similarities alongside the following, which is Hosking's (1998) definition of leadership, *"leadership concerns socially shared processes in which definitions of social order are negotiated, found acceptable, implemented and re-negotiated"* (p.147). One consideration might be that this merely illustrates the intimacy of leadership in delivering strategic goals, influencing groups toward better new futures in some way. However, it is worth considering Myer's (1991) work which suggests that the field of research in strategy is an example of the power of a 'non-concept'. He claims that neither strategy nor policy have intrinsic meaning in the sense that in their extreme derivation they mean everything. For example, in considering Porter's view of being competitively unique in adding value. Value is intrinsically unique to everyone and is also transient. Likewise, both Mintzberg and Chandler's definitional claims are focussed on, and synonymous with, behaviours (planned and unplanned) and therefore everything is strategy. In his view strategy and policy resemble a dominant power in political science. *"They are catch-all concepts that denote anything and so they mean nothing and therefore cannot be operationalized"* (Myer, 1991, p.831). However, if it is accepted that leadership is a form of power, then again Foucault adds clarity from his perspective of power and strategy. He establishes three forms in which strategy can be deployed and through which power acts. The first is arguably a means to an end, a form of *'rationality functioning to arrive at an objective'* (Foucault, 1982, p. 793). Another is more on a footing of war conflict and attempts to *"deprive the opponent of his means of combat and to reduce him to giving up the struggle"* (ibid, p.793). The third however is more insightful in terms of governmentality, when it frames a relationship between actors which have a similar or shared goal but perhaps differing purpose and situates this dynamic in a game. He claims that strategy *"designates the manner in which a partner in a certain game acts with regard to what he thinks should be the action of the others and what he considers the others think to be his own; it is the way in which one seeks to have advantage over others"* (ibid, p.793). This

allows better understanding of leadership strategy as a form of governmental technology, i.e., as a means of influencing toward a preferred state of things, but which also encompasses any number of combined tactics and techniques in achieving it. Moreover, the examples noted previously of actions of government upon midwifery can be seen as a relationship of confrontation of sorts and this is valuable in seeing discursive struggle in midwifery leadership and not a blatant domination of sovereign-like rule. Politically, and of course practically, government and society need midwifery. The dynamic of strategic confrontation in Foucault's sense of power illustrates both the power of government as institutions and its limitations, and equally those of midwifery as a professional institution. Leadership as power, and strategy as projects of power relations, has as its natural end game a state of order, of low entropy. Such mechanisms however are not mechanisms of rule, but mechanism of governmentality: *"one can direct, in a fairly constant manner and with reasonable certainty, the conduct of others"*. (Foucault, 1982, p.794).

7.3.6 Leadership as institution

Although eventually seen by many as overly structural in nature much of institutional theory can be traced to the work of Meyer and Rowan (1977) and that of DiMaggio and Powell (1993). As Deephouse and Suchman (2008) observe however because of a dominant focus of theory development rather than theory testing, its legitimacy as a concept *"...has exhibited substantial plasticity from its earliest usages"* (p.49). Accordingly, Lounsbury and Crumley (2007) note a shift from structural to agency-based perspectives and eventually to a compromise in such distinctions toward institutional entrepreneurship. Critically however, according to Alvesson and Spicer (2019) this implies the evolution of a field of study which claims to explain institutions in terms of isomorphism to variances, from structures to agency, from dynamics to stability and from individual management practices to corporations. This subsequently leaves the question of what an 'institution' is in terms of a concept. Another prevalent author in this field does define it, but much in the way leadership and strategy can be seen, the definition leans toward being all-encompassing. Institutions are *"cognitive, normative and regulative structures and activities that provide stability and meaning to social behaviour"* (Scott, 1995, p.33). It can be inferred from this that both thinking and doing are value-adding, and since they are normative and regulated, they are meaningful to an apparatus of wider, somehow predetermined, social value. Institutions in this sense can be

seen as a product of, and products for, purposeful action. However, Lawrence and Suddaby (2006, p,216) critique existing institutional research as overly focussed on cognition and *“the effects of individual and organizational action on institutions”* and consider this field of work on concept *“to represent the broad category of purposive action aimed at creating and maintaining institutions”*. In this sense, Lawrence and Suddaby claim institutions to be beyond the limits of the firm, professions, or schools for example, and instead exist as a direct result of reiterated processes. Likewise, institutions as a concept at a fundamental level, concerns organising and establishing procedures (Alvesson & Blom, 2022). This of course then adopts any number of transformations when enlarged and contextualised into the domains of professions, firms, and schools for example. However, within the discourse of institutional research, Thornton, Ocasio and Lounsbury (2012) refine the institutional concept to what they call institutional logics which *“operate at a supra-organizational level, as material-symbolic languages, a practical metaphysics”* (p.94). Therefore, in considering their definition of this concept, similar all-encompassing effects can be inferred from those of leadership and strategy, and from which implies that the institution is everywhere and is everything. Institutional logics are:

“The socially constructed, historical patterns of cultural symbols and material practices, including assumptions, values and beliefs, by which individuals and organizations provide meaning to their daily activity, organize time and space, and reproduce their lives and experiences” (Thornton, Ocasio & Lounsbury, 2012, p.3).

For Foucault, institutions are a way of setting particular relations of power so that a certain number of people are advantaged in some way. Likewise, he associates institutions as being able to propose sets of values and rules for action, as a type of moral system (Bevir, 1999). However, from all attempts to refine the concept of institution, some patterns can be unearthed. There are cultural components, those of organising and proceduralising; from which can be derived some sense of standards. Where such things exist, there would likely be a judicial component should standards deviate. For some authors that implies the need for shared meanings, frameworks, and formalised conditions of thinking and behaviours (Lounsbury and Crumley, 2007). However, Ocasio and Gai (2020) point out an evolution of institutional theory that they call ‘organisational institutionalism’ which focusses on the

dynamics between organisations and institutions. They attempt to clarify that institutions usually refers to one of three categories or conditions. Firstly, political, social, and economic organisations which have a role in government or governing populations. Secondly functional groupings of such organisations, such as hospitals or universities. Thirdly the *“practices and artifacts of such institutions”* (p.265). However, the latter of these they claim should not be a feature of institutional research *‘but rather considered as institutional products that may or have not become institutionalized’*. There are authors who consider the derivations of perspectives and opinions in institutional concept as positive examples of theoretical pluralism (Ocasio & Gai, 2020). It may well be that terms such as ‘institutional’ or ‘organisational’ are surface-level ideas which merely acknowledge a fundamental complexity which is fruitless to attempt to disentangle and which can only be observed (Lok, 2020; Alvesson, Hallett & Spicer, 2019). However, Ocasio and Gai’s (2020) claims of artefacts and practices of institutions, connects with Foucault’s ideas around the regularised and legitimised actions of actors within a discourse. For example, where repeated relations of power are creating become that which institutions then make visible. As he states discourses *“produce practices that systematically form the objects of which they speak”* (Foucault, 1970, p.135; cited in Smith 1972). In institutional terms then, if such practices are able to be influenced to then become regularised, the question remains not only *where* leadership should enter the discursive formation, but the form which it's influence should take.

7.3.7 Leadership as games

It has been shown that healthcare environments and systems of working, which amplify trust and inclusivity appear to have positive impacts on a range of functioning attributes in those who work within them. In lay terms, people who experience methods of working which are connected to value and values, seem to perform better than those who do not. The potential has been raised that leadership is implicated in changes toward creating such conditions, via its influence over groups. But questions can be asked around who is leading and who are following, at what time, in what way, and what associated motivations are behind such patterns of activity. However, Nobel Economist Robert Aumann (2005) claims that, *“The theory of repeated games is able to account for phenomena such as altruism, cooperation, trust, loyalty, revenge...in terms of the selfish utility-maximising paradigm of game theory and neoclassical economics”*. He bonds such activities to a form of ‘evolutionary mechanics’ which

have become utilitarian not necessarily as conscious tactical efforts of the few but as a routine of the many. He explains,

“That it accounts for such phenomena does not mean they deliberately choose to take revenge or act generously out of rational motives. Rather over millennia people have evolved norms of behaviour that are successful, indeed optimal”. (Aumann, 2005, cited in van Vugt & Ahija, 2010, p.42)

It is possible therefore to infer that the widespread use for example of compassionate leadership terminology across healthcare, and its demarcated existence in institutions which promote and deliver it, is an attempt to manage performance. If people perform better when they feel valued, trusted, and safe, and this translates to better outcomes for patients (or women in midwifery) the rationale is clear for acting to create such feelings in healthcare staff. If individuals perform better, then an overall organisational improvement would result. Multiplied across purposeful collections of organisations would then result in public institutional accomplishment and subsequent social gain. Therefore, managing performance in any public sector organisations seems ethical, justified, and reasonable. For example, according to Aboubichr and Conway (2021), systems of performance management (PM) are seen as vital tools in improving employees’ motivation, performance, and productivity. Likewise, assertions are prevalent that organisations who implement performance management approaches fair better overall than those who do not (Aguinus, 2014). However, targeted research on the relationship between such systems and individual employee performance is largely inconclusive (Poster et al, 2013). The term ‘gaming’ is used within the literature to refer to people who can exploit PM systems to better their own career progress. For example, in environments where prescribed standardised demands in the outputs of individuals are premised on advantage for the organisation, particularly where these are inspected, human actors can convey the appearance of compliance. These sorts of gaming tactics have been examined in a range of public sector spaces such as higher education (Bedeian et al., 2010), schools (Figlio and Getzler, 2006) and also healthcare (Conrad and Uslu, 2012). Moreover, what authors such as Aboubichr and Conway (2021) demonstrate is the ability of a prescribed performance environment to elicit the tactical games which emerge in response to performance metrics. The inference being that where strict prearranged

requirements are set for human activities, human actors are inclined to find workarounds. The assumption that a PM system could cherry-pick a series of metrics to infiltrate the practices of healthcare workers to elicit a sense of inclusivity is conceptually challenging. To therefore, *build* some form of performance management as a form of leading midwifery, there would need to exist a clear and unequivocal understanding of exactly what activities midwives should be doing, when, and where, as a prerequisite. Further, it would need to be established not only what but why and in what way a measure of performance could be improved. However, from a philosophical viewpoint this places a primacy on the organisation or institution and not biological women. From a professional values perspective it also challenges midwifery autonomy (Newnham & Kirkham, 2019). It is also dominated by a deterministic archetype of the needs of birthing women which would run contrary to their identity and right to choose, which is a core part of professional midwifery. Such an approach would also be reliant on forms of surveillance and inspection, measurement, or assessment of whether these organised expectations were being met. However, from a perspective of governmental rationality, the trust which seems essential within working environments noted already as beneficial, is not reflected in the governmental technologies levied upon midwives since Kirkup (2015). By that is meant, if the performance of midwives is to move toward one of performance measurability and categorisation of success judgements then the rational response of midwives could easily become part of gaming were it not felt as being in alignment with an implicit professional value-base. What is measured becomes what matters, and not necessarily the imbedded professional ethic of prioritising the individuality of birthing women. Were for example, the institution of government to impose such a PM approach, what becomes ultimately normalised is a rationality of midwifery as being 'with institution' over 'with woman'. Likewise, if a leadership direction is toward scrutiny and compliance, then a judgment must first be made that such things were lacking in midwifery. And such a thing can reasonably be asserted as a being a result of the Morecambe Bay maternity scandal which cast a public gaze not only upon midwifery, but upon government only months after Francis (2013) did the same. Traces of the discontinuity to a rationality of performance management can be traced in the midwifery archive as was seen in Chapter 4. For example, the removal of midwifery supervision as a form of professional self-governing. To manage its own annual professional development, can be viewed as another example, whereby midwives were forced against their democratic wishes to undertake revalidation alongside nursing and are

be brought *closer* to the panoptic gaze of the NMC. From a rationality of governmental technologies, we can see that just as the NMC licence universities to create new midwives that the UK government also licence the NMC via its parliamentary committee structures. In terms of governmentality traces show a demonstration of not only rationality but it's technologies of performance-adjustment for a profession with whom society has had a longstanding relationship for many years. An analysis of wider methods of healthcare performance management across the UK is beyond the scope of this thesis. However, what can be seen is that since work began post-Kirkup to alter the relations between the state and midwifery as a profession to improve maternity performance there are still issue of concern. What is observably different from the problems in Morecombe Bay is not only the size of the concerns in Telford & Shrewsbury and in Nottingham in 2022, but that midwifery as a profession has not been targeted in the way in which it arguably was by Kirkup in 2015. In fact, both Ockendon (2022) and Kirkup (2022) could be seen as supporting midwifery-led care in some sense, either indicating a shift in governmentality or a shift in acknowledgment of the profession. In probing leadership as games, alongside the dynamic between the governors and the governed, it is possible to see a congruity when aligned to the dominant governmental drive of 'safety' in healthcare. For example, the National Report on the State of Patient Safety in 2022, notes that progress has been made in "*creating a more positive safety culture among the workforce*", associating this with the highest level of reporting of patient safety incidents than ever before. However, Foucault offers useful critique of *culture* in *The Hermeneutics of the Subject* lecture at Collège de France in 1982, which illuminates this point in a wider scheme of thought describing it as, "*a hierarchical organization of values, accessible to everybody, but at the same time the occasion of a mechanism of selection and exclusion*" (Foucault, 2005, p.179). What is claimed is that healthcare staff, encouraged to report to the healthcare regulator where failures or near failures occur, have the collective effect of altering safety culture. The panoptic gaze of the Care Quality Commission (CQC) is commended in the report and its method of impact on performance referred to as "*the new inspection regime since 2014*" (Illingworth et al, 2022, p.6). The speculation of the success of scrutiny and incident-reporting is correlated with the number of NHS Trusts 'rated' as good or outstanding in the safety category from 13% to 40% between 2015 and 2022 (Illingworth et al, 2022, p.6) However, the NHS Staff Survey in 2021 noted one in four staff do not feel secure raising concerns about unsafe clinical practice, and two in five staff do not think they

would be treated fairly when incidents happen (NHS England, 2021). This can be interpreted in divergent ways, for example, that the workforce is overall docile as subjectified individuals within a regime of inspection. However, that inspection regime is not a tangible institution in and of itself, the regime is not the CQC, and unless that regime were totalitarian it cannot easily enforce those subjects to self-report issues of deviant practice with a view to preventing harm. The regime is one of 'truth games' made in correlating improvements with scrutiny and candour within an evolving discursive normalisation. According to the report's claims the governed are willing like never before to report their fellow citizens to the governors: and this despite a lack of confidence that they themselves will be protected by the governors in doing so. If Aumann (2005) is to be acknowledged the report implies there would be more to gain in a subject being compliant, if not in their own sound clinical practice, in reporting the non-compliant actions of others. In this dynamic of the art of governing, reporting deviance from prescribed demands of government, now becomes part of performance management itself. Furthermore, with a focus on maternity, the same National Report, illustrates the potential for leadership as games. Whilst acknowledging improvements in metrics such as maternal and neonatal mortality and morbidity, "*progress is not being made quickly enough to meet the Government's own targets by 2025*" (Illingworth et al, 2022, p.6). Performance is not yet at a satisfactory pace, and this is emphasised by comparisons to Sweden. Such statements could be interpreted (or misinterpreted) as making comparisons with Europe as games of competitive motivation. But more interestingly as an example of the wider dynamic of governors and the governed with respect to public opinion when the report notes, "*The public scrutiny that has followed the scandals at Morecambe Bay, Shrewsbury and Telford, and East Kent has provided further momentum in driving improvements in maternity safety*" (Illingworth et al, 2022, p.6). Public opinion, despite being anarchic, is seen as a justifiable lever to demand greater performance. In terms of the report's formal recommendations on the leadership target of safety, the governmentality of detection and adjustment can be seen. For example, the shift toward better more accurate, metrification of safety-centric data allied to monitoring is revived. Aligned to this is the prescription of activities of healthcare subjects via organised planning. The accountable governmental institution, the Integrated Care System (ICS) as outlined in the Health & Care Act 2022, is implicated in its role in monitoring activity. And despite it being a report covering the activity

of 1.5 million staff in NHS England, maternity care has its own declaration of intent in the recommendations.

1. *The breadth of patient safety data needs to increase.*
2. *The accuracy of key patient safety measures needs to improve.*
3. *A workforce plan for the NHS and social care system is urgently needed.*
4. *Integrated Care Systems need to play a central role in monitoring patient safety.*
5. *Progress in the safety of maternity services needs to accelerate.*

(Illingworth, 2022, p.8)

The cycle of activities of performance, improvement, the repeated statements within the discourse of healthcare are now pinned in the archive of safety by another formal lever for action. In other words, an institutionalised statement has been recorded as a point of measurement and legitimacy. If discourse is generated and sustained through sources of power in a social order, then reports such as the above prescribes certain set of categories of legitimating knowledge and by doing so create discursive truths. As Foucault (1970, p.136) explains, *“through its reiteration in society, the rules of discourse fix the meaning of statements or text to be conducive to the political rationality that underlies its production”*. Furthermore, in terms of leadership as games or justifying a ‘call to action’ such as this report, Gill (1995, p.399) provides an insight into discursive formations as *“a set of ideas and practices with particular conditions of existence, which are more or less institutionalised, but which may only be partially understood by those that they encompass”*. This does imply the creation of followers, but arguably not ones who completely conscious of why they are following. The purpose of noting reports such as this is to render them visible to Foucault’s later governmental work on ‘truth games’ (Foucault, 1988). As Besley (2005, p.77) points out, Foucault was intrigued by such games as to how in medicine and other social sciences *“have developed knowledge and techniques to enable people to understand themselves”*.

Summary of leadership as construct

Leadership happens. At a fundamental level it is questionable whether it happens by intention, or by serendipity, whether it can be encouraged or even successfully resisted. People do however follow other people (or things), which in turn can allow leadership to be observed.

Since life itself is complex, only parts of it are determinable, and perhaps because of this leadership as a concept is non-universal and very much context specific. As strategy then, attempts to control, limit, and prescribe those human actions which are determinable makes sense in terms of meeting required ends, when at the fundamental level leadership cannot resonate with all individuals in the same manner at the same time. Therefore, leading by strategy can create a collective reminder, a map of intentions, as those within its purview opt in and out of the foundational follower 'buy-in' at the conceptual level. Where repeated patterns of strategic activities become regularised around discernible societal imperatives leadership in this way can be seen to have meaning and worth. In economic terms, if institutional leadership is repeatedly 'value-adding' in the regularity of its organised processes, then it could be a purposeful way to consider creating change. The issue of course becomes what, and for whom, is the value being added. For example, in public sector institutions, prioritising a zero-error public-facing performance in governing, implicates value for political sovereignty. Implicit in this assertion is the requirement for standardised, heavily controlled processes which require a scaffold of surveillance since reporting publicly on governmental improvements becomes priority, as does reporting that more action is required and having this accepted without challenge by the governed. However, gauging success in performance improvement by focussing on the lack of errors seems convoluted in delivering value. In midwifery, routes where errors can occur would need to be traced quickly and adjusted. If, however, individualised midwifery-led care for women is the true value-centre then one interpretation of appropriate calibration and adjustment lies within the critical nature of professionalism. As a profession, midwifery has for centuries adopted a rationality of improvement based on objective clinical evidence and value-based practice for women. In the government of midwifery then, for the governors to relinquish direct control of the governed there needs to be an intermediary element, a proxy of trust in the profession and the professionals. In viewing these dynamics through a lens of governmentality, at a societal level, if the political sovereign is to remain 'popular' in the eyes of the electorate, they must be considered competent in the things which they are entrusted to oversee. Where midwifery is principled on trust between a midwife and woman, part of that trust is in some sense outsourced to government in terms of assumed trust in their governance of maternity care. From a philosophical perspective of midwifery, the autonomy of women and autonomy of the healthcare institution are in dispute. In seeing government as institution, the trust between

government and healthcare *professionals* has been challenged most significantly by the public enquiries of Shipman, Francis, and Kirkup. And the questions raised have left traces in governmental technologies. Shipman led to a shift in professional medicine from self-regulation to revalidation and greater probity by government. Francis led to revalidation in professional nursing by the NMC. And following Kirkup, midwifery was also shifted from a degree of self-regulation to revalidation. These traces of governmental shift (in rationality and technologies) are seen where trust is lost between state and professionals and specifically in a reflex response to a public enquiry. The leadership inferences drawn then are around the need to create certainty and manage expectations in the institutional, professional, and public context. It could be argued that what can now be seen from a drive toward order is a duality in value versus values. The perspective of the governors sees midwifery as part of a maternity service and derives an economic value from positive associated activities around childbirth. In the current climate the most *valuable* being demonstrable error limitation. From professional perspective, midwifery values are part of an identity, bound in autonomy, driven by women's needs and choices. The former would like to limit those choices, the latter (within clinical evidence) seeks to maximise not only choices but the element of giving choice. If it could be accepted that this governmental position was accurate, the governors would see birthing women as consumers, whilst the governed see birthing women as woman. Midwives would need to transfer from an internal virtuous rationality of individualised advocacy for woman, to an externally rationalised contract of limited activity with women. From a position of loyalty and ethics to one of compliance. From a rationality of professionalism to one of employerism.

7.4 Contract or covenant

According to Veloski et al (2005) for some fifty years the literature on professionalism noted that medicine placed too much emphasis on pathologizing the biological subject at the cost of compassion and empathy. Thirty years ago, clarity emerged on the distinction between a profession and an occupation. A profession became, "*a vocation with a body of knowledge and skills put into service for the good of others*" (Baernstein & Fryer-Edwards, 2005, p.742). In medicine, the nature of the specialist knowledge, and the complexity of expertise, conferred upon the profession the necessity of self-regulation '*in order to honour the social contract*' (Morgan, 2012, p.38). And although the idea of the social contract began as early as

the Greek Sophists, it gained traction in the 17th and 18th century in the work of Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau and more recently refined in Rawls (1979) in *A Theory of Justice*. Accordingly, Waugh (1993, p.132) outlines that such a contract exists “*when two groups within a society, between which a state of mutual dependence exists, recognize certain expectations of one another and conduct their affairs according to those expectations*”. In healthcare then, this is an implicit dynamic between a population and their providers. And despite the variance in work carried out by associations and institutions across the globe to refine what professionalism is in healthcare it normally results in some form of written charter, containing principals, which become a declaration of expectations upon which providers and consumers are intended to rely. However, *professionalism* must embrace a similar dynamic of interest as in Foucault’s governmentality, i.e., that it must be both individualising and totalising. By that is meant professionalism must capture the normative traits which are inherent in being a professional, and the positive collective behaviours of that group of actors in the profession. And according to Morgan (2012, p.40), midwifery as a profession, “*must sustain the covenant of trust that has long characterized the relationship between midwifery and those it serves.*” The question of whom midwifery serves becomes easier to comprehend in considering the contract, however, the relationship between woman and midwife seems rooted in covenant.

A contract, places certain conditions on a relationship, and if those conditions are not met, the relationship can be dissolved. As Lomasky (2010, p.50) points out, “*Contract is the dominant model for political philosophy’s understanding of government grounded on the consent of the governed.*” And while a contract can in that sense be ‘broken’ a covenant is a perpetual promise. Contract theory in economics has two broad perspectives. One based in law where a contract is an institutional arrangement limiting both the rights and obligations in transactional relationships. The second perspective focusses on *how* economic actors come to establish such relationships. A key element of contract is the dynamic of information asymmetry. In healthcare terms this is well associated with the dynamic between patient and professional as expert, the former of whom seeks help and the latter who holds the requisite knowledge to deliver it (Maatta, Lutzen & Oresland, 2016). Care is made here to avoid introducing a polemic of midwifery being right and government being wrong. Foucault after all in the 1970s was interrogative of professionals in medicine and psychiatry, with terms such as ‘biopolitics’ and the ‘disciplinary power of professionals’ (Foucault, 1974). Alongside terms

like 'expertocracy' (Gortz, 1993) and Illich's (1977) 'disabling professions', some authors trace such things the beginning of protracted debate about professional tendency to privilege their own interests above the common good and exist in elitist vacuums (Knijn, Duyvendak, & Kremer, 2006). In the case of midwifery however, where a core professional drive is to advocate for women, the arguments about the superiority of professionals and subordination of patients might not hold, since birthing women are not patients.

However, from a professional position it is clear than in normal birthing this asymmetry is something which the midwifery covenant strives to minimize by advocating for informed choices for women. It could however be inferred from participants in this thesis that perhaps a power-asymmetry exists between midwives and their employers. A core element of professionalism however is the principal of discretionary decision making once a professional has obtain license (Evetts, 2014). Part then of the midwifery covenant is arguably outside the boundary of the contract (Smith, 2004). Therefore, if midwives are practicing in a primarily *contracted* dynamic based on policy and prescribed practice, it is perhaps the professional covenant with women which either lubricates the dynamic in the form of a purposeful professional reminder, or which is the locus of practices of resistance. However, midwifery has been noted as nested within a dominant discourse of NHS healthcare. It is not unreasonable then to consider that a dominant governmental momentum premised on minimising errors would see the midwifery covenant as secondary and the contract between state and workers as primal. If for no other reason than the covenant is difficult to quantify, and the contract can be driven to a binary audit of success of failure: in or out of the discourse of employment.

Nevertheless, the 'human condition' is itself subordinate to existential threats that subjectify people as vulnerable by their dependence on the expertise of others. In healthcare terms, those professionals are expected to offer relief and respond by promising and committing (the literal meaning of the Latin verb 'to profess') to deploy that expertise in service to the public (Welie, 2012). However, a form of reciprocal dynamic exists if considering the trust placed by the public in those who provide the services of those professionals: a triad of public, professional, and state. In public sector healthcare this establishes midwifery as a social entity as well as a clinical one. Nevertheless, Foucault's focus on the art of government and on

biopower, illustrates well the subtle differences in the contract and the covenant. For example, by regulating the work of the Nursing Midwifery Council, government control both the professional contract and the economic contract. Yes, a deep covenant exists between midwifery and women, but the contents of learning curricula, the standards of competency, and code of behaviours are by proxy the charge of government to adjust, as has been shown. And whilst the professional skills, knowledge and behaviour are an integral part of professionalism i.e., the obligation of the profession to advance, innovate and improve (Morgan, 2012; Borrelii, 2016; Newnham & Rothman, 2022) this has been determined for adjustment by government. Equally, by stating in law that a subject cannot refer to themselves as midwife if they are not part of the governmental dispositif, or subsequently enter employment contract by the same juridical restriction, midwives are prevented from entering the economic state. The traditional view of the social contract, in governmental terms, can be seen as a politico-social contract. The midwifery covenant, in governmental terms, is being *contractualised* with a view to becoming *bureaucratized*.

7.5 Bureaucratization

Whilst bureaucracy as a concept, if not by name, has existed since Sumerian times in various forms, it is commonly associated with the work of Max Weber. And whilst others have developed his thoughts, from Wilson, to Merton, to Jaques, its arguable mainstay is around systems of organisation and administration (Runciman, 2002). However, according to Oniel (1986), Weber's analysis of the bureaucratic state and economy does draw certain parallels with Foucault's work on the disciplinary society (Foucault, 1978;1979). Equally, Foucault's work around docile bodies and the regimentation of the prison, the factory, and views of discursive forces, compare with Weber's historical account of the bureaucratic state and economy (Oneil, 1986). Whilst some credit Weber as the founder of organisational theory, they also suggest few have come closer in continuing Weber's work in organisational analysis that Foucault (Clegg, 1994). Both however shared an unease for the impact of cultural rationalisation upon 'the leading of life' or, more precisely, the influence of instrumental rationality on individual freedom (Gane, 2002). Furthermore, Gordon (1987, p.293) claims both shared an interest in what Weber called "*the power of rationality over men*".

However, in establishing the process of bureaucratisation as a form of governmentality in midwifery, Foucault's ideas around biopower are useful to highlight alongside Weber's ideas in illustrating how this can be seen. For example, Foucault views 'the self' as being moulded within a discourse over time by being subjected to the regulatory power within it (Barker 2008). In this view midwives are seen as subjectified to become a product of power *and* history. However, his concept of biopower arguably concerns the administration and regulation of individuals but doing so by directing that at the level of population. In seeing midwifery as a population in this way bonds identity to power (Rogers, Castree & Kitchin, 2013). This can be better illustrated by viewing his two targets for biopower as two potencies, but which act simultaneously: 'anatomo-politics' of the body (disciplinary power) and a 'biopolitical power' acting at the level of population. In Foucault's original works the former is claimed to have acted via institutions such as hospital, prison, and schools. In this way institutions are seen as "*disciplinary sites* which create docile bodies where people are '*subjected, used, transformed and improved*" (Foucault 1977, p.136), and in his view biopolitical power "*administers life*" (Foucault 1978, p.138). In this way biopolitical power are sets of forces which aim to "*optimise*" the life of populations (Foucault 1978, p.139). Foucault's suggestion is not that overt elements of juridical power have been replaced, such as issues of professional malpractice, but rather that biopower is a way to view the covert filaments of forces which operate alongside the juridical. In terms of bureaucratisation as a form of governmentality, what is proposed is not a plan for a singular *state* of bureaucracy, rather it is a foregrounding of the *desire* of government to adjust its socio-political contract with midwifery and in doing so altering the professional covenant. When considering for example Foucault's claims in *The Will to Knowledge* around biopower he refers to "*power that exerts a positive influence on life, that endeavours to administer, optimize, and multiply it, subjecting it to precise controls and comprehensive regulations*" (Foucault, 1978p.137). From this can be drawn a bureaucratic desire to limit the actions of subjects toward prescribed levels of accuracy, and this is seen in the regulation of midwifery professional standards and codes of conduct. Equally, and an organisational level these collections of forces repeated and optimised, implying a management of performance in the activity of subjects. Likewise, at the level of institution a surveillance of activity can be inferred, as well as the possible desire to replicate more of the optimised subjects. Together these can be seen as idealised facets of a landscape of administration which are seen in Weber's ideas which are outlined here.

It would be difficult to argue that competent systems of public management and administration have no place in a state economy. However, exactly which mechanisms work best is unclear, and much of the literature on the fragility of states suggests a greater understanding of what happens when elements are absent rather than how to construct effective bureaucracies (Besley et al, 2022). But based on his original works (Weber, 1922), we can characterise a modern bureaucracy as a formalised rule-driven arrangement, based broadly on containing appropriately competent individuals and some form of hierarchical control structure. He accentuates the individual motivation of the ideal bureaucrat as deontologically aligned to the mission of office. And in turn this loyalty is exchanged for security within the arrangement. However, these are terms when arranged like this, are not difficult to compare with the benefits and apparatus of professionalism, professionals, and professions (Ritzer, 1975). It is wrong however to suggest that Weber espoused some sense of stationary, epistemically tedious state-oppression within a bureaucracy. Rather he emphasises the appropriateness and durability of expertise in implementing public policies which contrast sharply with the arguably capricious politicians who in UK healthcare come and go with regularity (Besley et al, 2022). His wider thoughts however in Volume 1 of *Society and State* are useful in seeing bureaucratisation as a form of governmentality when noting his interest in rational actions and any deviations from that rationality. His views are similar to Foucault in seeing power as being relational, however Weber speaks of types of 'social actions' and the 'social relationship', describing this as, "*the behaviour of a plurality of actors insofar as, in its meaningful context, the action of each takes account of that of the others and is oriented in these terms*"(p.26). However, while Weber and Foucault both speak of power relations as being 'dominant' in certain conditions, some departure can be seen in this regard when considering Weber's definition of power alongside Foucault's biopower. Of the latter, Burchel, Gordon and Miller (1991) note Foucault's biopower provides examples of strategic reversibility in relations of power, and the terms of governmental practice, which can be turned to focus on resistance. As Foucault describes in his 1978 lectures, the history of government as the conduct of conduct is entwined with the history of counter-conduct (Foucault, 1978). However, in establishing bureaucratisation as a *momentum* in governmentality, it is important to note Weber's view of not only power, but of domination, in particular his legitimacy of states of domination. This can then be related to and further

justified by Machiavelli, in particular around Foucault's interpretation of political sovereignty. Together these premises will now illustrate the element of territory as a governmental rationality and the de-professionalisation of midwifery as a governmental technology.

Weber (1992) appears to see power and domination as outcomes of potential influence, which is perhaps not unusual in systems of management or administration. For Weber power is *"the probability that one actor within a social relationship will be in a position to carry out his own will despite resistance, regardless of the basis on which this probability rests"* (p.53). Furthermore, in terms of his view of domination he states, *"the probability that a command with a given specific content will be obeyed by a given group of persons"* (p.53). But the most significant interpretation of Weber's work is in showing his forms of legitimacy in states of domination as forms of authority, the *charismatic*, the *traditional*, and the *legal-rational*. Traditional authority is characterised by customs, and therefore rules are followed based on their traditional status. *"Commands are legitimised in terms of action which is bound to specific traditions and by action which is free of specific rules, falling within a sphere of discretion"* (p.227). However, of the charismatic, Weber views this as a form of *leadership*, noting that charismatic authority confers almost supernatural status upon an individual who is seen as something extraordinary (Breuilly, 2011). It would not be unreasonable to view such things as within the realms of modern servant leadership or heroic leadership, the main point being the inference in its consequent of generating followers. However, of the charismatic grounds of dominance he notes, *"There is no hierarchy; the leader merely intervenes in general or in individual cases when he considers the members of his staff lacking in charismatic qualification for a given task"* (p.243). A leader here then is easy to see as a manager in problem-solving environments. He notes however that such authority cannot remain stable. Nonetheless, his view confers legal authority on rational grounds, and in structuring it's agency around a hierarchy adopts *"that most unambiguous structure of domination, the bureaucracy"* (p.219). It is possible to consider charismatic authority as comparable to a professional environment where knowledge/experience and an a less formal authority associated with 'the expert'. When linked to Weber's claims of instability one can view a profession being 'left to its own devices' as being challenging if seen through a lens of public administration. When seen alongside traditional authority and the building over time of repeated legitimised practices it is possible to infer a picture not only of Foucault's discourse

but of professional identity, with *“action which is free of specific rules, falling within a sphere of discretion”* (p.227). Arguably it is that space for discretion which is the professional autonomy which has been contested by the governmental adjustments shown in midwifery regulation and noted by participants in this thesis. If it is possible to consider the two polar extremes, no matter their ridiculousness, in order that the governmental shift could better be seen. On the one hand midwifery is left to be the sole arbiter of normal childbirth based on ‘expertocracy’, be completely autonomous from the interfering state, but based on reciprocal trust in its relationship with state *and* where no errors in its practice conferred responsibility toward the state. In this extreme scenario the needs of birthing women are the legitimising authority. The alternative being, midwifery is integrated within a political bureaucracy which as Weber explains, is a state in which *“the dominant norms are concepts of straightforward duty without regard to personal considerations”* (p.225). And where bureaucracy has the effect of social levelling and *“everywhere bureaucratization foreshadows democracy”* (p.226). In this way any discretionary midwifery space is annulled, and women’s authority subsumed to be re-administered in a way which is most economically efficient for the wider apparatus of state. It is not far-fetched to see the zenith of such rationalities and technologies as robotised, algorithmic practice, with welcome predictability of minimal errors. The voluminous arguments of state and the problematics of power are beyond the scope of this thesis, however, if only to emphasise the point above, reference is made to Nietzsche of whom Foucault is known to have admired.

“The state is the coldest of all cold monsters...[it] lies in all languages of good and evil; and whatever it says it lies - and whatever it has, it has stolen...only there, where the state ceases, does the man who is not superfluous begin...”

(Nietzsche, cited in Miller and Rose, 1991, p.33)

Foucault highlights in his lecture on governmentality in February of 1978 that Machiavelli’s work can be seen as focussing on the dynamic between the prince and an established territory. But of interest to the art of government is the distillation of rationality as the need for the prince to maintain that territory. Foucault is able to help us frame this ongoing struggle of maintaining sovereign territory, to a modern rationality of political sovereignty. By that is meant the distillation of the sovereign political rationality to maintain its’ territory, but not of

borders, but of “*of things*” (Foucault, 1978; cited in Burchell, Gordon & Miller, p.101). From this can be inferred that public sector maternity care is a core part of political territory operating at a macro-level of power dynamics. The midwifery profession can be argued as a group of citizens within that maternity territorial modality. Kirkup (2015), on the heels of Francis (2013), appears to have targeted midwifery as a group of citizens, a population for adjustment, because the focus from these two reports moved the gaze toward governmental competence, public trust, therefore popularity and thus threatening political sovereignty. In this scenario Machiavelli may have advised the prince of ‘the need to be seen to be’ (conduct of conduct of conduct, Gillies, 2013). A second argument can be made in terms of territory, and that is around the spaces for professional discretionary practice. In this way the autonomy and professional decision-making of professionals are seen as risky territory, reclaimed by the political sovereign. No claim is made here of a governmental desire to dominantly *supress* midwifery practice, rather to redesign parts of it which are potential risks to the political sovereign may arise in terms of threatening its ability to stabilise its territorial longevity, likely compelled by the temporal nature of UK electoral terms in office. In governmental terms the political sovereign must, as Weber noted, generate a sense of duty to the office in return for the protection afforded from being part of a bureaucratic rationality. And what it must *supress* are events which threaten that office, in the case of maternity care that threat comes from errors. The rationality of territorial political protectionism as a governmental desire, forms the subsequent leadership target for implementation via strategy, and institutionally normative practices. It is therefore not suppression at all, rather it is a systematically adjusted type of unending performances, as one of Fairclough’s (1992, p.8) “*technologisations of discourse*”. The political sovereign must be able to confer public trust and popularity from it’s performance as governors, and therefore midwifery must be part of that performance. Either as a metric of poor performance, or as a justification for even greater emphasis to be placed upon it, the data from NHS Resolution, offers some legitimacy. Of the £13.6 billion spent on clinical errors in 2021-22, 60% was in maternity, or £8.16 billion for the year. NHS England spent £3 billion on delivering maternity services in the same year (NHS Resolution, 2022; Thomas, 2022). As a governed public system of maternity care, it is not difficult to see why performance improvement would be a natural focus. The actions, strategies, and technologies which are decided as a result by government would likely exist in an environment of complexity. It is therefore unlikely that singular solutions to improved

performance would be able to be isolated and determinable. As such it would seem prudent that all subjects within its governmental reach were engaged in environmental conditions which normalised the primacy to perform.

7.7 Performativity

Performativity is not merely a view of performance management, rather, like Foucault's biopower it alludes to the powerful relationships between indicators of performance and the subjectivity of both professionalism and professional identity. For brevity, the view offered here is aligned largely to Ball's work and Foucault and does not offer critique of the topic from its progenitors, such as Austin (1962), Lyotard (1986), Derrida (1988) or Butler (1990; 1993). In the realms of a governmental rationality noted earlier, performativity reveals the effects of subjective forces on the management of the self and Foucault calls these 'arts of existence' (Foucault, 1992). Technologies of performativity are a way to see the associations between institutional relations and individual practices. And to see beyond the highly visible legal-rational limits of activity, to the subtle practices of stimulation which encompass our own moral being as a lever of adjustment. Much as leadership claims to connect with a human internal imperative, over and above the simple cost-benefit instrumentality of management, *"Performativity invites and incites us to make ourselves more effective, to work on ourselves to improve ourselves and to feel inadequate if we do not"* (Ball, 2010, p.125). These levers to perform therefore exist within our minds and moral core and have the ability to have us mould our ethical selves *"those intentional and voluntary actions by which men not only set themselves rules of conduct, but also seek to transform themselves, to change themselves in their singular being, and to make their life into an oeuvre"* (Foucault, 1992 p.10). Activities which are institutionally commonplace, which judge the worth of subjects *overtly*, have the effect of legitimising and internalising these *covertly* in the way in which we value our own worth. This has the effect not of oppression, but as a mechanism of reward, satisfaction, and adjustment. In this form of normative existence, leadership is no longer an existential theory to be repeated in programmes of activity toward making evermore new leaders, rather the ability to direct and influence is within the subjects in the discourse.

As a political technology, performativity works best in the context of a neoliberal normative landscape. In such an environment, for the subject the possibilities of success, achievement but more importantly of recognition are many (Davies, 2005). In this way they become

“subjects which have to be seen” (Foucault, 1979, p. 187). In reflection of previous claims about the contract and the covenant however, *“The neo-liberal subject is malleable rather than committed, flexible rather than principled – essentially depthless”*. (Ball, 2010, p. 126). And in Weber’s view of the bureaucracy, the institution, and the professionals within it become essentially the same object. *“The self-managing individual and the autonomous organisation are produced within the interstices of performativity through audits, inspections, appraisals, self-reviews, quality assurance, research assessments, output indicators etc”* (Ball, 2010, p.126). Questions then can be asked of potential de-professionalisation by replacement of the values of professionalism, with neoliberal economic value. For example, in midwifery the demands made by a performative governmentality in the extreme, would misalign with the motivation to enter and remain within the professional world. A clash of discourses of professionalism versus one of employerism. Their performative practices would become ‘inauthentic’ in a professional sense but valuable in an economic one. Such things as commitment to woman, would become a need to generate the *impression* of commitment. The vital relationship between the birthing woman and her midwife becomes one of *calculability* rather than *memorability*. But an idealised performative environment has a way to resolve that as it's reach is to the level of the moral soul, as such it musters the sense of letting the side down, of guilt in the pursuit of goals which might not support midwifery colleagues. Part of the neoliberal landscape and the normalisation of performativity also creates uncertainties. Likewise, Shore and Wright (1999) note these uncertainties make subjects susceptible to leadership. In light of the need to be seen, organisational leadership messages of potential promotion, the grandeur offered by a leadership title, the economic agency offered by larger salary could outweigh professional leadership messages of selfless determination to improve the lives of birthing women. Shore and Wright (1999) even claim the creation of such performative uncertainties are a general tactic in discourse of public sector management and administration.

However, for the topic of leadership, a performative discourse is useful in that it moves the binary debate from leadership as being pluralistic with management (Denis, Langley & Sergi, 2012), or being purely relational (Cunliffe & Eriksen, 2011), and moves argument toward one considering leadership in the socio-political environment. Leadership becomes *“less attributable to the actions of individual leaders, but rather as continuously constituted in the*

ongoing creative and improvisational movements that bring about change in the trajectories of social action" (Simpson & Buchan, 2018, p.645). However, performativity as an art of government, captures a more interesting leadership trifecta; the *human-to-human* capacity, be that practices, or strategies of practices; the *institution* as a normative social amplifier; and the *governance of the self* as a modality of sustainability in governmental form. However, the art of government is strategically intentional, in that it strives to inflict in some way, the will of the one, upon a group of others. But rather than simply leading by 'influence' in traits of charisma or inspiration etc there are limitations placed on the abilities of subjects to resist. Governing the self in this environment however is a result of an economisation of life, or of living, and performativity allows us to see that responsabilisation of the living subject is not simply compliance, it is a form of embodiment of government, as self-governance. As Shamir (2008, p. 4) explains, "*responsibility is the practical master-key of governance*". The entrepreneurial self within this discursive norm is tasked furtively with the repeated creation of self-value (Poz, 2019). In this way governmental leadership is 'seen but not heard' and largely self-sustainable, provided the institution-subject relationship is active and participatory within the context of the wider econometrics of life. Nonetheless, for governmental intention to be normalised in discourse, subjects at all levels of organising have to perform within boundaries, around which the art of governing must be able to generate urgency but also impart deterrents from deviation. The concepts of internalisation and responsabilisation of the self as a willing and constitutive part of that apparatus of performativity can be seen as part of a corporate intention. For example, drawing on Foucault (1980), Knights and Morgan (1991, p.251) analyse corporate strategy "*as a discourse which has its own specific conditions of possibility*". In their article titled 'Corporate strategy, organizations, and subjectivity: A critique', they show corporate strategy as discursive formation by representing it, "*as a set of discourses and practices which transform managers and employees alike into subjects who secure their sense of purpose and reality by formulating, evaluating and conducting strategy*" (Knights & Morgan, 1991, p. 252). This is useful in seeing the effects of power relations in a corpus of encouragements and limitations when considered a governmental perspective of midwifery, and which overcomes any over-simplicity of management as authority. As they highlight, "*managers and staff are not just passive victims of the power of strategic discourse; through it they are constituted as subjects either in support of, or in resistance to, its plausibility*" (Knights & Morgan, 1991, p. 269). And where

encouragements and limitations were toward a normalised performativity they offer, “*both those who embrace and those who resist strategy find themselves caught up in its reproduction*” (p. 269).

In a UK healthcare perspective, but in the hope of avoiding the diatribe of the *transformation thesis* (Osborne, 2010; Sørensen and Torfing, 2007), it is possible to see the following pattern in leading midwifery in the recent historical context. *Government* as a corporeal political sovereign, and *governance* as the strategies of instructed adjustment and regulation, with *self-governance* toward political goals as the ultimate leadership target. Moreover, we can see the momentum for this conduit of governing as the *governmental rationality* of sustained territorial advantage, with the political *technology* of a normative environment of performativity toward maintaining that advantage. To achieve the leadership target noted, one could consider the alterations made to midwifery post-Kirkup as a type of midwifery biopolitical reform. However, those reforms do not only appear as demanded changes in what midwifery does, it leans toward changing what midwifery is, a shift toward a socio-political identity rather than a fully professional identity. Foucault himself seems to prefer the dissolution of identity, if for no other reason to focus on its historical construction. He sees identity as a form of subjugation and a way of exercising power over people, with a view to preventing them from moving outside fixed boundaries (O’Farrell, 2005). Nonetheless, healthcare professional identity, viewed through a lens of governmentally, is a political notion that is necessary for strategies of power through which human beings are made subjects (Mackey, 2007; Doolin, 2002).

Summary

The political direction and influence toward a government being seen to be able to govern, sits in stark contrast with midwifery professionalism. The former must deliver convincing performances to ensure its continued sovereignty within a capricious and unstable political electoral discourse. The latter has a singular locus around which to evolve and improve, that of women-centred care. Faced with a position of consecutive public investigations around poor performances in safety, this becomes the biggest risk to government, and likely why the drive to standardise and control has been pushed by successive governments for 40 years. This Chapter has shown that attempting to ‘clamp down’ on discretionary spaces for

professional decision-making has little if any value in healthcare, and participant midwifery leaders have offered similar views. And although likely never the intention, governmental approaches in healthcare can now be shown to be harmful to those professionals who are tasked with reducing harm to others. Likewise, such seemingly simplistic leadership targets are focussed on making healthcare staff feel a sense of kindness, inclusivity, and safety. The wave of governmental rationality focussed on tackling the fragile relationship between state and health professionals can be seen in the history of NHS litigation and commensurate policy responses. Likewise, the demand for increased blame and accountability is heard in the voices of the midwifery leaders in this research. The NHS cannot 'contract out' for better maternity care, it's only option is to adjust it within a discourse, or as one participant called it, 'the bubble'. But direction and influence in leading those changes are shifted from a flexible complementarity to a rigid no-option bureaucratisation, where following become compliance and enforcement. The antecedents of the governmental drift in midwifery were not Kirkup. Kirkup was a trigger episode that justified not leadership direction and influence, but a set of directives, legitimised in the minds of the political state. For example, the only 'evidence' that could perhaps be argued was that changing the way doctors were regulated could be carried over to midwifery. The approach chosen was not identifying the best evidence for midwifery care, it was the best 'ideas' in managing risk. The implanting of regulatory measures throughout the entire apparatus of professional midwifery life is itself a large-scale risk management programme. But I do not believe the risks to mothers and babies has actual primacy in that programme. According to some participants in this research, new versions of midwives have evolved whilst many others are, or plan to leave. The professional covenant in midwifery is a perpetual promise to the primacy of women at the heart of their ethical practice. But the magnitude of the contract of employment with government is arguably greater.

“A new scientific truth does not triumph by convincing its opponents and making them see the light, but rather because its opponents eventually die and a new generation grows up that is familiar with it”

Nobel Physicist and founder of quantum mechanics, Max Planck

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Appendix 1

Research Process

Prior to the thesis element of the Doctoral journey, the three prerequisite Level 12 modules were completed: Critical Professional Reflection, Research Theory and Design and Situated Professional Inquiry

Research Progression

1. Understanding Foucault's philosophy and methods, *to inform*,
2. Critical appraisal of the archive (list in Appendix?) *to inform*,
3. The ethics application, *by*,
 - a. creating the research protocol
 - b. improving the interview schedule (as panel of peers viewed not only as a point of permission but as a reflexive part of the rigour of the study)
 - c. approving a recruitment strategy (not just the who from the policy appraisal, but the how based on crossover into political, employment and legal discourses)
4. Recruit, interview and analyse data from 13 participants in leadership roles in midwifery, either directly by title or by agency role. For example, Nursing Midwifery Council, Government Department, Royal College of Midwives, *to inform*,
5. Consolidation and synthesis of both sources, i.e., the archive and the participant data, to formulate a representation of Foucault's perspective on midwifery leadership using Gillies (2013) as a scaffold and source of methodological reflexivity.

My background is public health. Defined by a previous 'independent inquiry' in healthcare by a knight of the sovereign, Sir Ronald Acheson in 1998 as *"the art and science of preventing disease, prolonging life and promoting health through the organized efforts of society"*. I was exposed to all of this archival knowledge around 'organising society' and stamped as a Master of Public Health (MPH) by the University of Glasgow in 2006. The UK Faculty of Public Health are very particular about the 'Master' part of that and that it mustn't be an MSc. I had little that was masterly at the time in my opinion, but the award allowed me to progress through the NHS grading at the time and apply for management positions, which I did three times in all. Speaking with former colleagues these positions are now named as leaders rather than managers. The point being I'd never viewed my career in that way, my own genealogy, until the end of this thesis. The power-knowledge validation from a dominant discourse or the elevated agency gained by individuals within the apparatus, the examination etc. I was very aware of some of Foucault's other concepts, such as 'truth games', governmentality, technologies of the self and particularly his view of ethics. I didn't however label them as that but on reflection I can narrow to within a few months, the point at which I began to recalibrate my own internal self to 'fit' within the governmental apparatus of 'state public health'. Foucault's critique is centred around the ways in which these organised elements of society, their relationships to power-knowledge and interplay with government come to be. To that end, I see his approach could easily be applied to the discourse of public health.

Insider/outsider but always in between

In this research endeavour I never chose a method or theory to explore an issue in midwifery. I chose Foucault as a philosopher of systems of thought and as a thinker who appeared to resist categorisation, and never quite fit in. I had applied every one of Foucault's ethical positions to myself to fit within the discourse of corporate public health. But nearing the completion of this thesis, I realise I demanded the same of my staff team as their 'leader' but without explicitly doing so. I have spoken with my former Director, who since retiring had drawn the same conclusion of her leaderly relationship with me. I was recruited to UWS 13 years ago to bolster public health in the School of Nursing and Midwifery. I spent the first year

trying to get back to the NHS as I most definitely did not fit in. At one point in the entire school, I was the only person not registered as a nurse or midwife, from Dean to Lecturers. I have heard countless times the phrase 'you're not a nurse' either as a question or a proclamation. I am placed within the Division of Midwifery teaching post-graduates, am 0.5 WTE in the Adult Nursing Division, teach Health Economics in the MPH in the Biological Sciences Division, and politics and policy in the Division of Mental Health Nursing. I am neither inside nor outside of midwifery. However, I can with conviction say I have observed midwife academics for these years in their conversations and mannerisms as being unique when compared to other colleagues in nursing for example. A sense of 'resistance,' were only one word allowed to describe it. On hearing conversations in my doctoral group about Kirkup (2015) in 2017 I was quickly able to engage in discussions around NHS management and governance based on my public health background. But I was struck by the irony of being employed in a university in a role which has never capitalised on that background. Only in the last year of this doctoral work has that frustration made sense. From one discourse to another and the partial loss of self, as it wasn't a requirement of fitting in. So this doctoral journey has been partially cathartic in the re-valuing of an 'insider claim' to policy creation, planning and commissioning as part of my historical discursive creation. On reflection my own genealogy enhanced the process of navigation through policy, strategy, and guidance, and familiarity with terminology. But also, being close to, but not within the midwifery profession has been valuable in enhancing the exploration within its leadership discourse.

Changed views on the value of P

At interview for the student place on the Professional Doctorate programme I stated my wish to do something that ended with a P value close to zero. Through grinning lips, the panel asked why? My reply was that I wanted to have something real at the end of six years. That alone is reflective of a philosophical absurdity which demonstrates growth. I teach differently, engage in conversations differently and now accept that some colleagues no longer engage with me because of those changes. I can see differently however, particularly in the organisation who employs me, and not everything I see as a result is pleasant. Foucault's methods, which emphasise rebellion toward equilibrium are incredibly powerful, but can weaponize and destabilise in ways which some discursive formations do not appreciate.

Appendix 3

Phase 1 archive analysis material

Position	Document	Date
Central Government	NHS Five Year Forward Review. NHS England	2014
	Nursing and Midwifery Council - amendments to modernise midwifery regulation and improve the effectiveness and efficiency of fitness to practise processes Government response. Department of Health	2017
	The Best Start: A Five-Year Forward Plan for Maternity and Neonatal Care in Scotland. Scottish Government	2018
	Neonatal Care in Scotland: A Quality Framework. Scottish Government	2013
	Learning not blaming: The government response to the Freedom to Speak Up consultation, the Public Administration Select Committee report 'Investigating Clinical Incidents in the NHS', and the Morecambe Bay Investigation. Department of Health	2015
	A Plan for Scotland: the government's programme for Scotland. Scottish Government	2017
	Midwifery supervision and regulation: recommendations for change. Parliamentary and Health Service Ombudsman	2013
	Proposals for changing the system of midwifery supervision in the UK. Policy paper. Department of Health and Social Care	2016
	The Report of the Morecambe Bay Investigation: An independent investigation into the management, delivery and outcomes of care provided by the maternity and neonatal services at the University Hospitals of Morecambe Bay NHS Foundation Trust from January 2004 to June 2013. Dr Bill Kirkup	2015
	National Maternity Review. Improving outcomes of maternity services in England: A Five Year Forward View for maternity care NHS England	2017
	Safer Maternity Care: Next steps towards the national maternity ambition. Department of Health	2016
	Interim NHS People Plan. NHS England	2019
	NHS Long Term Plan. NHS England	2019
	The Mid Staffordshire NHS Foundation Trust Public Inquiry. Sir Robert Francis	2013
	Promoting professionalism, reforming regulation. Department of Health and Social Care	2017
	Clinical Leadership Competency Framework. NHS Leadership Academy	2011

	Clinical leadership- a framework for action. A guide for senior leaders on developing professional diversity at board level. NHS Improvement.	2019
Regulatory	Midwifery Regulation in the United Kingdom. The Kings Fund. Commissioned by the NMC	2015
	Review of midwifery regulation. Council minutes in response to the Kings Fund Review, NMC	2015
	Regulation of health care professionals, regulation of social care professionals in England. Law Commission, Scottish Law Commission, Northern Ireland Law Commission	2014
	The Code: Professional standards of practice and behaviour for nurses, midwives and nursing associates. NMC	2018
	Future midwife: Standards of proficiency for midwives. NMC	2019
	Future midwife: Standards for pre-registration midwifery programmes. NMC	2019
	Realising professionalism: Standards for education and training Part 2: Standards for student supervision and assessment. NMC	2019
	Standards for competence for registered midwives. NMC	2009
	Emerging concerns protocol. All Health Regulatory Bodies	2018
	Enabling professionalism in nursing and midwifery practice. CNO England & Devolved Nations and NMC	2017
	Taking revalidation forward: Improving the process of relicensing for doctors. Sir Keith Pearson's review of medical revalidation. Commissioned General Medical Council	2017
Professional Standards Authority	Progress on strengthening professional regulation's approach to candour and error reporting. Advice to the Secretary of State for Health	2014
	Right-touch reform: A new framework for assurance of professions	2017
	Strategic review of the Nursing and Midwifery Council Final report	2012
	Regulating an occupation in fewer than all four UK countries Implications for policy-makers, the public, and practitioners <i>Advice for the Scottish Government</i>	2018
	Lessons Learned Review: The Nursing and Midwifery Council's handling of concerns about midwives' fitness to practise at the Furness General Hospital	
	Response to government consultation – Promoting professionalism, reforming regulation	2018
	Bad apples? Bad barrels? Or bad cellars? Antecedents and processes of professional misconduct in UK Health and Social Care: Insights into sexual misconduct and dishonesty	2017

Royal College of Midwives	State of Maternity Services Report – Scotland	2018
	The development, implementation and evaluation of a leadership programme for midwives.	2016
Health Improvement Scotland	Review of Ayrshire Maternity Unit, University Hospital Crosshouse, NHS Ayrshire & Arran (Adverse Events)	2017
Other		
Kings Fund	Safe Births: Everybody's business: An independent inquiry into the safety of maternity services in England	2008
	Staffing in maternity units: Getting the right people in the right place at the right time	2011
	Improving safety in maternity services: A toolkit for teams	2012
	Leadership and Leadership Development in Health Care: The Evidence Base	2015
	Leadership and engagement for improvement in the NHS. Together we can.	2012
	<i>The Future of Leadership and Management in the NHS: No more heroes.</i>	2011

Study Protocol

Contact Details: email [REDACTED]

Telephone: [REDACTED]

June 2019

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Exploring leadership in midwifery.

You are being invited to take part in a research study as part of a Professional Doctorate being undertaken by me at the University of the West of Scotland. Before you decide whether or not to participate it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve for you. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please contact me if you would like more information or if anything is not clear.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to explore the views of a range of professionals within the field of midwifery. Specifically, the study will explore the roles and mechanisms used to lead the profession both at a policy and practical level. This means asking questions in one-to-one interviews around the experiences and opinions of participants of the topic of leadership in midwifery.

Previous studies have shown this topic to be complex and multifaceted. For this reason, the study will engage individuals who are experienced midwives, who hold or have recently held a role which has some focus on leading the profession. This could be within a **clinical leadership role**, one in **policy development and regulation** or within **higher education**. Clarity of which of these areas you feel best represent your role will be agreed with you (However your employer or explicit role will not be highlighted anywhere in the study. Please see subsequent section on confidentiality)

What is a one-to-one interview?

This will be a closed interview with only the researcher and one participant at a time. Arrangements as to where this interview will take place will be agreed with the participant on an individual basis to ensure you feel at your most comfortable. The interview is then transcribed for analysis to allow me to collate and discuss these findings alongside the review of the current literature in this area which has already been conducted.

Why have you been invited?

You have been invited to take part because you are (or have recently been) working within the three areas highlighted above.

Do I have to take part?

No you do not. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you are interested in taking part you should contact me within the next 2 weeks of receiving this request. Even if you decide to take part you are free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you agree to take part in this study you will be invited to make an arrangement with me to agree a suitable place, time and format for the interview to take place. For example, it can take place in a venue of your choosing or include systems such as Skype. Before the session begins you will be asked to sign a consent form including consent for the interview to be audio recorded. Only you and I will be in the interview which will last no more than one hour. Confidentiality will be agreed at the beginning of the session and maintained throughout.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There is a very small risk that you could become anxious during the session due to the topic of discussion. In the unlikely event that this was to happen the session will be stopped and appropriate support would be offered to you. For example UWS Counselling Services 01292 886267 or counselling@uws.ac.uk.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The study is unlikely to directly impact on you as an individual. However, by sharing your personal and professional experiences and insights the study aims to gain a deeper understanding leading and therefore developing the midwifery profession. As the study, when published, will be shared with the wider professional community it will contribute to the literature and therefore body of knowledge in this area.

What if something goes wrong?

Any complaint about the way you have been dealt with during the study or any possible distress you might suffer will be addressed. You are free to contact the University Doctoral College who will refer your concerns or complaint onto the academic supervisor for this study. Telephone [REDACTED]

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

No data or subsequent analysis will **ever** be shared in a format which could identify you as a participant in the study, including your professional role. Ethical and legal practices will be followed and all information about you will be handled in strict

confidence. Data collected from the interviews will be recorded on a passcode protected electronic device, accessible exclusively to the researcher. The requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2018) will be adhered to and all written information will be kept confidential and locked in a filing cabinet at the researcher's office for 5 years. Electronic data gathered may be held on encrypted devices, accessible only by the researcher.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

It is intended that the results of this study will contribute towards a thesis for a Professional Doctorate at UWS. The information gathered in this study may also be used for publication in peer reviewed journals or for presentation at conferences. You will not be identified in any way in published work produced from the information gathered by this study.

Who is organising and funding the research?

The research is being organised by me, Stuart Telfer. The costs of which, if any, are met by me as student of the University.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been approved by the School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland. However, consent has been given by your employer and/or senior manager only to contact individuals (unnamed) to request your participation. This does not affect your right to refuse to participate.

Contact details

If you would like any further information, please do not hesitate to contact me via email [REDACTED] or by telephone on [REDACTED] or [REDACTED]. Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Appendix 5

Example of coding by hand participant interviews, noted in Chapter 2

revalidated.

↳ [] @ quote (Note: empty response)

Me; and unfortunately, I would be able to reflect that in other conversations had across strata in this work, and that's...

D; In supervision, you had an ongoing relationship with a senior midwife who could get feedback and observe you, I mean my supervisees I worked alongside them at least one whole shift a year, I knew how they talked to women, I knew how they...whether they were...this is just nothing really.

Me; is the implication there from what you're saying, that the previous version of supervision was in some sense actually safer than the new version?

D; Yes, and um it had improved hugely over the time of my career, it was becoming far more proactive, perhaps that's the problem with it, now...I'm not saying that they didn't screw up in the north west of England but...and it was improving. I'd seen in improving over nearly 40 years, so it was really a shame

other? CODE'S PERFORMANCE. EVENT.

Handwritten notes and codes:

- ↳ [] @ quote
- (Note: empty response)
- ↑
- CODE: IDENTITY
- SUB CODE: TRUST
- CODE: SCENARIOS
- CODE: SUBORDINATE
- SUB: TWO DISCOURSES EMPLOYER / PROFESSION
- CODE: PROCEDURE
- PROFESSION
- desire

Appendix 6

Copy of FOI Request to establish financial sums paid to the private sector investigation of maternity failures in Shrewsbury & Telford NHS Trust

Dear Mr Telfer,

Freedom of Information Request Reference

Freedom of Information Team Department of Health and Social Care 39 Victoria Street London SW1H 0EU

www.gov.uk/dhsc

19 November 2021

Thank you for your request dated 28 September 2021 in which you asked the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC):

“Can I please request the financial cost of Donna Ockendon’s Investigation into Maternity services in Shrewsbury & Telford. As the final report has not been completed I’m happy to be guided by a final total cost via trajectory or where that has been capped and/or agreed. However the cost of reaching this point in the timeline should be available which I’d like to have please for my own research into maternity safety.”

Your request has been handled under the Freedom of Information Act 2000 (FOIA).

I can confirm that DHSC holds information relevant to your request.

However, we consider that this information is exempt under Section 35(1)(a) of the FOIA, which provides protection for information that relates to the formulation or development of government policy. Section 35 is a qualified exemption, and requires consideration of the public interest test.

We are withholding this information under Section 35 because the findings and recommendations of the Ockenden Review will be considered by the Government in formulating and developing future policy relating to NHS maternity services. The Review is still ongoing, and the final report has not yet been delivered to Government and NHS England and Improvement (NHSEI). The Government and NHSEI’s response and development of future policy cannot be made until the recommendations of the Ockenden Review that will be delivered in its final report have been considered.

We are required to assess as objectively as possible whether the balance of the public interest favours disclosing or withholding information under Section 35 of the FOIA.

The Department recognises a general public interest in promoting openness in the way in which public authorities manage major current events and in transparency in relation to public spending. However, the purpose of the exemption at Section 35 is to protect the internal deliberative process as it relates to policy making. In other words, the exemption is intended to ensure that the possibility of public exposure does not deter from full, candid and proper deliberation of policy formulation and development, including the exploration of all options, the keeping of detailed records and the taking of difficult decisions. Premature

disclosure of information protected under section 35 could prejudice good working relationships, the perception of civil servants' neutrality, and ultimately, the quality of Government.

We consider that the disclosure of the information requested at this stage would result in scrutiny of the conduct of the Review, which could risk its delivery and objectivity. In the circumstances, we consider that the public interest in withholding this information outweighs the public interest in disclosing it.

If you are not satisfied with the handling of your request, you have the right to appeal by asking for an internal review. This should be sent to FreedomOfInformation@dhsc.gov.uk or to the address at the top of this letter and be submitted within two months of the date of this letter.

Please remember to quote the reference number above in any future communication.

If you are not content with the outcome of your internal review, you may complain directly to the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Generally, the ICO cannot make a decision unless you have already appealed our original response and received our internal review decision. You should raise your concerns with the ICO within three months of your last meaningful contact with us.

The ICO can be contacted at:

The Information Commissioner's Office Wycliffe House
Water Lane
Wilmslow SK9 5AF

<https://ico.org.uk/concerns/>

Yours sincerely,

Freedom of Information Officer

freedomofinformation@dhsc.gov.uk

1. Could you give a brief summary of your journey up to this point in midwifery, how did you get here?

2. What is the very first thing that comes to mind if I ask you who or what leads midwifery?

3. When people talk about leadership it often means there are followers. Why and how do midwives follow?
 - a. Willingness
 - b. Guidance
 - c. Inspired
 - d. No choice

4. There is a great deal of pathways, guidance, standards around what midwives do. How do they fit into leading?
 - a. Safety
 - b. Evidence
 - c. No choice
 - d. Expectations

5. What role do the NMC have in influencing what midwives do and is any of that seen as leadership in some way
 - a. Followers
 - b. Safety
 - c. Control

6. There have been some fairly big changes in midwifery in the last 5-10 years. Any thoughts on what they are, how they influenced the profession
 - a. Accidents
 - b. Supervision
 - c. Revalidation
 - d. Safety

7. The RCM, they're a union but are described as an advocate or a voice for midwives. What are they advocating for, or against whom, why a voice?
 - a. Professional body/voice
 - b. Resistance
 - c. Interplay NMC/NHS